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**NO TEACHER LEFT OFFLINE: A HERMENEUTIC STUDY OF ONLINE
COMMUNICATION AND RELATIONSHIP BUILDING FOR NEAR-RETIREMENT
EDUCATORS AT UNIVERSITIES IN MANILA, PHILIPPINES**

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27 August 2024

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **KRIZELLE R. AMOYO** with the title: **“NO TEACHER LEFT OFFLINE: A HERMENEUTIC STUDY OF ONLINE COMMUNICATION AND RELATIONSHIP BUILDING FOR NEAR-RETIREMENT EDUCATORS AT UNIVERSITIES IN MANILA, PHILIPPINES”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

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Biographical Sketch

Krizelle R. Amoyo is from General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite. After finishing her basic education at Colegio San Agustin-Binan, she went on to earn a Bachelor of Arts in Communication from Far Eastern University-Manila. While exploring various media opportunities, she discovered a passion for event management. However, life took an unexpected turn, leading her to a private educational institution. This new path ignited her passion for teaching and allowed her to support her colleagues as an online class coordinator.

Acknowledgment

Looking back, I would always regard this journey as my leap of faith amidst the chaos. I took a chance to apply to the university during the pandemic, when everything was uncertain in so many aspects of my life. From application, braving my first class, cramming my submissions, waiting for grades to be posted, to finishing the revisions to writing this, it would not have been possible without the immense support of the people around me.

To my family, Papa, Mama, Ate, Max, and my guardian angel, Yuki, your endless '*kaya mo yan!*' and '*we're proud of you!*' helped me push through after countless '*ayoko na*'.

To my friends and colleagues, please know that our random conversations, dates, and just your mere existence gave me comfort and peace. Thank you for being you.

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To my participants, your heart and passion for education will always be my standard when it comes to being the teacher I strive to be. I am lucky to be able to listen to and learn from your stories. Thank you for being an inspiration.

And lastly, to our Creator. I owe it all to you. I always remind myself that I should not worry about anything because, even if things do not happen the way I want **them** to, knowing that you are in control puts my heart at peace. This is all you, Lord.

Dedication

For all teachers, educators, professors, ma'ams, sirs, and everyone shaping the youth, thank you for being an inspiration.

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Abstract

Purpose:

The pandemic forced a shift in the mode of delivery in education. Forcing everyone to migrate to the online platform just to make learning and communication possible. The platform is one thing, but paying attention to the sender of the message in the educational context is also a must to ensure effectiveness despite the trials. With near-retirement educators or those who belong to the baby boomer generation regarded as the tenured and respected individuals in the field, we must ensure support and assistance to help them navigate their way through an unmastered territory. This study seeks to understand the experiences of near-retirement educators and how they adapt to the obligatory online communication setup for relationship-building with their students.

Data Gathering:

Through purposeful sampling, four near-retirement educators were invited to a one-on-one interview where they shared narratives during the shift to fully online communication. Interviews were recorded, transcribed, and following the Hermeneutic approach, analyzed and interpreted.

Findings:

Four main themes emerged from the analysis that directly answered the research questions: (1) 'Cause of Disconnect' that focuses on the challenges and hurdles of the participants; (2) 'Triumph to Reconnect' that expounds on their wins and successes; (3) 'Switching Gears' that narrates their changed practices to adapt to the situation; and lastly, (4) 'Embracing the Change' that highlights their key learning and lessons they can impart as veterans in the field of education. These four main themes can be further analyzed with the help of three to four sub-themes present, respectively.

Conclusion:

Due to the haste generalization that we subject baby boomers to, we sometimes forget that the year a person is born or their age shall never be the sole determinant of how we perceive their actions. With a strong prejudice toward close-mindedness and receptivity to advancements, we box these individuals without knowing that they are more than that. The years under their belt should be seen as a sign of dedication, for they are driven by heart and fueled by passion, which resulted in their willingness to adapt to changes and embrace challenges for the welfare of their students. Ultimately, it will take more than a shift of mode and an unfamiliar platform before you can take a strong-willed individual like the four participants.

Keywords:

Online Communication in Education, Baby Boomers, Online Communication Practices, Relationship Building in Education, Intergenerational Communication

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The existence and maximization of the digital platform have been our tools for complementing the traditional practices in our everyday lives (Patella, 2022). However, as much as it aids and supports every sector or industry we have, it is proven that its progression and integration into the Philippine education system are laggard until March 2020 (Ngwacho, 2020). During the pandemic, education has been redefined as we welcome the total shift to online education (Tria, 2020). According to Barnes (2016), despite transitioning to online communication, the purpose and goal remain the same: to share knowledge, interact, and build connections. And this has been made possible by the exemplified social presence of the instructor. This counters the notion that online learning minimizes or even removes the presence of the educator (Berge & Clark, 2009, p. 4, as cited in Barnes, 2016), because, by principle and application, this form of learning requires more from the involved parties, especially in the area of communication. Aside from planning and executing their lessons, educators must now sharpen their orientation of their students to communicate accordingly, strengthen their Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills, and get acquainted with computer-mediated communication (CMC) to keep up with the demands of establishing interaction, a strong connection, and a relationship with their students despite the lack of in-person communication. This has introduced various experiences in communication between teacher-student

relationships since adaptation became mandated and no longer an option, especially when it comes to maximization and utilization of communication on the online platform.

Baby Boomers, born between 1946 to 1964, were exposed to advancements in the latter part of their lives, thus being called 'digital immigrants' (Venter, 2017; Bennett-Kapusniak, 2015; as cited in Puspitasari et al., 2021). But being the generation that is the reason for online learning's birth and triumph, this generation acknowledges technology as it is. Seeing it as an aid to how they can better their lives, but not to the point of it shaping their reality, the way the younger generation uses it (Huyler & Ciocca, 2016). These qualities are manifested in how they play a role as teachers in a student's life. In a traditional teacher-student relationship, Baby Boomers or our near-retirement educators still seek to utilize face-to-face communication (Venter, 2017). Feedback was given in person, consultation was done inside the classroom, utilization of technology is optional, and other practices shape how they build a sense of community in education. However, with the situation's imposition, our educators shifted to another platform to make communication and education happen. Baby Boomers or near-retirement educators are forced and pressured to learn and adapt to these changes, abandoning their prior practice inside their classrooms (Huyler & Ciocca, 2016). Although not alien to these types of communication advancements (Huyler & Ciocca, 2016), it takes a lot on the end of the educators for this to be mastered, or at least, be accustomed to. In other words, the age difference between teacher **and** student is a consideration in communication in itself, but adding the complexity of the platform can lead to different narratives and experiences of our older generation of educators.

Being one of the coordinators of online learning in a private university, where the implementation of blended learning existed pre-pandemic as classes were conducted

three days face-to-face and two days online, the provision of training and support for effective online education has been a must. I am fortunate enough to be a part of the committee that plans for the training and monitoring of the faculty and students. That means being in charge of the know-how of all types of users of the online learning management system. However, since online communication is just an option during that time, some older educators still opt to communicate during face-to-face meetings and just use the online days to upload materials and worksheets. But once the pandemic hit, online communication became an obligation that pushed our near-retirement educators to embrace this phenomenon, making it a daily occurrence to hear and witness the triumphs and troubleshooting struggles when it comes to establishing online communication between teachers and students. Active participation and interaction are anticipated to create meaning and a sense of community in learning (Nabila et al., 2020). More than the students, teachers are much more expected to take the lead in making the interaction possible and stronger. That means bridging gaps and making a continuous effort to reach out to the learners. These efforts are exerted with the intent of avoiding possible communication breakdowns (Manuaba & Putra, 2021) that can be brought about by different factors and considerations. With the help of the participants from different universities in NCR, this study can shed new light on how my role in the institution can further extend help and assistance to our tenured faculty when it comes to online communication. Crossing the boundary means that our role is not just concerned with the implementation of online learning but also has the best intention of providing support when it comes to online communication to establish relationships between teachers and students. As the stories from the participants were gathered, their best practices can be our benchmark in enhancing our system, and those that are noted to be hurdles

were points for improvement without taking them against the participant. Despite the conflict that might arise given the connection between my designation and the topic at hand, my position remains objective, and I shall act with the sole aim of having a deeper understanding of the experiences of our near-retirement educators.

Even though some older educators chose to retire rather than adapt (Ahituv & Zeira, 2011; Zamaro et al., 2021), we have to pay attention to those who stayed. Not to mention the infrequency of studies that focus on this matter (Frey, 2019). However, various components are required, such as knowledge and orientation, the drive of the actual user, and technological literacy and skills. Once these complement and supplement each other, it strengthens the purpose of communication in education through teacher-student interaction (Cho, 2021). Despite Baby Boomers not being born with the mastery of online communication, we must acknowledge that they are lifelong learners (Huyler & Ciocca, 2016), and one of the greatest ways for us to understand who they have become is to carefully analyze what shaped them and their experiences.

Statement of the Problem

With the forced transition and shift of communication platforms in the educational sector, this qualitative study aims to answer the question:

1. What are the experiences of near-retirement educators in the obligatory online communication for relationship building with their students?
2. How did the near-retirement educators relate to or adapt to online communication for relationship-building with their students?

Objectives of the Study

General Objective

This study aimed to describe the lived online communication experiences of near-retirement educators to build connections and interactions with their students.

Specific Objectives

1. To understand the experiences of near-retirement educators in the obligatory online communication for relationship building with their students.
2. To examine how near-retirement educators relate to or adapt to online communication for relationship building with their students.

Significance of the Study

- **Government, Department of Education (DepEd), and Center for Higher Education (CHED):** On a macro level, the Philippine government, DepEd, and CHED can use this study to develop and improve their support for educators. Understanding that there are differences and diversity in needs based on various considerations. At the same time, ensure that all schools, universities, colleges, and institutes in the country will get equal and ample opportunities for growth and improvement when it comes to communication practices, ICTs, and CMCs.
- **Academic Institutions:** On a micro level, respective educational institutions with near-retirement faculty must invest and work on increasing their assistance. The data that was gathered can serve as their benchmark

on the areas where they need to channel effort for the development of their tenured faculty when it comes to communication.

- **Teachers and Educators:** With the lived experiences of educators from the older generation, this study can harness the best practices and implementation of online communication between teachers and students. Simultaneously inspires cooperation and collaboration between the different generations of educators to motivate harmonious advancement.
- **Students:** They are the direct recipients of the communication efforts done by educators, and this study can help the students understand the communication process from the given narratives. Through this, the students can also adapt and match their utilization to create better communication practices on the online platform. After all, for communication to be fruitful, both sender and receiver must ensure active participation.
- **Future Researchers:** As much as it is vital to understand the effectiveness of online learning from the student's end, we must not disregard the importance of caring for those in the instructional part of education. This study can spark interest in understanding online communication based on a specific generation and the implementation of communication in various areas of education. Aside from that, the data can also be used as a basis for communication rates in mandatory scenarios or environments.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

Despite online learning encompassing different aspects and concepts, this study only focused on the online communication experiences of near-retirement educators

from universities in the National Capital Region (NCR) that aid interaction and connection-building between teachers and students. This study may also touch on ICTs and CMCs from the perspective of near-retirement educators, as they are integral to making communication possible. The time frame of their narratives for the lived experiences must be from March 2020 until the present day, when they are maximizing the online mode of learning, thus pure online communication with their students. This does not focus on their experiences if the participants are already maximizing blended learning to this day. However, it might still be mentioned under the context of continuously utilizing their online communication practices from the height of the pandemic.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Communication being dynamic, adaptation occurs depending on various considerations that dictate the efficiency of the process or exchange. However, it is crucial to understand the when, why, and how of communication, especially on an online platform where complexity is expected and experienced.

Communication

Communication came from the Latin word '*communicare*' which means to share or to make common (Weekley, 1967). And there are different aspects of communication that make it unique and distinct. It is a process (Pearson et al., 2021), it seeks to understand (Elhami, 2020), it imparts knowledge (Johnson, 2020), and it provides meaning (Kapur, 2020). Communication, in itself, is dynamic and complex. The existence of verbal and non-verbal communication, together, makes any form of interaction richer. Ideally, they complement each other, which makes the reception and comprehension of the message easier (Stewart & Logan, 2002; Nichol & Watson, 2000; Duck & McMahan, 2009). Components such as sender, message, channel, receiver, and feedback, among others, are constant when it comes to the process of communication. However, the use of models best explains how a message is transferred from one element to another (Kapur, 2020). Models further shed light on the possibility that the communication process might be interrupted by noise (Shannon & Weaver, 1949), and some highlight the importance of factors that influence each

component in communication (Berlo, 1960, as cited in Janse, 2018). Theories also paved the way to deeper understanding by focusing on a specific aspect that summarized the communication process (Van Ruler, 2018).

Online Communication

With the rise of new media, communication is no longer restricted to intrapersonal, interpersonal, or public communication. It provided a new platform for communication to prosper and grow. The birth of the new platform redefined communication and gave birth to more possibilities as compared to what it imposed before (Scott et al., 2022). Face-to-face interactions can now be supplemented, or even replaced, by the online communication efforts of individuals through various technological advancements. Aside from just nurturing a person's offline presence, it is further exemplified by the online persona they are presenting (Paradisi et al., 2021). According to the Digital 2024 Global Overview Report released by We Are Social and Hootsuite (Kemp, 2024), there are 5.35 billion internet users and 5.04 billion social media users, which grew 8.08% and 9.09%, respectively, in two years. This shows the immense adoption and usage rate of the world's population. The data presented various reasons why the internet is adopted by users from ages 16 to 64, but it should not go unnoticed how staying in touch with friends and family ranked second, following information gathering. Contrary to its secondary placement in the question of why people use the internet, chat and messaging, and social networks took the first two spots, respectively, in terms of what types of websites are most visited and used.

Online communication tools are used for social, entertainment, educational, and professional goals, among others (Martyushev et al., 2021). Mirroring the aims of face-

to-face interaction—sharing information, voicing out thoughts, seeking to be understood, and fostering a sense of community (Alawamleh et al., 2020) through many forms of online communication such as email, forum, chat, blog, and social networks (Martyushev et al., 2021). This interaction can occur synchronously, in real time, or asynchronously (Khalil & Ebner., 2017). Seeing that ‘when’ and ‘why’ are not concerns in online communication, this places a question on the who and how of a communicator. Digital inequality is a known concern in online communication. The variation in access to resources and know-how puts a step back in a supposedly parallel growth (Nguyen et al., 2020). This puts into perspective the varying experiences when it comes to online communication. Putting pressure on an individual to harness their communication skills on the digital platform, not just in offline scenarios, affects the efficiency of the process. Subsequently, constant exposure to the proper use of information and communication technologies and the mastery of computer-mediated communication.

Over the years, the pandemic is enough justification for why online communication adaptation reached its all-time high (Kemp, 2022). This reshapes how a person defines and applies online communication, depending on their rate of conversion to the online arena. One of the industries that greatly suffered from this obligatory ‘great migration’ is the education sector.

Age and Platform as a Factor in Online Communication for Education

One of the generations leading the interaction between educators and learners is the Baby Boomers. Born between 1946 and 1964, Venter (2017) stated that the Baby Boomer generation upholds the importance of face-to-face communication because

of the use of body language or non-verbal cues that make the exchange effective. They would rather go to the person if they are not physically present at that moment or use email. However, they do not see instant messaging as an option to compensate for the lack of in-person communication (Venter, 2017) and even regard it as a 'poor substitution' (Mikal et al., 2021). Not to mention their hesitancy about completely transitioning to online communication due to various reasons such as cybersecurity, accessibility, and comfort (Gao, 2023).

Baby Boomers are well aware of their lack of technological skills, and that results in the pressure of keeping up with the younger generation (Huyler & Ciocca, 2016; Venter, 2017). In an attempt to make up for the fact that digital literacy is not innate to them, Baby Boomers would find ways to fit this phenomenon into their daily lives, such as printing a document that can be accessed on their device and gradually progressing to the use of social media or instant messaging despite uneasiness (Venter, 2017). This is supported by a qualitative study conducted by Mikal et al. (2021), where the participants, with an average age of 69, show that their internet usage is geared towards formal or work-related communication with very limited social networking interactions. According to one of the participants, 60% of his digitally connected time is for email, 20% for Zoom, 20% for gaming, and Facebook and Instagram share 10%. On the other hand, one of the respondents mentioned that they consume social media passively, such as by scrolling, reading, and liking to check on their family members that they have not seen due to social distancing. This shows how baby boomers maximize the use of the internet as a means of communication with loved ones and information gathering that helps them with trivial to in-depth discoveries (Mayer, et. al., 2020).

As educators, age comes experience, as this was highlighted as one of the strengths of Baby Boomer educators according to the study conducted by Polat et al. (2019), as they seek to analyze the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of teachers from different generations as told by school administrators. This generation is also considered as model teachers as they show that they are responsible, productive, responsive, and respectful. They are also regarded as disciplined and good problem-solvers. While technologically inadequate, resistance to technology and closed communication are pointed out as some of their weaknesses, along with monotonous, authoritarian, non-progressive, hypercritical, and others. Despite the cons, the opportunities for Baby Boomers as educators lie in their ability to transfer knowledge and experience to their colleagues, provide guidance, and share best practices. And for the threats, discouraging the younger generation, exaggerating the importance of their age, keeping a slow pace at work, and being against innovation are identified, among others.

This is supported by the study conducted by Puspitasari et al. (2021), in which 100% of Baby Boomer participants lack ICT skills to make online learning successful for their students. They stated that, despite the option of maximizing Google Classroom as their platform to conduct lectures and communication, it is too complicated and complex for them. Baby Boomers are resistant to the adaptation of technology as they see it as unnecessary (Venter, 2017; Restyandito & Kurniawan, 2017; Vaportzis et al., 2017; as cited in Puspitasari, 2021). Eventually, some participants chose WhatsApp to share materials, collect outputs, and communicate with students. However, challenges were still encountered, such as the difficulty of uploading materials, downloading the activities, checking requirements, and replying to the concerns one by one. Because of the bulk of concerns and submissions from

each student, they also mentioned the difficulty of keeping track of the progress. Despite the assistance coming from team-teaching or attempting to be self-taught, it is regarded as too complicated for the participants. They reiterated that even before the pandemic, only some maximized the use of laptops and projectors in in-person instruction, while others still preferred the board and marker approach.

Although in the online learning set up, various communication adaptation efforts have been exerted such as adding personal touch or element in online learning is an important factor to support the platform as discussion boards, prompt replies, praises, questions, and encouragement of deeper thought is highly critical (Tanis, 2020); exploring the importance of the use of tone in communication through this textual exchange that discovered that friendlier, clearer and encouraging tone results to better academic performance and open communication on the end of the students (Dickenson, 2017); encouraging the students to download Skype to speak to each other, communication was much easier; assuring that the student is indeed talking to someone that is 'human' and lessening the barrier in online communication (Varre et al, 2010); and other forms of communication channels that are easily accessible to their students, such as WhatsApp (70%), MS Teams chat and text (28%), Facebook pages (14%), and even phone calls (8%) (Almahasees, 2021). However, it was discovered that despite the ease of maximization of communication on social networking sites, there are ethical rules for maintaining a professional tone and focusing on academic topics (Măță, 2021). Although these adjustments have been managed and executed by other educators, we then again have to consider: does the older generation of educators have the motivation and ability to implement the same measures?

Intergenerational Online Communication in Education

If digital immigrants are classified by their delayed adaptation to a digital platform, digital natives master this practice. Digital Natives are the speakers of the internet, computers, and other technologies (Prensky, 2001; as cited in Crieghton, 2018). Even if there is a huge gap between Baby Boomers and the younger generation, their lives must be connected, as Baby Boomers can be considered parents, teachers, and supporters of the younger generation. They give meaning to each other's lives. However, despite the necessity for them to create a connection and good relationship with one another, older and younger generations rarely see eye to eye due to the generation gap as well as the use of communication technologies (Venter, 2017). Downs (2019) emphasized that if the generation gap manifested in a lack of understanding in communication behavior is not mutually addressed, this causes a breakdown in the quality and shared meanings that should exist. Fruitful communication can be obtained between older and younger generations through open-mindedness, respect, constant communication, and adaptation to each other's communication practices (Venter, 2017; Hart, 2017).

Applying it to online learning, a literature review study conducted by Camas et al. (2021) showed that social networking sites (SNS) are used by educators to initiate a closer relationship with their students, and this has been acknowledged by numerous authors. Through SNS, it provides a platform for the instructor to communicate with their students in a deeper sense that creates a better relationship between the two. And as a recommendation, Camas et al. (2021) mentioned that future studies should touch on the possible digital spaces or educational strategies that can foster a relationship between educators and students. Which was expounded by Koh and

Daniel (2022), where they explored two learning engagement strategies during the fully online shift of learning and communication. It has been reiterated that active learning that encourages students to explore and practice the topic helps them to learn it better, while it does not go unnoticed how reinforcing a positive learning environment where educators actively communicate with their students, show empathy, provide assurance, and offer unwavering guidance gives a different level of support to their students on the online platform. This highlights the importance of creating a much stronger sense of community in the online setting, may it be educator to student or student to student. Fostering that 'safe space' where anyone can freely express their thoughts and share their insights for needed support during these trying times (Eklund & Isotalus, 2024). This entails constant assessment and adjustment to each other's communication style, which, in the academe, can be predominantly dictated by those from the older generation (Bongco & Ama, 2023).

In Channel Expansion Theory (Carlson & Zmud, 1999), they stated the importance of various experiences that can make communication richer, aiming to bridge the gaps of Media Richness Theory (Daft & Lengel, 1984; Daft et al., 1987; as cited in Carlson & Zmud, 1999). They have identified that experience with the channel, experience with messaging topics, experience with the organizational context, and experience with communication co-participants must be ensured to result in fruitful communication. Despite online communication's application in various contexts, its lens in the educational sector needs more exploration. Teachers and instructors who converge in line with expectations for behavior are deemed to be more effective (Chory & Offstein, 2017; 2018); however, we cannot guarantee if the same narrative is experienced by all near-retirement educators (Frey, 2019). Our older educators have varying experience when it comes to keeping up with the advances and connecting with the

younger generation that seems to speak a different and complex language (Prensky, 2001; as cited in Crieghton, 2018). There are abundant studies that focus on assessing the effectiveness of online learning from the perspective of the students or how Baby Boomers navigate the online platform, such as Sheldon et al. (2021) and communication practices as told by Hardy et al. al. (2019), and there are studies such as Petalla (2022) that analyze the lived experiences of the baby boomer generation when it comes to teaching and learning during this setup, but there is far less literature that focuses on how relationship and connection building prospered for those who preferred their traditional approach. Furthermore, some studies focus on online communication in terms of age, education, and platform; there has been minimal exploration that seeks to discover the convergence of these components in a single context.

Hermeneutic Phenomenology

Drawing from Van Manen's (2014, as cited in Santiago et. al., 2020) analogy, phenomenology highlights the process of an individual situating themselves to a phenomenon, while hermeneutics divulges the giving meaning to the "texts" of life. Therefore, hermeneutic phenomenology deals with expounding the meaning of part and the whole based on how individuals live their lives, given a specific temporal and situational consideration, through an ontological perspective, highlighting that it is a process of probing and analysis until the "truth" comes out (Suddick et. al., 2020). Truth is obtained through the participation of narratives and methods. In the context of phenomenology, sense and meaning-making give individuals the power to interpret information from those who experience it; however, given the existence of values and norms, this provides objectivity and sets limits to the formation of perception and ideas.

Adding hermeneutics to the mix adds depth to what should be taken into consideration in interpreting the lived experiences gathered (Guillen, 2019). Understanding the theory of meaning and interpretation that is tied to the idea of hermeneutics, it must be recognized that making sense of the lived experiences and narratives of the participants should not just be dependent on what is explicitly seen or stated; thus, a researcher must subject themselves to discerning the implied or inferred meaning out of these texts, or fusion of horizons. This also calls for the application of a hermeneutic circle that marries individual accounts to treatments of the whole to arrive at a better and stronger interpretation (Gadamer, 2008; Heidegger, 2003, as cited in Suddick et. al., 2020).

Phenomenology is widely used in different fields, such as medicine, nursing, and business, to shed light on a specific phenomenon. (Campbell, 2018, Zahavi and Martiny, 2019, as cited in Santiago et. al., 2020). However, it is undeniable that its importance in the field of education is also acknowledged. Hermeneutic phenomenology in education helps those in the field, such as teachers and professors, become more aware of the meaning behind these experiences that affect professional growth through reflection and analysis. (Ayala, 2008 as cited in Guillen, 2019). Through hermeneutic phenomenology as a theoretical lens, this study was able to obtain meanings and interpretations of e-communication in education from the perspective of near-retirement educators to use as a basis for improvement when it comes to providing support and assistance.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This qualitative research aims to understand the lived experiences of near-retirement educators in online communication. A phenomenological research design was implemented. Phenomenology explores the creation of meaning that is molded by the experiences of people. This seeks to understand how an individual subjectively defines a phenomenon by exploring the 'what' and the 'how' (Neubauer et al., 2019). This research design entails careful analysis, description, and interpretation of an individual's perception, beliefs, ideas, emotions, and recollection of that experience. Phenomenological research is also identified as based on the assumption that a single study cannot discuss the totality of a phenomenon. Given that this gives freedom for the participants to divulge their experiences and narratives about a phenomenon without much restriction or influencing direction stated by the researcher, this will also be used as the theoretical lens of the study. Highlighting that the main focus and source of discussion will be drawn from what is shared by the participants while incorporating the positionality of the researcher. Thus, to further understand it, continuous exploration and investigation must be conducted to collectively supplement those that exist (Hourigan & Edgar, 2020).

Phenomenological research components (Magrini, 2012) are as follows:

1. Stage of gathering life experiences
2. Stage of analysis and determining themes
3. Stage of practical application that leads to suggestions for improvement

However, Max Van Manen, known in the field of educational research and hermeneutic-phenomenological approach, developed six research activities (Van Manen, 1990; as cited in Magrini, 2012) that help better treat studies:

1. Turning to the nature of lived experience
2. Investigating experience as we live it
3. Reflecting on essential themes
4. The art of writing and re-writing
5. Maintaining a strong and oriented relationship to lived experience
6. Balancing the research context by considering parts and whole

While phenomenology is the study of essence, hermeneutics offers an in-depth approach to experiences as it focuses on the process of interpretation (Kakkori, 2009). We often make sense of the word 'understand' if we have deduced something out of a text or context and express otherwise if we have failed to interpret based on the given (George, 2021). Hermeneutics follows the principle that, for us to have a deeper understanding of a person's experience, we should not just focus on what is explicitly stated but dive into what is implied (Fuster, 2019). This approach does not just place importance on the experience but also takes into consideration the person behind the experience, the one seeking to understand, and the prior and dynamic knowledge of the phenomenon (Suddick, et al., 2020). Alongside the analysis of the who and what, the how is also considered. How these texts and contexts are communicated, verbal, non-verbal, behavior, culture, systems, and others also play a role in the interpretation of the phenomenon (Vélez & Galeano, 2002; as cited in Fuster, 2019). Making the process highlight not just the part but also the whole.

Participants of the Study

Given the abrupt transition to online learning that occurred in the educational sector these past few years, the foundational needs of educators must be prioritized in the same way as our learners. However, despite the extended support, we have to understand that certain considerations and aspects make one educator different from the other. One of which is age (Soliz & Giles, 2014). And this affects the rate and effectiveness of communication that can exist on the learning platform. To understand how communication takes place in the online learning platform between educator-learner, near-retirement or baby boomer educators were the participants of this study. Those born between 1946 and 1964 who have ample experience in pure online instruction at the undergraduate or graduate level during the obligatory online setup.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted locally. Near-retirement educators from different universities from NCR were of great help to this study as participants. As preferred by the participants and for their convenience, all interviews were conducted via online conferencing.

Sampling Scheme

Purposeful sampling was utilized for this study. This type of sampling places importance on the selection of participants based on their ability to shed light on the theme or phenomenon. In line with this study, participants must be born between 1946 to 1964 and have teaching experience, with at least 5 years under their belt, exposure to and experience in conducting pure online instruction and teaching at the

undergraduate and/or graduate level during the pandemic. These components dictate how online communication is experienced by the participant.

In principle, phenomenological studies require fewer participants as compared to ethnographic research, grounded theory, or content analysis. It is projected that less than 10 interviews will suffice to understand the lived experiences of the participants (Moser & Korstjens, 2018). For this study, four participants were invited. Phenomenological studies do not aim to give the general context of the phenomenon but to contribute an angle to it due to its first-person point-of-view (Hourigan & Edgar, 2020).

Research Instrument

One-on-one, unstructured interviews were deemed the best fit, as this study seeks to understand the lived experiences of the participants. Limitless and boundless interviews took place. The researcher gave respondents the freedom to tell their stories and experiences when it comes to online communication and relationship building during obligatory scenarios. In line with that, the researcher also functioned as an instrument in data gathering, interpretation, and contextualizing the narratives of the participants (Yoon & Uliassi, 2022). This actively involves the background and sense of self of the researcher in how the data was treated and rationalized.

Data Gathering Procedure

To understand how communication accommodation is applied and experienced by Baby Boomer educators on the online platform, data was gathered through the following efforts:

1. Through purposeful sampling, participants were invited to take part in the study. The participation invitation letter and informed consent were released and explained.
2. Once granted, an interview was scheduled. Conducting computer-mediated interviews was decided by the participant, as it was most convenient for them.
3. During the scheduled interview, the participant was reminded that the interview was recorded, and at the same time, the researcher's notes were also utilized for non-verbal observations and highlights.
4. Afterwards, the recording was transcribed, and notes were organized for the data analysis procedure. Verbatim, intelligent, and edited transcription took place depending on the need for clarity and analysis.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical considerations were strictly followed. The nature and scope of the study were fully explained to the prospective and invited participants. The researcher fully understood that voluntary participation must be exercised.

Once the participant committed to the study, an informed consent form was explained by the researcher, read, and signed by the participant for the reference of both parties. However, should they wish to withdraw at any point, it will be respected and accepted by the researcher.

All schedules for interviews were adjusted according to the availability of the participants. A briefing prior to the interview was conducted so that the participant was well-aware of the flow of the discussion. The duration was also declared as a minimum

of 30 minutes and a maximum of 1 hour. However, it was also extended based on the participant's jurisdiction to continue the discussion.

An approval from the participant was asked before recording the interview, and all gathered information or recorded audio or video was kept on a safe online and offline drive.

Privacy and anonymity were honored by the study. No information or data shall be released that may cause harm to the participants. All mentioned names or the like shall be replaced by code names as a form of protection. And all the gathered information was only used for its intended purpose. Once the gathered materials are no longer needed, they will be deleted in all forms.

Researcher Subjectivity

Reflexivity was also practiced to ensure proper positionality that benefited the direction and result of the research (Holmes, 2020). As a communication graduate working in the academe for almost five years, I am a part of the coordinating team for online class implementation. The researcher discloses all this vital information before the interview with the participants to establish trust and rapport. The declaration of the nature of the researcher's background is a way to encourage the participants to be open, as the study aims to understand their experiences for the development of better practice in the institution.

Hermeneutic Analysis

Building knowledge and establishing beliefs is perceived to follow a 'vertical' motion where, as an individual learns more or forms new learning, it piles up, showing how

recent information is supported below by foundational beliefs. However, hermeneutics contradicts this idea by focusing on the ‘circularity’ of understanding, or hermeneutic circle (George, 2021). Instead of interpreting knowledge building as one linear upward motion, it is a series or continuous back-and-forth cycle that drives deeper and fuller understanding.

Figure 1:

The ongoing dialogue and work toward a unified, hermeneutic, and phenomenological understanding (Suddick et al., 2020).

The hermeneutic circle (Figure 1) suggests:

1. Constant reading of the available material

2. Development of themes and concepts based on individual accounts
3. Deriving initial meaning from themes and concepts
4. Record understanding by documenting the findings
5. Revisit materials gathered on individual accounts
6. Organize excerpts from all individual accounts as we start to treat it as a whole
7. Revisit individual accounts for confirmation and clarification
8. Creating maps with all the individual accounts as a whole
9. Continuously seeing both the individual and the whole for understanding development

This motion represents the movement of the being interpreted by what is analyzed from the text and context (Fuster, 2019) and is characterized by the 'opening, closing, broadening, and fusion of horizon' that might happen as the cycle continues (Gadamer, 2008; as cited in Suddick et al., 2020).

For this study, I tried to follow the hermeneutic circle above.

I began the analysis by reading and rereading through all the transcripts of the four interviews. As I went through the transcripts, themes were gradually assigned to the statements and narratives of the participants. The themes that initially guided me with the direction of grouping the statements were based on the time element and their communication practice pre-, during, and post-shift. This eventually evolved to just treating the time element as a secondary consideration and regaining focus on the types of experiences they had as a near-retirement educator.

I listed all the themes shared by participants to make sure that all their narratives were accounted for before using them as a reference for all other participants in the study. After which, I grouped the themes based on how they related to the research objective. With this, I grouped the statements per participant with the others and

reanalyzed their similarities and differences based on the main theme. This resulted in the creation of sub-themes based on the main themes that tied up their individual experiences, relating them to the whole.

Lastly, I did a series of reading and rereading once again to check whether their statements aligned with the main and sub-themes. All of these were organized with the help of a dedicated sheet that was created to keep track of the themes that came out of the interviews. This sheet maps out the participants, research objective it answers, main theme, sub theme, and statement. This helped me further assess and develop where I stand as a researcher, online class coordinator, and educator.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After the obligatory online setup drastically changed the definition of education, teachers underwent diverse narratives that shaped its meaning when it came to building relationships with their students. This paper is focused on two research questions: What are the experiences of near-retirement educators in obligatory online communication, and how did the near-retirement educators relate to or adapt to online communication for relationship building?

With phenomenology as the theoretical lens and following the hermeneutic approach, the narratives and statements given by participants were repeatedly read and analyzed, treated as an individual account, and at the same time used to give context as a whole. After careful analysis, the excerpts were manually coded based on the idea or type of narrative they expound on to assess similarities and differences between the experiences of each participant. Codes were further identified to indicate which research objective was achieved or which question was answered. This process reconstructed the experiences of the near-retirement educators in the obligatory online setup that resulted in emerging main and sub-themes:

Table 1:

Research Objectives and Emerging Themes

Research Objectives	Experiences of near-retirement educators in the obligatory online communication for relationship building with their students.		Near-retirement educators relate to or adapt to online communication for relationship building with their students.	
Main Themes	Cause of Disconnect	Triumph to Reconnect	Switching Gears	Embracing the Change
Sub Themes or Codes	Age is just a number... or is it?	Status: Sent, Delivered, and Read	Boomer, the Explorer	Redefining 'Boomer Energy'
	Imposition of the Position	Actions speak louder than words	Count on me, like 1, 2, 3	An Open Heart is an Open Mind
	Educator and Student ÷ Access and Usage	I am a Survivor	Access to Success	Formula for Lifelong Learners
	Absence of Presence			

Although some schools and universities are slowly adapting to online modes of instruction before the lockdown, the majority has been struck with urgency and a crucial shift just to make education possible. While the teachers or educators seek to get their lessons across to their students, communication to build rapport and relationships with their students has also been limited to squares on the screen and the stability of the internet connection. The marriage between learning and connection building between teacher and students in these trying times has caused various narratives from my four participants that redefined their perception of online communication for their generation.

Experiences of Near-Retirement Educators: The Cause of Disconnect

In the course of my discussion with the participants, various directions were taken as they looked back on their situation when the speed of their internet connection and online practice shaped their connection with their students. With the variety of stories and narratives shared, the predominant hurdles and challenges for them as educators were enumerated, that can be considered a clear depiction of the battles they fought just to stay connected to their students.

Age is just a number... or is it?

In the discussion with the participants of the study, one has expressed that age is a vital factor during that period. In the academic environment that I was exposed to, the year one is born can be a great consideration for preconceptions about them as individuals. Age molds attitudes and perceptions that alter how an individual assesses and addresses a situation. This specific mentality is shared by all environments of the participants, as they expressed how a numerical value can greatly affect how one predicts their level of involvement or adaptability when it comes to the situation. Participant 2 classified that there are two types of people from her generation during the obligatory online setup:

“Number 1, ‘I’m too old to learn’ ‘I no longer wanted to learn that and I’m done with it’, parang ganon, hindi ko na siya kailangan. Kasi as an administrator, as per experience, yung mga... yung mga old generation na ‘di ko na po kaya yun. Di ko na po yun magagawa’ so eventually they have to make a choice, especially during the time of the pandemic. Either

you adjust, you embrace this new norm in education. Or else you have to go. Yun naman mga iba, of course the other side of the coin is that, they are still willing, despite of age, and at the same time, they know age is not just a number and they have a specific role to play and importance in the academe.” – Participant 2

[Number 1, ‘I’m too old to learn’ ‘I no longer wanted to learn that and I’m done with it’ somewhere along those lines, it’s like not needing it anymore. Because as an administrator, as per experience, the... the old generation that keeps on saying ‘I don’t think I can do it anymore’ ‘I don’t think it is possible for me’ so eventually they have to make a choice, especially during the time of the pandemic. Either you adjust, you embrace this new norm in education. Or else you have to go. While the others, of course the other side of the coin is that, they are still willing, despite their age, and at the same time, they know age is not just a number and they have a specific role to play and importance in the academe.]

Whether one belongs to the former or the latter, this mindset has greatly affected an educator’s experience during the obligatory setup. While this remains to be the case for the other participants as well, they have been very vocal about the fact that they are leaning towards the latter. I have seen how these two types of individuals situate themselves during the period of obligatory online setup adjustment. I saw how one airs out frustration about how complicated and complex the situation is and purely lets the students do the adjustment to their traditional ways, while the other one bends and goes the extra mile, just to make sure that their greater purpose in the field is their driving

force to embrace what needs to be done for their students. Although expected, this type of distinction is not always a consideration on my end as an online class coordinator. When it comes to delegating tasks, the characteristics of an individual based on factors such as age, will be an immediate notion because it makes the achievement of tasks and goals easier for the team. Taking note that, with everything too fast-paced on the online platform, not to mention that you are dealing with students that are well-versed in the dynamics of online communication, you just want to make sure that you get things done from my point of view. That is why, it is always an easier choice for me to assign tasks to those with prior knowledge while asking those who take time to get used to tasks to shadow them until they get a hang of it. However, making age a prejudice is unjust for educators like them. Seeing the cited types of educators during that period, you cannot help but admire that they acknowledge where they stand. I have seen some younger educators who are in denial of their weaknesses, that hinders them from turning them into strengths, while these seasoned educators never cease to be transparent about where they are in any given situation.

Imposition of the Position

Participant 1 cited that it is not just their age that conditions their decisions and actions towards students during the obligatory online setup, but also their position in their respective institutions. Truth be told, three out of four participants have an administrative role, and this alters not only on their end but also affects how their students perceive and approach them.

“Especially, for me age and position, malaking factor din yun na nagbabago yung relationships sa students kasi pag merong authority

na... uhhh... like administrative uhhh... work ka na they, students I think, think of the consequences when they approach you.” – Participant 1

[Especially, for me, age and position, it is a big factor that it changes the type of relationship you have with your students because of that authority... uhhh... like administrative uhhh... work and the students would consider the consequences of approaching you.]

As much as a position creates an impression for Participant 1, Participant 2, and Participant 3, they are also on the same boat with wearing two hats in the institution. This shows that age equates to experience, and experience leads to credibility, which makes any tenured educator the best or most sensible choice for an administrative position. But despite the demands of being the man or woman in the office, they make sure that they are their student's teachers before the administrator. This means showing a much more approachable demeanor, not limiting themselves in their office, encouraging students to be more open in communication, and making the students feel their presence as their teacher. As I have observed our environment in the institution that I worked for, and those that I know of, tenured faculty would always have two dominant classifications when it comes to demeanor: either they are the terror ones or the motherly-fatherly figure type. Given the administrative role that they have, there is a certain level of boundaries to maintain; nonetheless, an approachable demeanor is much more expected of those who fit the motherly-fatherly figure type, as this gives the students a comfortable relationship. And seeing how the participants find balance between the two is admirable. They ensure that respect is maintained but does not appear too closed off. However, their efforts do not matter if the recipients of the effort,

the students, are already fixated on the idea that you are still someone who is in control. And it is human nature to be drawn closer to people whom you perceive to have more similarities with you, given the fact that the participants are aware that their year of birth and their job title create a wall on a supposedly closer relationship between an educator and the learner. The intent, on the end of the near-retirement educator to build a relationship is already there, but the way I see it, it can only be successful once the students will not let the intimidation and fear of the position get to them. But according to the participants, prioritizing their demeanor is their same approach even prior to the obligatory online setup; however, in Participant 3's words, "in a more challenging mode."

Educators and Students ÷ Access and Usage

Aside from age and position becoming factors in relationship building, the mode or platform has been one of the biggest facets of their experience. The participants expressed that there is an overwhelming pressure to learn so many applications in such a short period of time just to make communication and instruction possible. A platform to give the readings and activities; an app for video conferencing; a medium for updates; and real-time coordination. All those efforts of reorienting themselves to a complex set-up just to reach out to their students in the most convenient way possible. And it is not as if these navigations can be absorbed in a single training, but it entails continuous practice and even habit formation for you to at least be comfortable with the hows of the platform. Not to mention the paperwork, preparations, and other tasks that are expected in their job description. All in all, they have a lot on their plate during those times. I have seen it happen on our end as well. Since we are in charge of training the faculty, I noticed that seasoned faculty, given that they know where they lack, are the type who will personally approach or message us questions on how to navigate this and that. I

clearly remember that one of our older faculty members expressed how grateful she is to our team that we have been so patient when it comes to answering questions and assisting them with their concerns. Given this type of routine that we noticed from the near-retirement faculty, this motivated our team to create a handbook or guide that helps our faculty and students navigate through the platforms we are utilizing during the fully online setup. However, it has been highlighted by the participants that, as much as we are forcing the obligatory online setup, connectivity is still an issue. Not all can afford to be consistently available during their synchronous meetings, even if it is their avenue to make real-time connections with their students. To make ends meet, Participant 1 opts for a traditional way to reach her students:

“Text. Cellphone. Kasi lahat sila sigurado nakakabit sila sa cellphone. Hindi internet kasi may mga estudyante na walang internet. So hindi uubra ang email, pag nagsend ako ng email eh sasabihin down ang internet, pano nila mababasa yun?... Final validation and verification sakin ang text, cellphone. Kasi pag sumagot sakin doon, ‘oh ma’am wala po kaming ilaw.’ ‘oh ma’am wala po kaming internet.”ma’am wala po kaming... may sakit po ako.’, ‘ma’am inaalagaan ko po magulang ko.’ Dun lalabas eh na... yung hindi uubra yung internet.” – Participant 1

[Text. Cellphone. Because everyone for sure is connected through their phones. Not the internet because there are some students who have an issue with connectivity. So email is not a viable option since if you send an email but the internet is down, how will the student read the message?... For me, final validation and verification is through a text

message. Because they would often respond there with statements like 'oh ma'am we do not have electricity.' 'oh ma'am we do not have an internet connection.' 'ma'am I'm sick.' ' ma'am I'm taking care of my parents.' it will show... that internet is not that dependable.']

This proves that, on the participants' end, there are far more things that the Internet cannot replace. The reality of the situation is that, it is not just the capability of the end users, the near-retirement educators, to navigate their way through platforms and mediums for communication, but rather, it is also facing the manifestation that the digital divide is much more evident in situations like this. With the advent of advanced technology, which has caused more debate and discussion in the academic community about whether it is still helpful or disruptive to learning, we are still battling a long-standing issue such as the digital divide. It has transitioned from how not everyone can have direct access to the digital platforms that we can maximize to the question of usage and utilization. Especially in a period where everyone is mandated to abide by the situation we are in, the ideal scenario is that everyone would have equal footing where they are in the rise of technology and advancement, but there are still numerous cases where it is not as easy to be able to hop on the digital landscape. And in a class ranging from 10 to 40, it is with great concern that the participants are the type of educators that show immense care for their students. Going the extra mile just to make sure that whether their students are onboard with the online platform or are getting left behind, they see to it that they will not feel alone in this, thus still encouraging open communication in whichever way possible. Personally, I cannot help but admire them in this specific narrative, but looking at it from a deeper perspective, baby boomers are known to be fixated on the traditional habits and practices that they have formed or not

much of a fan when it comes to abandoning their usual routine, and these are the instances when I thank these characteristics because these traditional ways of reaching out that our generation abandoned for new practices became a saving grace for students that are in need. I cannot even remember when I asked for someone's cell phone number because, for me, it is much easier to look for them on social media or message them on Messenger, but it is their wisdom that comes with age and experience that makes them 10 times more equipped than us younger educators. But aside from the harsh reality that we are in, it is noticeable that the participants can easily focus on their own struggles in making online communication possible, but they also put themselves in the shoes of their students, considering the situation that they are in. I have seen educators who will just message their students once, and if they do not answer, the 'bahala ka diyan' mentality kicks in. Seemingly settling for the bare minimum effort when it comes to bridging gaps. And in a country where not all educators and learners are given equal opportunities and resources to power through a demanding period, the compassion that is enriched by their years in service managed to show how much they are willing to go the extra mile just to be the teacher their learners need.

Absence of Presence

As much as they do their best to be seen and felt, one of the greatest concerns of the participants is their absence. From seeing everything that is happening inside the classroom during lectures at maximum interaction, the obligatory online setup has forced the educators to stare at squares on screen without knowing whether they are still talking to someone.

“It's difficult the first time I experienced that na you don't see your audience. You only see profile pictures and if you ask them to open their cameras, they have all the excuses... na sira yung camera nila etcetera. when you see the students malalaman ng teacher na... talagang intently listening or the students may be looking at you but their minds are wandering. Iba talaga yung... face to face 'di ba. ...pati body language indicative of... whether they are in... or they are out.” – Participant 3

[It's difficult the first time I experience that you do not see your audience. You only see profile pictures and if you ask them to open their cameras, they have all the excuses... that their camera is not working etcetera. When the teachers see their students they would know if they are intently listening or the students may be looking at you but their minds are wandering. It really is different... face to face right? Body language is indicative of... whether they are in... or they are out.]

“The quality of communication, yun yung... hindi ko pa masabi. Kung positive or negative kasi depende sa kinakausap, sa edad, sa age. Although there are some young people, or young students that will be mature enough, but in terms of quality of communication, may mangilanngilan kasi na parang nawala yung concept ng pakikinig. The listening portion, either, short span, or dahil... I'm not sure if it's a means of Zoom di ba, minsan kasi multi-tasking. So yung multi-tasking naform na hindi nakakafocus. Kung minsan hindi mo alam kung ikaw ba kausap or nakikinig ba sayo or hindi. Which is different nung pre-pandemic kasi

nakikita mo yung face and lahat. Yun yung sinasabi ko lang na during lectures, during discussion meetings na malaking bagay kasi kung face-to-face kasi nakikita ko yung mukha, alam ko kung may sinabi ako, uy nakakunot, hindi naiintindihan. Hindi ko yun mapick up sa Zoom. Hindi ko mapick up yun. So yun yung malaking bagay sa communication na and understand that... understand the return message. You only have to rely on the sound and sometimes you can open the video, but still it is not enough to be able to see, sakin malaking bagay sa lecture yung body language, na makikita mo na uy, nababagot na sila, uy wala na dito sa classroom ang kanilang isip kasi nakatingin nalang sayo, so yung mga ganong klase, hindi mo yun mapipick up sa Zoom.” – Participant 1

[The quality of communication, that.. That is something that I cannot assure. If it is positive or negative for me, it will always depend on the age. Although there are some young people, or young students that will be mature enough, in terms of quality of communication, there are some that the concept of listening is gone. The listening portion, either, short span, or because... I'm not sure if it is a means of Zoom because of multitasking right? So because of multitasking, they can no longer focus. There are times that you do not know if they are talking to you or if they are listening or not. Which is different during pre-pandemic because you can see their faces and assess everything. That is what I'm saying during lectures, during discussion meetings, that seeing their faces during face to face meetings is a huge deal. I would know if I said something, their facial expression would show, indicating that they do not understand. It is

difficult to pick that up from Zoom. So that is a big deal in communication that they understand... they understand the return message. You only have to rely on the sound and sometimes you can open the video, but still it is not enough to be able to see, for me body language greatly helps, you would see if they are bored, if their minds are wandering but they are looking at you. That is something that is difficult to pick up at Zoom.]

The participants mentioned that the non-lexical cues that exist only during face-to-face interaction, cannot be replicated during online communication. Facial expression used to be an indicator of whether the students were getting the lecture or not. A simple head tilt or scratching of the head says a lot and can alter their approach as a teacher. Jokes and bantering during class is a common fun approach to making the atmosphere lighter. Simple statements like “*uy ma’am maaga kayo ngayon.*” every time they enter the classroom pre-pandemic give that sense of assurance on both ends that they have a comfortable relationship. But that is long gone during the online class, as they are often greeted by off-cameras and muted microphones. Being an effective teacher is more than being able to deliver a lesson in front of a class. One of our supposedly greatest weapons in ensuring a healthy class dynamic is being able to read the room by assessing what needs to be done to gain their interest, or what needs to be said to encourage conversation. And even knowing what is acceptable or fun for the students or which ones are not up their alley, especially in the digital age when anything can be easily misinterpreted or even the boom of ‘cancel culture’, us educators might remain clueless of what works and what does not since our visual cues were taken away and unsure if the receivers of our message perceive it as intended. It actually became a running joke for our faculty that we have to be very careful of what to say because we

might get posted online. However, given the mentioned difficulty in access and connectivity, the educators are in no position to require the whole class to turn on their microphone because it disrupts their concentration or switch their cameras on as it might lead to connectivity issues. Making it impossible for them to encourage their students to mirror their same effort in building connections. This causes frustration on the end of the educator. They are already pushing themselves to learn and relearn so many things. However, as much as you want to do more, there are just a multitude of reasons why it will not happen in the most ideal way possible. But regardless, the efforts made by the educators are not solely to make their students academically excel during the obligatory online setup; but it is also a way for them to support their students in any way possible.

“...body language, yung expression nila etcetera, mahalaga yun sa communication eh. Na makuha totally... kung, let's say na... na may problema na yung estudyante right and... minsan gusto mong iextend your support mo pero you are only limited with using words, wala ng mga gestures minsan a tap on the back or you know yung mga ganon. Lalo na kapag ah... kapag may problema yung estudyante at umiiyak di ba? Yun lang, nakikinig ka lang parang helpless ka na you want to reach out pero limited ka lang. Yung ang mga difficulties kasi ang mga... ang communication kasi hindi lang naman hearing and seeing. A lot more than that. So I think yun yung problema ko sa online.” – Participant 3

[... body language, their expression etcetera, that is important in communication eh. That you can fully grasp it... that, let's say that... that

my student has a problem right and... sometimes you want to extend your support but you are only limited with using words, the gestures like a tap on the back or actions like that are no longer possible. Especially if... if the students have a problem and they are crying about it right? All you can do is just to listen, it is like you are helpless that you want to reach out but your actions are limited. That is extremely difficult... because communication is not just hearing and seeing. A lot more than that. So I think that is my problem with online.]

This shows that their efforts in the online obligatory setup are not just done for the sake of complying with what is expected of them. In a classroom, the term 'present' will usually be mentioned during class attendance, that marks the physical presence and participation of a student. With the hand raising replaced by a button on Zoom, eyes staring at an educator that indicates paying attention to the lecture shifted to names listed as participants, or squares on screen accompanied by deafening silence, measuring or assessing being present in the online context became a challenging concept for the participants. And for an educator who tries to make not just education possible, but connections prosper, they have to try to ride the waves of redefining presence in an unaccustomed situation. The textbook description of a tenured and near-retirement educator would most probably be synonymous with the word 'terror' but these participants showed that their years of experience do not just translate to wiser and better educators but compassionate and 'heart on their sleeve' types of individuals, which is something that every learner needs at that point, more than ever.

Experiences of Near-Retirement Educators: The Triumph to Reconnect

The near-retirement educators experience is not just defined by what contributed to their growth through difficulties; it is also remarkable how their initiatives during those trying times paved the way to countless accomplishments on their end as educators. The four participants recounted what they reaped, for they sowed rigorously.

Status: Sent, Delivered, and Read

Despite the trials of redefining “being there” for their students regardless of the physical distance, there are various wins that the educators have celebrated in the years of being on the online platform. And these efforts did not go unnoticed by the students, even parents, as they became vocal in expressing their gratitude to the participants. The evaluation after every semester became one of their driving forces to continue the good practices during online communication and improve what did not work for the students. Participant 3 shared the experience he had with a parent of his student.

“Kaya during the graduation, first time ko silang makita face to face. Ipinakilala niya yung daddy niya sakin at ang sabi niya... And sabi ng daddy niya ‘I want you to know that you are the idol of my son.’ Ang sabi naman nung son ‘that’s true sir but I also want you to know na mas idol ka ng daddy ko.’” – Participant 3

[That is why during the graduation, that is the first time that I saw them face to face. A student introduced me to his father and he said... his father said ‘Sir, I want you to know that you are the idol of my son.’ And his son

said 'that's true sir but I also want you to know that my father idolizes you more.']

This is just a perfect example of not knowing how impactful you are in a person's life. One of the educator's goals is to be able to inspire and motivate their students to become a better version of themselves, and hearing that they have successfully achieved that goal, the gratification that comes from the parent says a lot about how well they have done their job, not just as teachers but as role models for young minds. This shows that even at the most difficult time for educators, they still manage to go beyond just touching lives and hone the future professionals of this nation. And the inspiration that is brought about by the relationships built in academic communication is not just appreciated by the direct receiver, the students, but ripples in their other relationships, such as those with their immediate family members. In line with that, Participant 4 cited an experience that, due to the type of setup that they have in an online class, it resulted in a much more relaxed environment during synchronous meetings. Same with Participant 3's interaction with the parent; she also shared that this type of communication leads to a deeper relationship that ripples beyond the academic community and to a personal degree.

"If there are changes, no it... it became more. It... it... the relationship became closer. Yung we were able to build the relationship. More meaningful and deeper, more deeper and more meaningful relationships. Not only with students, but also their parents and colleagues. Like us, even friends, no friends who we were not able to communicate with for such a long time We were able to, you know, reach out to them. Sabi ko

nga hindi lang to magiging because of the pandemic. Lifetime na to kaya dumami yung... dumami na yung friends ko sa facebook kasi hindi, totoo. Kasi di ba sabi ko nga sayo, sa sobrang kabusyhan, sa sobrang kabusyhan sa school no talagang school bahay school bahay school bahay, hardly that I was able to have the chance na makausap sila.” – Participant 4

[If there are changes, no it... it became more. It... it... the relationship became closer. Yung we were able to build the relationship. More meaningful and deeper, more deeper and more meaningful relationships. Not only with students, but also their parents and colleagues. Like us, even friends, no friends who we were not able to communicate with for such a long time We were able to, you know, reach out to them. I have mentioned this before, that this is not just because of the pandemic. This is for life that is why I have gained... I have gained friends on Facebook. Like what I have said, due to busyness with school, my routine would be school-house school-house, hardly I was able to have the chance to talk to them.]

Despite facing the difficulty of obligatory setup, the participants are reaping the results of their efforts, as online communication for them leads to a different degree of closeness and connection to their students. The gap that has been brought about by age and setup has been bridged by shifts of practice and routine applied in communication. Seeing how both the educators and students are well aware of how the system goes in this situation, they find that sense of comfort in knowing that someone

understands them. That the person who meets them for synchronous classes, someone they consult for their academic growth, is also a person who cares for them and appreciates them on a much deeper level. In universities where parents and family members are not that expected to be more involved in the education of their child, building a greater sense of community up to this extent shows the level of effort that the participant showed to be able to form a stronger relationship, not just with their students, but also with their support system at home. And this continuity in openness and care for a student can greatly affect their self-esteem, leading to more active participation and engagement in online communication. Resulting in a positive environment that can start with just a single effort by an educator.

Actions speak louder than words

But not all triumphs came in the form of verbal affirmation for the participants; most importantly, they noticed a valuable change in the demeanor of their students. Through the initiatives and actions taken by the educator to bridge gaps, Participant 3 noticed that even the subjects that were once unappreciated by the students, became more enthusiastic about learning the course. Maximum participation was achieved, and the online platform did not restrict them from being active in class. Participant 4 also shared that she saw a change in the attitude of her students in class.

“That they became independent. That they became independent. Kasi they are on their own eh. That's the fact. Those people, those young people who seldom are heard during the traditionally set up the pre pandemic period kasi di ba, a class of 40, 25, 30 students yeah, you will not be able to hear them talk in one in 1/2 period. But during the pandemic

online class, wow, I was able to motivate everyone to speak. Kasi that brought out the talkative side of them. Yung... yung... talagang during the class. Online to ah, I was able to really listen, you know, and we were able to hear students who seldom talk when they during the time that it was not online.” – Participant 4

[That they became independent. That they became independent. Because they have to deal with it on their own. That's the fact. Those people, those young people who seldom are heard during the traditionally set up, the pre pandemic period, because a class of 40, 25, 30 students, yeah, you will not be able to hear them talk in one in 1/2 period. But during the pandemic online class, wow, I was able to motivate everyone to speak. Because that brought out the talkative side of them. That... during the online class, I was able to really listen, you know, and we were able to hear students who seldom talk when they... during the time that it was not online.]

It brings a different type of elation to be able to see a different side of your students. A positive change is something that we all need during those trying times, so to be able to see that sense of growth is a rewarding feeling at the end of a heavily pressured and trying educator. These participants have been in the field for a long period of time already. You might think that seeing moments in a student's life would just mean a random and unimportant part of their professional life, but as I dig into the life of a teacher, speaking in front of a group, and seeing how they transition into a better version of themselves is a sight that is beyond compare. And it is not even an instance where

you savor it for you to feel good about yourself, taking credit as if you have made it all possible, but it is those moments that you would know a young individual's life is bound to get even better because you know that they are motivated to be better. These moments made their rigor of braving through the uncertainty and challenges of the situation all worth it. And during my discussions with the participants, they spoke highly of the growth of their students; it was pure joy and appreciation for the type of person their students have become, without them knowing that they are part of that growth.

I am a Survivor

If there is one achievement that all participants agreed on, it is the fact that they survived those years in the fully online setup. The term "I survived" was mentioned and implied in different contexts, but all to commemorate how the experience was as a near-retirement educator during the obligatory online setup. They survived by learning countless software and applications just to make communication possible. They survived attending their first online meeting. They survived facilitating an online assessment just to check the integrity of the students' work. They survived by establishing a connection with their students that goes beyond academic conversations. This experience anchored numerous realizations in the minds of the educators. Having a newfound appreciation of online platforms such as email and group chats being useful, or, to put it simply, the survival of expanded communication,.

"We were able to survive and... and online learning is here to stay. Hybrid learning is here to stay. We can no longer go back to the traditional full face to face. You know we... We need to really adapt to the changes that are happening and are taking place. the... the best person, no, having any

sabi nga nila If you want to endure, you have to really embrace the changes. You know you have to cope with changes are going to happen and we have to be able to really learn from it. Hindi na pwede yung full, full face to face, you know, so you just fill in the minds and the thoughts and the... the thoughts of the students with so many information. Wala na yun, wag na yun, kasi talagang we have proven that it really didn't work. It really didn't work. So ayusin natin yung education system, because talagang the pandemic is what the education system was waiting for so that it could change finally. Finally.” – Participant 4

[We were able to survive and... and online learning is here to stay. Hybrid learning is here to stay. We can no longer go back to the traditional full face to face. You know we... We need to really adapt to the changes that are happening and are taking place. the... the best person, no, having any, they say that If you want to endure, you have to really embrace the changes. You know you have to cope with changes that are going to happen and we have to be able to really learn from it. Full face to face is no longer allowed, you know, so you just fill in the minds and the thoughts and the... the thoughts of the students with so many information. That will no longer be possible because we have proven that it really didn't work. It really didn't work. So let us fix the education system, because the pandemic really is what the education system was waiting for so that it could change finally. Finally.]

Given their track record, we can honestly say that they have seen the transition and changes in the field of education. They have endured more and pushed more for the love of molding and training future professionals. In the field of education, there will always be ceremonies that celebrate the achievements of the students, but the adaptation of our near-retirement educators to online communication and setup are all silent battles that they won. Celebrated in the littlest of ways, but its impact is seen in the improvement of their students. I can still recall the number of messages that I have received from my older colleagues saying that they have successfully mastered sharing their screen on Zoom, usage of breakout rooms, administering a poll for their class, strategic use of social media, and many more triumphs that solidified that they did not just survive that period. They won over the challenges and reigned victorious as these practices became a habit. A habit that helped them also become a better educator regardless of the setup. And being in this industry, I can say that teaching is not a profession that is financially rewarding. It is not a career for a person who seeks immediate monetary stability. So, for someone who is not fueled by financial reward, practically speaking, it is supposed to be easy to walk away and look for other opportunities, especially since these participants are holders of graduate and doctorate degrees. However, these heroes decided to stay for a long period of time, to withstand all these changes, all for the love of education. And this expansion in communication and education has resulted in reflection on the end of near-retirement educators. The participants expressed their willingness to be taught by the younger generation just to be fully versed in the online platform. These educators already master the 'what' when it comes to their lectures, but they are strengthening the 'how' of the platforms. And this specific mentality is what they want their students to also inculcate, to put a premium on learning. To continuously be a lifelong learner.

“Kasi say I refuse to still hang my jersey, kung basketball player ako, I... I refuse to still hang my jersey kumbaga... ayokong...uhm... I will approach retirement na ganon nalang na sige I own... I have reached this age already. I'm way over the hill. I don't need to really prove anymore myself, so I will not any more study this no because hindi kasi ako ganon because those those new stuff still excite me. Excited pa rin ako sa ganon no.” – Participant 4

[Because I refuse to still hang my jersey, If I'm a basketball player, I... I refuse to still hang my jersey. In other words, I don't want that... uhm... I will approach my retirement thinking that 'okay, I have reached this age already. I'm way over the hill. I don't need to really prove myself anymore, so I will not study this anymore.' No, I don't think that way. Because for me, those new stuff still excite me. I still get thrilled thinking of new learnings like that.]

A philosophy that we can all learn from. Age can be a factor, not as a restriction but as a place where you should anchor your aspiration. As someone who is still starting out in the field, we can make a lot of excuses for why we do not want to do certain things. However, we have to understand that growth will always be uncomfortable because it is something that we are not used to. Looking at how the participants approached the challenges and triumphs of the obligatory setup, the regret of not trying and doing what you can for the sake of relationship building should always be greater than the fear of failure.

Experiences of Near-Retirement Educators: Switching Gears

After experiencing the highs and lows brought about by the phenomenon, the near-retirement educators became smarter in how they dealt with changes and shifts. They took what was working and removed those that were no longer serving its purpose to help strengthen communication for education. Those experiences redirected the steps of the participants as they adjusted and adapted to the situation.

Boomer, the Explorer

With the intent of becoming a better educator for their students and building rapport despite the limitations of the setup, the participants conquered the technicalities and altered their approach to tailor it to the needs of the students and be leveled with their capabilities.

“Bilang teacher, kahit na sabihin nating at my age... uh... you have to... try other ways of communicating with the students you know hindi lang Zoom, MS Teams, marami pa. Ang natutunan ko dun ay,... as a teacher, you should always be open to new things, changes. Hindi ka dapat masettle na sa ‘ayoko na niyan, kayo nalang bahala diyan magretire nalang ako’. Kasi right now even if I’m retired already, nagtuturo ako sa maraming eskwela I teach part time in FEU. I teach part time in the De La Salle University. I teach part time in Batangas State University and I teach uh... face to face sa alma mater ko nung high school, St. Joseph’s Academy. So ibigsabihin ang advantage naman netong online namamaximize ko rin yung reaching out to different students from Senior High to college students to PhD students” – Participant 3

[As a teacher, even if we say that I'm already at this age... uh... you have to... try other ways of communicating with the students, you know. Not just Zoom, MS Teams, there are so many options. And what I learned is that... as a teacher, you should always be open to new things, changes. You should not settle for 'I no longer want this.', 'you deal with it, I will just retire.' Because right now even if I'm retired already, I still teach at different universities and colleges. I work part time in FEU. I teach part time at De La Salle University. I teach part time in Batangas State University and I teach uh... face to face at my own alma mater in high school, St. Joseph's Academy. So, for me, the advantage of online is I was able to maximize reaching out to different students from Senior High School to PhD students.]

The statement 'even if I'm already at this age' has been continuously used in different scenarios and narratives of the participants. With the prejudice that their generation is closed-minded and traditionalist, these four near-retirement educators are actively voicing out that they know when to bend and tweak their ways for the right reasons. Which is something that I have not seen nor encountered with any of my baby boomer professors back when I was still studying. What I have come across are those who let their students make all the adjustments with barely any effort from their end. That is why hearing these narratives from the participants is mind-altering experience for me as well. Proving that they are not boxed in the generalization that they evade the use of online communication platforms, but instead they explored more, beyond the needs of the teaching, all for building relationships and bridging communication gaps brought about by the online setup. This is a personal wake-up call for someone like me. I am well aware that I can navigate through any online or social media platform just for

the sake of it, but I am so fixated on my comfort zone that it hinders me from discovering more technological advances that I can use in my class. And through the conversations that I had with the participants, it was a reminder that I have no excuse for not learning more when these tenured educators are not closing their doors to any learning opportunities. In short, the near-retirement educators have the intent in improving their ICT skills, while some younger generations, like myself, have the ICT skills but no intent of going beyond.

As the participants mentioned, it has become overwhelming for them to orient themselves and maximize all the platforms available. They are slowly exploring the best social media platform to give and get updates from students.

“What we did was to look for an avenue whereby we can communicate with our students still and conduct our lessons. So what we did was here. You know, we had this messenger. Created group chat.” – Participant 4

“I try to start at the beginning when they offer to create group chats... group chats na kasali ako. Kaya sabi ko siguraduhin niyo na gusto ninyong kasali ako kasi makikita ko lahat ng exchanges ninyo so isinasali nila at lahat at dun pagnagcocomment sila ng about their assignments about their... about the people that they met during doing their outputs etchetera at sumisingit ako, uy nandito si ma’am. Thank you ma’am.” – Participant 1

[I try to start at the beginning when they offer to create group chats...group chats that I was a part of. That is why I said that they have to make sure that they really want me to be a part of that group chat because I will be able to see all their exchanges. And they did include me, they would often comment about their assignments... about their... about the people they met during doing their outputs etc and whenever I butt in and share my insights, they would say, 'uy ma'am is here.' 'thank you, ma'am.']

The word 'try' was given a different meaning for me after going through the narratives of the participants in their attempt to explore the best avenues for their students. Try became a symbol of courage, a manifestation of bravery, on the end of the tenured educator. And their consideration for trying is all based on what is best and most convenient for the students. I have seen numerous educators use their status and position to make everyone adjust to their wants. While the participants have all the reasons to do this as well, their humility is something that we can easily admire and imitate. Their stories and experiences became a manifestation of how a single act can greatly affect the output. It was mentioned that one of the struggles that they experienced in the full implementation of online communication—the lack of being 'present'—but the moment that they have entered the social media arena, the term 'seen' no longer has a negative connotation for their respective classes. Because once their students see that they are online, seeing all their exchanges, they instantly feel that you are there for them. I was once a student, and even now I still am. At a certain point, a student might feel nervous that their professor is seeing their messages, but that subsides and is replaced by the comfort of knowing that they are there to help. This starts a much more comfortable communication and relationship-building process

between educators and students. Although some participants already maximized the use of social media and online communication prior to the obligatory online setup, other participants were not open to this type of setup before the lockdown started. The hesitancy of being 24/7 open for students to reach out to has been a dismissed idea due to various reasons.

“At first no, noon, pre pandemic, iniisip ko waste of time lang yan eh imagine magseset up pa kami ng ganito, ganyan tapos it will take much of my time, tapos nung pandemic, wala talaga, I explored everything there are to explore.” – Participant 4

[At first no, before, pre pandemic, I used to think that it is just a waste of time, just imagine that you will set up this and that, and it will take much of your time, and during the pandemic, that mentality changed, I explored everything there are to explore.]

“I don’t like the.... The.... ano ‘to... the attitude or the behavior of the students being formed that anytime they can text you after 6 or after that so I reserve the phone before for urgent matters so yun lang din yun, pinipreserve ko din kasi alam kong may experience din ang co-faculty ko na wala kasing perspective... especially kasi I was teaching then undergraduate, so minsan walang perspective of time yung mga bata na madaling araw, alas dose, they expect you to answer.” – Participant 1

[I don't like the... the... what's this... the attitude or the behavior of the students being formed that anytime they can text you after 6 or after that so I reserve the phone before for urgent matters and that's about it, I preserve because I know that my co-faculty has an experience of students having no perspective... especially when I was teaching in undergraduate, sometimes, students have no perspective of time that even early morning, midnight, they expect you to answer.]

Being an educator demands that you should be on the constant beck and call of the students to be able to attend to their needs without causing any delay. And prior to the pandemic, this had already been experienced by a lot of our educators. However, it is a lot easier to set boundaries once everyone leaves school to go home; interaction between teacher and student is greatly minimized. But, coming into the online platform, it is much more difficult to know the limitations because of the blurred line between using it for academic exchange and for casual communication. Students might have misinterpreted the situation by thinking that since the setup can be synchronous and asynchronous, educators can also attend to their queries and concerns whenever they need to. And for someone who is like the participants, where they are just dipping their toes in the online communication platform, exploring what can be done, and given the type of lifestyle that they live outside of work where health and ample rest are prioritized, this can be a great eye-opener for them. I once had a passing discussion with my students about this notion, and they bravely mentioned that they are doing that because some educators are also assigning tasks and giving deadlines, even if it is way past their school hours. It is just their way of making things even. This conversation, although it opened up briefly, struck me as an educator because that is true. As an educator,

there are times that we have messaged our students way past the school hours for reminders, and the students also reached out to us beyond working hours. As mentioned by the participants, these are scenarios that they have observed, contributing to their valid reason why they do not want to jump on online communication prior to a fully online setup. There is a lot to unpack there, but as online communication and setup are here to stay in the educational context, both ends must also sharpen their netiquette.

The obligatory online setup forced a shift in their perspective, and the participants became more insistent on open communication and exerted effort just to compensate for the lack of physical connection during the online period. The participants made adjustments, such as including contact details to their syllabus, giving their social media accounts, and allowing flexible consultation hours just to be able to meet the needs of their students and increase rapport. And that came from the fact that they knew it must happen. They must do something to aid the situation. Looking at where we were during that period of time, the participants knew that their previous practice would not suffice anymore since they have to offer extended reach just to make sure that communication is accessible, in whatever way possible, for their students. From having a firm 'no' in social media to adding a good number of Facebook friends, piling up class group chats in Messenger, and announcing their cell phone numbers in class, it was not an easy yes for them, that is for sure, but it was a must 'yes' at that point.

Count on me, like 1, 2, 3

Even with their purpose strengthened, it was not as easy as how the younger educators navigated through online communication. Being well aware that they lack practice in technical aspects, the participants greatly acknowledge the assistance that they receive from colleagues and institutions that they work for. Team teaching became a way for them to address the concerns of the students without the fear of getting lost in the navigation of the online platform.

“I had the privilege also of as a senior faculty and as a Dean of being assisted by a young faculty member na siya ang sumasagot ng mga tanong sa Canvas... but... I’m... I’m... always present actually in the platform, except that I will only be asked to give... I would say supplementary lectures or main other materials.” – Participant 3

[I had the privilege also of being a senior faculty and as a dean of being assisted by a young faculty member that helps me when it comes to answering queries in Canvas (learning management system)... but... I’m... I’m... always present, actually on the platform, except that I will only be asked to give... I would say supplementary lectures or main other materials.]

“Plus the fact that... hindi kasi ako aware that much about the apps that are available. So all the available apps that there are, natuto ako on my own with the help also of young... younger colleagues na gumamit ng interactive apps like for example Quizziz, Kahoot, Poll everywhere, yung

mga madalas na ginagamit namin, edpuzzle, ano pa yung mga apps na we were able to really explore no.” – Participant 4

[Plus the fact that... I'm not really aware of the apps that are available. So all the available apps that there are, I learned it on my own and with the help of young... younger colleagues that are using interactive apps like, for example, Quizziz, Kahoot, Poll everywhere, those are the things that we usually use, ed puzzle, and other apps that we were able to explore.]

Their respective institutions also provide skills development training that can aid their initiatives in class, such as conducting training and seminars every time the institution implements a new platform for learning and communication. This manifested the importance of a strong support system for our educators. The personal intent of any individual to do more will be best supplemented and complemented by the evident assistance that they get from the people around them. And the mere fact that the four participants expressed and shared their adaptation to the phenomenon is somewhat influenced by the fact that they felt that it was not just them solely trying to make things better for themselves and for their students. But there is a helping hand that came in the form of seminars, buddy system, and orientations that make them feel provided for. Which makes it an ideal situation for them to try more, be more, and do more to build a connection because they know they have people to seek help from when times get a little more challenging, which it eventually did. It made me realize that there is a greater reason why we were assigned tasks as coordinators during the shift to be fully online. Among the other responsibilities that are entrusted to us, it is for the purpose of helping

these near-retirement educators navigate through unmastered territory. It was hard for us, but their narratives proved how much more difficult it was for them.

Access to Success

As much as the years in a fully online setup helped the participants understand the needed change and retention in their actions for the improvement of relationship building, it has also helped them discover the boundaries and limitations that they still have to set for themselves based on what they can and are willing to do. Participant 1 remained rooted in maximizing synchronous meetings as a way for his students to reach out to him. He still does not open his social media accounts or create group chats for work purposes; he only uses them for personal relationships, such as with family members. Participant 2 and Participant 4 expressed that they are in the process of assessing the extent of the necessity to learn.

“Because not that I’m that willing to learn, medyo nababawasan pa nga ako. Siguro nasa middle ako. May mga areas na siguro hindi ko na siya kailangan. I’m trying to make sure na yun naman sa mga satingin ko na kailangan ko pa, inaaral ko yun. If I won’t be able to master it at least I will be able to maximize what I know and with what I know I will be able to maximize its use so that I will be able to send across my message. Send across my message. Yun po yun.” – Participant 2

[Because not that I’m that willing to learn, actually I’m slowly losing the drive. I think I’m in the middle (when it comes to learning). There are areas that I can say that I don’t need anymore. I’m trying to make sure that for

those that I think are necessary, I explore it. If I won't be able to master it, at least I will be able to maximize its use so that I will be able to send across my message. Send across my message. That's it.]

*“Pero outright during the pandemic sinabihan ko na yung mga estudyante na ‘last resort ko ha facebook group at messenger’ if we could do it some other way, syempre request nila, mas madali ang communication, group chat, yung mga messenger sabi ko ‘may rule lang ako’ kasi sabi ko sa age ko na ‘to, ayoko na aralin, kayo na ang mag create ng group kasi ayoko nang aralin pa hindi ko naman ginagawa ever. So yun lang naman yung mga requirements na naintindihan naman nila. Actually ang akin ay understanding yung mga request ko sa undergrad kasi sila yung matechy. sa graduate students kasi marami kaming ganto *laughs* (meaning older in age).” – Participant 1*

*[But I mentioned to my student, outright during the pandemic, ‘my last resort is facebook group and message, okay?’. If we could do it some other way, as requested, for easier communication such as through group chat and messenger, I verbalized my request that I have a rule when it comes to its use. Because at this age, I don't want to be forced to learn about it if it is something that I'm not used to. They have to be the one that creates those group chats for us and they understood my request. Actually, undergrads are usually much more accommodating when it comes to my requests like this since they are more techy, but for graduate students, they have more excuses *laughs* (meaning older in age)]*

Baby boomers are said to have been welcomed and grew up with the existence of online communication. Like any phenomenon that comes their way, it is within their jurisdiction to determine whether they are going to embed it in their day-to-day routine. It would not totally disrupt their pre-existing practice, but it is more about how they chose to evaluate where it sits in their lives. That is why, it is not a surprise that they carefully assess and act based on their set limitations. Even if they are all for doing what is best and right for their students, they also take into consideration what they are capable of and comfortable with. On my end, it shows an intelligent way of dealing with a situation. Knowing where to channel your strengths, overcome your weaknesses, and explore opportunities for growth. It is also a must that we understand that not all efforts of each educator should be parallel. Just because that one educator is maximizing group chats and social media, does not mean that everyone else must follow their path. It is their own self-assessment that can dictate which approach works for them. However, I am firm in encouraging that all options and choices must be presented and explained to our educators for them to make an informed decision about which online communication for rapport works best for them. All in all, the adjustment in terms of the technicalities of online communication for relationship building has been a humbling experience for the participants. Participant 4 reiterated that after all these years of being in the academe, the mentality of knowing enough or a lot suffices for what is needed for her role. But then, the obligatory setup made her realize that there is more to learn. In the same way that they influence their students to pick up their books and increase their knowledge, it also applies to the educators as they become students to learn and unlearn.

Experiences of Near-Retirement Educators: Embracing the Change

The four participants expressed and showed how well they accepted changes, as they knew they were necessary. With their impressive credentials and foundation in hand, they shared a thing or two on lessons we can learn from when it comes to braving phenomena that pose a challenge in the field of communication in education. Showcasing who they are as educators will always win over what comes their way.

Redefining 'Boomer Energy'

It is ironic that Baby Boomers or near-retirement educators have years and years of exposure to online communication, given also the fact that they are surrounded by people and systems that are anchored on it; however, some, like these four participants, still chose to keep a measured distance with integrating and maximizing the use of the online platform. Given that they exhibit a traditionalist attitude with a hint of an attempt to jump on the bandwagon, they were not that motivated to exhaust the potential of the platform to build relationships with their students. That is why, Participant 3 is vocal about the fact that he is 'weak' when it comes to technology, but that weakness is compensated by his approach to his students. He firmly believes that you can still get to know a person regardless of what platform you use. How you communicate with them can still be their ticket to understanding who you are.

“Whether online or face to face, students will really know and feel.. the kind of person you are. Kahit na online, lalabas at lalabas din yung personality mo. As a teacher, as a person.” – Participant 3

[Whether online or face-to-face, students will really know and feel... the kind of person you are. Even if it is online, your personality will also be evident. As a teacher, as a person.]

And this specific philosophy is also implied by the participants, as they all adjusted their personal approach when dealing with their students. Showing that a person's character or personality is a huge consideration in the exchange or communication practice. And given the situation, where face-to-face communication is considered a health risk at that time, online communication is their only option to reach out and be 'present'. However, online communication is much more complex than meets the eye. It is difficult enough that they have to ensure the effectiveness of the teachings, but showing their personality when you are unsure if the person you are speaking to is even there, is a mountain that the participants are willing to climb. But it is much more evident that if your heart is pure, the genuine concern and love for your students are there; no unforeseen phenomenon can hide that fact. Teaching is a unique and unsung profession. Whenever an educator starts the lecture, they are not just sharing the lesson for that meeting; they will always, regardless of whether intentional or unintentional, share a piece of themselves. Personally, it is to make sure that the students know and acknowledge that a real person is in front of them, not a talking book. And teaching is not just defined by what can be read in a book but also by the stories that an educator and their students can impart, which makes teaching a much more personal exchange. And battling different challenges at that time, the participants understood that the emotional implications of the obligatory online setup were taking a toll on how their students perceived learning. And to help them, they became more expressive in appreciating the efforts of the students in school.

“...and I think at one point, I reminded them that the following meeting, I want them to be ready with their cameras and I called them one by one and I asked them to recite and I would... I would say... give them kind words when they are able to answer and participate well and that particular year I think.” – Participant 3

[...and I think at one point, I reminded them that the following meeting, I want them to be ready with their cameras and I called them one by one and I asked them to recite and I would... I would say... give them kind words when they are able to answer and participate well and that particular year I think.]

*“Alam ko naman ang personalidad ko, matagal ako or mabagal ako magbigay ng recognition or appreciation, yung well done well done. Parang ang nasa ulo ko kasi, if you know what you have done and it's good, you don't need that *laughs*. But I know, some people need that. So yun yung dilemma always so sige para lang nasa safe side, okay, excellent work, good job, yung mga ganong klase...” – Participant 4*

*[I know my personality, I'm not the one that easily gives recognition or appreciation such as saying 'well done, well done!' Because for me, if you know what you have done and it's good, you don't need that *laughs*. But I know some people need that. So it is a form of a dilemma for me. That*

is why to make sure that I'm on the safe side, okay, 'excellent work', 'good job', along those lines...]

This alters the notion on the students' end that older educators are much more closed-off compared to others. They understood that during that difficult time where they do not know what type of situation their students have at home. Through encouragement and verbal affirmation, the students can find comfort in knowing that there are people around them who appreciate their existence. Some continued this practice from their pre-pandemic period, while some participants used the situation as motivation to adapt this approach.

An Open Heart is an Open Mind

With the continuous adjustments, the relationship between the participants and their students became 'open' in so many ways and forms. Openness means a sense of accessibility. A participant expressed that they explored so many platforms just to better understand how they could get their message across. At the same time, openness is measured in terms of frequency and compassion.

"Compassion and lahat, hindi mo alam ang pinagdadaan ng estudyante so we, the faculty, has to exhaust all means to be able to reach out para lang malaman hindi nakapagsubmit dahil hindi nagawa, hindi magawa or dahil wala akong access at system para isubmit so kailangan malaman ano yung rason kung bakit hindi mafulfill yung requirements. It could happen that they got sick or it could happen that the family got sick so they have to take care so it has to be incorporated... So yung... yun yung

*talaga change... it's more of more communication with their students with regards to their accomplishments and status which is different nung pre-pandemic. Nung pre-pandemic kasi merong understanding na responsibility mo ang progress mo. Kung hindi ka pumapasok, acceptin mo yung consequences ng hindi pag pasok. Pag hindi ka nagsusubmit ng requirements, alam mo yung consequences ng hindi pagsubmit ng requirements, tanggapin mo *laughs* kung ano yung outcome. Ngayon sa pandemic, may... may konting puso eh *laughs* na lalabas. Maraming puso ang lalabas.” – Participant 1*

*[Compassion and all, you don't know what the students are going through so we, the faculty, has to exhaust all means to be able to reach out so that we know that they were not able to submit because they did not do their coursework, they do not have time to do it or they do not have any access to the system to submit. So we need to know the reason why they cannot fulfill the requirements. It could happen that they got sick or it could happen that the family got sick so they have to take care so it has to be incorporated... So that... those were the things that totally changed... it's more of... more communication with their students with regards to their accomplishments and status which is different pre-pandemic. During that time, there is an understanding that each student is responsible for their own progress. If they will not attend their classes, they have to accept the consequences. Know the consequences if they failed to submit their requirements, you have to accept that *laughs* whatever the outcome is. But during the pandemic, there... there is more compassion *laughs*.]*

It is said that aside from mastery of the subject, what fuels an educator more, is their heart for teaching. That is why, these are the types of people who genuinely wear their hearts on their sleeves. I have had my fair share of teacher-student interaction before. And some educators have the mentality that it is the student's sole responsibility to reach out and approach their teachers. Seeing countless interventions and discussions where it all boils down to the question, 'did you talk to me about it?'. Giving all the burden to the students. And hearing about the narratives of these near-retirement educators solidified that their compassion is what guides them. Going beyond what is expected just to check on their students, while for all we know they also have their personal battles during that time but the need to make sure that they are not lacking in extending an extra hand and guiding their students is still there. These scenarios are what pushes them to explore more and learn more about online setup, because by hook or by crook, they have to make communication happen. And this routine of teaching, checking up, and open communication became a habitual conversation that does not just focus on academic discussion but more on asking how their students are just to lessen that unwanted emotion during the obligatory online setup.

“Mas naging, mas naging ano siguro... kumbaga... frequent... kasi apart from apart from the classes, no apart from whatever we give them during class periods. No, we always see to it. That they're okay. Kasi pandemic yun eh, those were the years, not those And the years that you really want and you really wish that everybody's okay. Kaya from time to time pag may naririnig kami na parent na merong COVID I don't get to... we really see to it na 'oh ang mga bata kamusta?' How are you? How are you

coping? Sinong tumutulong sainyo? How are you able to get food? Kaya mas naging constant, mas naging close.” – Participant 4

[I have become more... more... what do you call this... because apart from the classes, no... apart from whatever we give them during class periods. No, we always see to it that they're okay. Because that is during the pandemic, those were the years, not those... and the years that you really want and you really with that everybody's okay. That is why, if I hear from parents that there is someone who has COVID, I don't get to... we really see to it that we ask them 'oh how are the kids?' 'how are you?', 'how are you coping?', 'who's helping you?', 'how are you able to get food?' that is why communication became more constant, and closer.]

In a single day, a teacher's and student's schedules are completely packed. Each class was only given a limited amount of time to meet synchronously, while the rest of the discussion and communication happened asynchronously and at their own jurisdiction. However, that is just one aspect of their day, they also have their administrative responsibilities, family obligations, and external commitments. However, even if the dynamics that primarily exist between the communicators is purely teacher to student on the grounds of academic exchange, supposedly restricted to lecture-based discussions, the frequency of communication and depth of conversation shifted. Another layer of openness is entertaining trivial conversations just to get their mind off the dangers and uncertainties of the situation.

“I give in kasi that is also one way of keeping our sanity. Kasi nag overthink ka na na ano kaya kung saakin dumapo yung Covid? Sa pamilya ko kumabit yung Covid, so to get that off your head no, sige magkita kami ng mga bata kahit online. Kya kahit kwentuhan lang na ma’am alam mo ba marunong na akong magbake, mam may bago na akong kanta sa spotify, yung mga trivial stuff na I don’t. I don’t usually entertain. I don’t usually entertain. Kasi syempre no, nung mga panahon na walang ganyan no, why would I entertain such stuff, do it sa mga kaibigan mo but not to me, Pero during that time, mas naging mahaba pasensya ko eh, talaga sige no, sige ano yang binebake mong yan, ano yang inaano mo, just to show na parepareho kaming maging okay, maging fine.” – Participant 4

[I give in because that is also one way of keeping our sanity. Because we tend to overthink what if you get COVID? Or my family gets it, so to get that off your head, we often have online meetings with the kids. That is why even if it’s random stories like ‘ma’am, did you know that i know how to bake?’, ‘ma’am, there is a new song on Spotify.’, trivial stuff that I don’t... I don’t usually entertain. I don’t usually entertain. Because why would I entertain conversations like that? They can tell those things to their friends but not to me. But during that time, I got more patient. I would ask them ‘what did they bake?’, ‘what are they doing?’, just to show that we are all going to be okay. We’re going to be fine.]

One way or another, this is their way of coping with the situation. Without them knowing, these conversations help both the educator and the student. We have also experienced being students, being pressured by so many things, and being in that awkward phase of being too young to be old but too old to be young. And during this difficult time, a simple question like, 'How are you?' is enough to make someone cry. And as all the students know, exchanges between them are healing their teachers as much as they are helping them. It does not go unnoticed how personal relationship building is during the online setup. Educators go above and beyond to make communication possible. With the uncertainty of whether a student will respond, or how they will make sense out of that initiative, we are not just doing it for us to get a high evaluation score after every semester; it is genuinely out of concern. Questions or messages checking on you might be annoying for students, but on our end, it is to make sure that you know someone is here ready to listen.

Formula for Lifelong Learners

But regardless of this new-found openness with their students, the participants also managed to remain mindful of what they do and how they speak to their students on the online platform. If face-to-face communication can still lead to misinterpretation, what more if you engage in a conversation with someone that you only identify by their username? The supposedly assistance of non-lexical components, and the lack of tone became a challenge, and caused the consciousness of the participants on how communication prospers.

“And of course it also has something to do with how you send your message. Let’s say the words that you are going to use...” – Participant 2

“...at tsaka sa online you have to be very, very careful also. Kapag nagagalit ka... Kasi narealize ko minsan nung nag open ng camera ang aking student, katabi niya ang mommy at daddy niya ...you have to watch your language, your behavior, di ba, kasi you do not know kung sino yung audience mo. Hindi lang estudyante di ba.” – Participant 3

[...and in the online platform, you have to be very, very careful also. If you get angry... because I realized that sometimes when the student opens their camera, their parents are seated beside them... you have to watch your language, your behavior, right, because you do not know who your audience is. It's not just your student.]

The added complexity of the setup led to extra precautions on their end. Even if there is no ill-intention on the educator's side, we do not know how anyone from the receiving end will interpret any message or make sense out of their actions on the online platform. With that, taking time to read through a message that is supposed to be sent out to the students, or thinking things through before addressing a situation in a class helps assure the educator that they are taking precautionary measures for the benefit of all. The obligatory online setup has been a challenging time for the educational sector. The near-retirement educators that are the participants of this study, can easily bid farewell to the academe given that they have served their time educating the youth. Regardless of how tough the situation got, it did not serve as their reason for leaving their profession but rather as an anchor that reminded them of their drive.

“I think in this profession. Teachers should be at the forefront of change. Otherwise, kung ayaw mo na, then you simply have to retire.” – Participant

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[I think in this profession. Teachers should be at the forefront of change. Otherwise, if you do not want to adjust, then you simply have to retire.]

“You have to embrace it. You have to find ways for the academe or the learning to continue. So kung ano yung available way for us, administrators and teachers, to continue our role, we have to learn, we have to... we have to embrace and we have to adjust. Kasi if you would not be able to adjust, as I’ve said, my advice is if you will not be able to embrace this change, then you might as well go. Kasi there’s still the continuity of learning eh. Ibang modality nalang ngayon. And yung sinabi mong mandatory and obligatory during the pandemic, iembracing mo talaga yun if you want to remain. That’s why madami ng umalis eh. Many left... many left.” – Participant 2

[You have to embrace it. You have to find ways for the academe or the learning to continue. So whatever the available way for us, administrators and teachers, to continue our role, we have to learn, we have to... we have to embrace and we have to adjust. Because if you would not be able to adjust, as I’ve said, my advice is if you will not be able to embrace this change, then you might as well go. Because there’s still the continuity of learning. But with a different modality this time. And what you have

mentioned as mandatory and obligatory during the pandemic, you have to embrace it if you want to remain. That's why there are so many educators who left. Many left... many left.]

Reminding us that it is not the age that motivates a person to retire, but the willingness to embrace the change that will come. The adjustments are driven by the shared experiences and narratives of the participants. And moving forward, Participant 4 highlighted that we may have triumphed over fully online communication during the pandemic, but their accountability and responsibility for regaining their students' rigor in learning and communication remain steadfast through proper communication for the lost, the least, and the last.

One's Transformation Causes Another's Awakening

Being born as a millennial, I have had my fair share of encounters with baby boomers. May it be through my extended family, teachers in school, or random strangers. And through this collective experience and, unconsciously, the influence of other perceptions as well, it fully shaped how I regard their generation to be. And going into this research, I already have my mind fixed on how I predict it will be. As ironic as it sounds, it is as if I am conducting quantitative research with a definite hypothesis that I am trying to prove, disregarding the variety of narratives that I might encounter depending on the participants that I have. But the type of participants I gathered proved me wrong. They are not at all boxed in by the characteristics that we depicted their generation to be. They are far more considerate, accepting of changes, and open to the adaptation of technology, contrary to the harsh generalizations that we easily conclude inside our heads. Being a part of the younger generation, we are meant to be influenced

by the older generation, whether we like it or not, especially in the academe where seniority and tenure are highly valued more than anything else. Being appointed as the online class coordinator in an educational institution means that you have to deal with reinforcing and imposing certain rules and regulations on these older, smarter, more experienced, and far more credible people than I am when it comes to the field. One thing we have to understand is that their years of experience, being at the center of technological advancements in education, are strengthened by their hearts. It is their passion for educating the youth that makes the impossible possible. That gives a clearer perspective on my end: their commitment to this field is not bound by what is happening in education but is defined by their core and passion for shaping the youth. And just by having that as the foundation, there is no question as to how far and how long these educators can withstand any phenomenon. It takes more than a complicated platform and online transition before you can tear apart a fortress-like individual who is fueled by heart.

So how do we deal with them? One thing I learned from the participants' narratives is that if the heart is willing, the helping hand must be giving. We deal with them by having a give-and-take relationship. We give them support, training, and assistance when it comes to sharpening their ICT and CMC skills, while we take influence from them in terms of compassion and heart in this profession. It must be understood that ICT and CMC will always be there, evolving, and continuously growing, but it is the user's end that determines whether it is something that they are willing to exert effort into, and for my participants, it is innate because of their passion and purpose. It dawned on me how much pressure was placed on the shoulders of these great educators, who graciously met and exceeded those expectations. It is just right that we take the next steps based on where it is most troubled. There is no issue when it comes to their

motivation and dedication in battling uncertainty, but there are just things that are bigger than they can control, one of which is the digital divide. It is a long-standing concept, but we cannot seem to overcome it completely. Because in reality, the digital divide's negative impact is much more felt and seen during that period. When everyone else has no other option to continue their lives than through a device, an internet connection, and a click away, some students and educators have the clear intent of adapting to whatever shift there is just to continue learning, but the unfortunate reality is that not everyone has the same privilege. In a single class, an educator cannot just let that student with marked incomplete requirements and absences during synchronous meetings be, without them making an effort to know what is going on. But what can be done when the supposedly only means to reach out to them is not possible? That ICT and CMC are not that dependable, as technology and computer-mediated communication are not an option for some individuals? They go back to the basics. We always paint baby boomers as too traditionalist to a fault. As if being intact with their practices and routines is always negative. But this time, it is not. It is a blessing for the students who do not have access to embrace the online shift completely. Who does not have the option yet to be online or to habitually attend classes via Zoom. The baby boomer initiative of text messaging and calling their students became the saving grace for them. This phenomenon proved that their weaknesses can be turned into strengths. A reminder that advancement should not mean abandoning traditional ways. It should not be separated from or as if an individual must pick only one when both can complement each other to serve their utmost purpose at any given time or period. We must admire how well these near-retirement educators have embraced communication technology for education. How much they are willing to explore and apply new and

profound ways of being on the same page and track as their fast-paced students. All for the love of communication to make education possible.

The same way that these near-retirement educators welcome and balance out everything to continue with the passion for education, this is an awakening of someone who strives to be able to make their path in educating the youth. We sometimes think that we already know enough to get through anything in this lifetime, but seeing the world from the perspective of these brilliant educators, who have spent every waking day staying true to their oath, has become a perfect motivation for me to still be teachable. Continue learning, as it will never stop. You will never reach a point in your life when you can say that you have learned enough, because there is still so much to gain as you live every single day. And with their lived experiences shared, it puts me to shame on how much I have rejected growth just by sticking to my comfort zone and neglecting new opportunities through embracing change. As they continue to navigate their way through open communication and strengthened relationships, may it be on online or offline platforms, speaking as one of the online class coordinators, we will make sure that their rigor to learn will be supplemented well by endless support and assistance to boost their confidence in surviving anything, regardless of age, platform, and phenomenon.

And as a younger educator, I consider myself lucky and blessed to be able to encounter these types of inspiration at the early stage of my teaching life. It makes perfect sense why they have been in this industry for a long time, and I must say that they have raised the standard that I have set for myself when it comes to becoming the best teacher for my students. May the heart that they continuously wear on their sleeves, and the character they freely show to everyone they encounter be my constant

reminder of doing more and being more, like what they have told me, for the lost, the least, and the last.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

With the imposition of a full transition to online learning, the instructors became more active in communication just to make education possible. Although online learning is no longer a new practice in instruction, the Philippines, with more hurdles and difficulties in making this a prime setup for our learners, still chooses to stick with the traditional ways of teaching and learning. But with the face-to-face setup becoming obsolete due to the health risk, online mode became obligatory for all, regardless of a person's background, skill, resources, and age. This phenomenon brought about narratives and experiences from different points of view. While there is a great deal of study about the student's adaptation or efficiency of the setup, there is little to none that focuses on the perspective of the educators, especially those that are valued for their tenureship or those that are near-retirement but with exceptional passion for the field. This study seeks to understand the stories behind four near-retirement educators, belonging to the baby-boomer generation, and their wins and trials when it comes to fully online communication with their students to establish rapport and connection.

Summary

Following the hermeneutic analysis, where statements of the participants are assessed in a cycle to give depth to their meaning, individually or treated as a whole, the narratives of the four participants resulted in four emerging themes that discuss

the challenges, triumphs, changes, and realizations that answer the two research questions focusing on the experience and adaptation of the participants.

For the Cause of Disconnect, that expounds on their struggles, the participants shared how their age affected their perspective of how they should go about the fully online communication setup. This factor dictates and limits their action. Being one of the tenured faculty in their respective institutions, the majority of the participants already hold an administrative position alongside their teaching function. The participants shared how their age affected their perspective on how they should go about the fully online communication setup. Prior to the shift in mode, a participant already had the mentality that online communication was necessary for their generation. However, the times forced them to change their perception of 'I cannot do it anymore' to 'I must embrace the new norm'. The willingness to abide by the new platform of communication is there, but position also hinders free and open communication due to the students' hesitancy to approach someone who is in authority. Skill sets are highly important in making online communication possible; however, participants expressed that learning the platforms proved to be one of their greatest hurdles. They have to orient themselves on how to navigate through their respective learning management systems, video conferencing, check outputs, and maintain open communication with their students all at once. And the reality that not everyone is on equal footing when it comes to online access resulted in some participants going back to traditional ways of building connections with their students, such as text messages. But they must keep the spirit of being present for their students despite the challenge of online communication, that is why they emphasize the importance of constant Zoom meetings or conferencing with their classes. However, the lack of nonverbal cues, body language, or a sense of being actively present in

those meetings proved to be difficult for the near-retirement educators. It became questionable for them whether the communication that they are initiating is still a two-way engagement or purely one-way without the students making the effort to show that they are there, listening. Banter and jokes that are usually a way to make their relationship lighter as teacher-student became obsolete on the online platform, as both ends are usually greeted with black squares on the screen and silence.

But despite the difficulties that the participants faced as they adjusted to the new norm of education and relationship building, there were triumphs that made the adjustment worthwhile, as discussed in *Triumph to Reconnect*. Even if students are not that vocal during online class discussion, they, along with their parents, have been more expressive when it comes to showing gratitude for the efforts of their teachers. The participants also learned that their efforts to keep communication constant and open, resulted in a deeper and more personal connection with their students. This is manifested in the shift in demeanor, effort, and enthusiasm of their students every time they communicate. In the same way that near-retirement educators are catalysts for learning, they themselves are proud of their new-found willingness to learn, not just for themselves, but also for the welfare of their students.

Through *Switching Gears*, the participants described their survival of the obligatory online communication as a way for them to stay afloat because they have accepted that online learning and communication are here to stay. And their ways to adapt will still be a continuing practice, regardless of the current state. Adjustment to the technicalities or demands of online setup, such as mastering the navigation and function of each platform or application or exploring new ways to deliver learning, is one of their go-to practices now. They are also appreciative of the extended help from their institution, such as conducting training and seminars to strengthen their skills and

tapping younger colleagues for team teaching and assistance in implementation and monitoring. These practices have greatly changed their perspective on the importance of online communication, and they solely emphasize that they do it for the benefit of their students more than anything else. However, despite their willingness to embrace the change, the participants expressed that this is up to a certain extent only and have set a limit as to what they can do. The constant assessment of whether a specific adjustment is necessary will be a major consideration for them, as well as the establishment of and abiding by their own dos and don'ts.

Lastly, Embracing the Change serves as a testament to their dedication in the field. Regardless of the platform or the period of time, the participants have been reminded that their personal approach remains an effective way for them to bridge gaps and physical distances with their students. This means showing compassion, expressing kind thoughts, and motivating and encouraging their students, which go hand in hand with the frequency of communication. Openness in all aspects that can help them and their students as well. Despite the difficulties and changes the near-retirement educators experienced during the obligatory online setup, it made them love the profession more. Their purpose and role in society motivated them to remain steadfast amidst the uncertainty of the situation.

Conclusion

In an industry where lessons are learned and clearer life paths are formed, you might think that the most important organ in the human body is the mind. But the hour-long conversations with these tenured faculty showed me that minds might form wisdom, but it is the heart that gives purpose.

The educational sector is no stranger to shifts and changes that alter the customs and practices of delivering knowledge to students. Whether this transition is man-made or due to a natural phenomenon, the act of teaching on any platform and intergenerational interaction will always be regarded as a continuous process of trials and triumphs to attain effectivity (Patella, 2022). With more than 40 years of service under their belt and thousands of students educated, there is no doubt that the Baby Boomer generation, or near-retirement educators, have prepared the professionals that we have today. And despite the challenges of the obligatory setup, the decision to stay true to their mission of molding and shaping the future of the youth is beyond question. As I listen to their narratives, I discover the underlying reason for what it takes for educators like them to stay in this profession for a long period of time.

When we think of the older generation and their immersion in technology, resistance will always be mentioned, but after carefully analyzing the experiences and adaptations of the participants, it shows us the perfect balance between heart and capacity. It is an assessment of what they can do best and how they can make up for the things that they are incapable of or inexperienced in. The years under their belt were never an excuse for them to slack off and just give up on making an effort in communication and relationship-building on a new platform. But it became a way for them to sharpen their skills, challenge themselves, and find balance between what works and what does not work for them. Embracing the marriage between passion and capacity, giving in and setting boundaries, traditional acts, and new-found practice.

ICT and baby boomers may not seem to be the ideal mix, as there are complexities and considerations in ensuring maximum use, but an educator's passion for teaching and character in connecting to their students are far greater than the hindrances and

difficulties of obligatory online setup. Proving that their years in service did not just give them a better understanding and depth of knowledge in their respective fields but also a better mentor outside of academic relationships or connections.

We may be at the stage where we can now turn off our cameras and switch off our laptops for the resumption of face-to-face interaction and connection, but the learning and experiences brought about by the setup, will always be a brand new standard for those whom we always see as 'know it all' given their tenureship, but it turns out, they are willing to embrace changes and shifts not just because they care for their students' grades but most importantly, their welfare.

Recommendation

The current state of our educators and the whole education system is a wake-up call for our governing bodies, such as the Department of Education (DepEd) and Commission on Higher Education (CHED), to be able to create programs for preparedness in facilitating any form of learning delivery. Establishing a standardized minimum requirement for ICT and CMC enhancement and training for all academic institutions can guarantee smooth and effective implementation of education. On the other hand, this initiative should not solely focus on the navigation and familiarization of each platform that can be maximized but instead also harness the interpersonal and communication skills of each faculty that foster healthy relationship building between faculty and students. Likewise, this can be best complemented by academic institutions' buddy system or team teaching, partnering tenured faculty with those with advanced mastery or familiarization of ICT can promote collaboration for best practices and effectiveness in instruction.

Lastly, never give up on seasoned faculty. Some schools prefer to hire younger faculty just for easier technical adaptation with a minimum pay requirement, but if there is one thing that young educators should learn from these tenured faculty, it is their prioritizing of character and their students.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: Interview Guide

With the study's aim to understand the experience of near-retirement educators on online communication for relationship building during the obligatory online setup and its pursuit of the unstructured interview, encouraging the participant to freely tell their experiences and stories, the following guide questions, but not limited to, shall be considered as reinforcements should the participants hesitate or find it difficult to formulate a response:

1. How long have you been a teacher? In the course of your career, what is your perception of the importance of communication as an educator?
2. Can you share or explain your pre-pandemic communication practice with your students? Do you maximize online communication then?
3. Can you share your experiences with fully online communication set up during the pandemic? What are your ways to communicate with your students and the outcome?
4. What are your triumphs in the course of fully online communication with your students?
5. What about your struggles?
6. How do you think the pandemic changed the way you used online communication to establish connections with your students?
7. What are the aspects of your online communication practice that you wish you could improve or that the institution could help you improve?

APPENDIX B: Informed Consent Form

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Informed Consent Form for **No Teacher left Offline: A hermeneutic study of online communication for near-retirement educators at universities in NCR.**

Good Day,

I am Krizelle R. Amoyo, a graduate student of the University of the Philippines-Open University (UPOU) conducting a study on the lived experiences of near-retirement or baby boomer educators when it comes to obligatory online communication set up with their students during the pandemic, as an academic requirement for the Master of Development Communication program.

In line with this, I would like to ask for your participation in this research study entitled No Teacher Left Offline: A hermeneutic study of online communication and relationship building for near-retirement educators at universities in NCR. You were referred to me by one of my colleagues, and I am certain that your insights and experiences can greatly help in shedding light on the triumphs and trials of online communication.

By all means, your participation is voluntary. Your participation will come in the form of a 30-minute to 1-hour interview, online or offline, depending on your preference and availability. Specifically, the questions that would be asked seek to know your teaching background, communication practice with your students prior to the pandemic, experiences in fully online communication, and the highs and lows. Changes in your communication practices to establish a connection with your students during the obligatory migration to the fully online platform, and points for improvement. Should there be any questions that can cause discomfort, embarrassment, or negative emotion, you may opt not to respond, and the interviewer will move on to the next question. And should you wish to withdraw at any point, it will be respected by the researcher, and all information disclosed will be removed. All the information that will be gathered will only be used for the stated purpose. It shall be recorded and analyzed for the achievement of the paper's objective. All data will be stored for 3-5 years and shall be deleted afterward. The researcher assures you that your privacy will be prioritized.

Should you be willing to participate in this study, kindly sign the consent form below.

Thank you, and stay safe!

CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it, and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study that seeks to analyze the experiences of near-retirement educators with online communication during the obligatory set-up of the pandemic.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

Date [MM/DD/YYYY]: _____

APPENDIX C: Transcription of Interview with Participant 1

Speaker	Statement
Researcher	Okay. And of course po Participant 1, I want to introduce myself first before we start the interview proper. I am Researcher R. Amoyo. I am currently finishing my Master of Development Communication in UPOU and I am currently working as a senior high school faculty in FEU Alabang and I'm also working as the online class coordinator that is why I take interest in this specific topic. Because I want to make sure that our teachers... we will be helping our teachers not just in facilitating and implementing online classes since we are following blended learning but of course helping them in communicating and building relationships with their students even in the online platform. So, I am conducting a student entitled No teacher left offline: a hermeneutic study of online communication for near-retirement educators at universities in NCR. So, I will be asking you a few questions. I believe I have sent you a copy...
Participant 1	Yeah. I saw that. I saw that.
Researcher	But please also allow me to inject on the spot questions...
Participant 1	Sure, that's okay.
Researcher	... and follow up questions as we go along with the interview. Thank you so much. So I think we can start already.
Participant 1	Yeah, go ahead.
Researcher	Once again, good afternoon, Participant 1. Please please introduce yourself first po.
Participant 1	Okay, I'm Participant 1. uhhh Professor 12 of UP Asian Institute of Tourism and I've been, part of your question anyway is how long I have been teaching...
Researcher	yes
Participant 1	So, more or less, 40 years of teaching. So I'm retiring anytime soon. December extended. So...my... I think you will ask as well my birthday so I might as well...
Researcher	yes
Participant	...give it to you now, September 29, 1958. So... I think

1	that's about it. I have a PhD in Tourism Management and I'm handling graduate and undergraduate courses.
Researcher	Okay. Thank you so much for that Participant 1. I would like to ask since we are already discussing your background when it comes to teaching, ever since po for 40 years, you've been handling undergraduates or you also have an experience when it comes to basic ed or whatnot.
Participant 1	No. I don;t have any experience in senior high downwards elementary. So my experience is really collegiate and post-graduate or graduate courses. So I started teaching...uhhh...graduate degree course in EIT I think in 2018...
Researcher	Okay
Participant 1	Or 2017. We started our graduate program but I have been teaching as a visiting professor in Taiwan and Chang Mai, Thailand for master's level as well as I've handled some PhD advising as well.
Researcher	Ah okay so, Participant 1, you have experience both locally and international
Participant 1	Yeah
Researcher	In terms of teaching
Participant 1	Oo kasi I got... I think I was 4 years or 5 years on call visiting professor in Chaiyi, National Chaiyi, Chaiyi is in Taiwan. And then I was visiting professor for about 2 years teaching in Chang Mai, Medio University in Chang Mai Thailand and I've been involved in their PhD degree advising and panel for about 6 years.
Researcher	Ah okay po
Participant 1	Kasi wala kaming PhD. Walang PhD sa EIT so I grabbed any opportunity na iniinvolve ako for PhD mmmm
Researcher	Ah okay po. So thank you so much po for that quick background. And of course po Participant 1, I want to understand your communication perspective as a teacher. Ano po yung perception ninyo when it comes to the importance of communication especially when it comes to building relationships with your students.
Participant 1	It's essential. You cannot go I think, teaching, without the proper communication and the means of open communication channels. So without communication

	<p>channels, you wouldn't be able to know what's going on with your students. And I don't...I'm not the person or I'm not the faculty that is pure lectures. That just gives powerpoint, lecture...lecture...lecture then exam but I prefer discussions. So uhhh at some point, maybe at my teaching career, siguro uhhhh mid through the years that I've been teaching that I've gotten the confidence of all the teaching subjects that I have. So the powerpoints are just props. Uhhh beforehand uhhh before the lecture it is already given to them so it is purely discussion. So I prefer to ask whether they understand the powerpoint or which aspects of the powerpoint they would like to have more explanation, discussion. So mas interactive. I prefer more interactive, even before the pandemic. I... I tend to have that uhhh in the classroom so that is my means of communication with them...within the classroom</p>
Researcher	Opo
Participant 1	<p>Outside the classroom, it is the openness for consultation. The consultation before the pandemic is always face to face. So we have consultation hours and they can run to you if they are some matters of the course that they...they have problems with. So it's more of advising face to face before the pandemic. We have at least 10 hours as university rule but I do more than 10 hours...</p>
Researcher	Ah okay
Participant 1	<p>And then I don't mind uhhh students reaching out to me by phone. So I... although on a request basis. Hindi... nung pre-pandemic hindi ko inooffer kaagad. Uhhh If you need it, I can give it to you but it is not... noon hindi siya... hindi ko nilalagay sa syllabus during the pandemic it is required so nandun na. So communication for me is very important.</p>
Researcher	<p>Okay po. So that is an interesting take Participant 1 so before po, pre-pandemic, open ka po makipag face-to-face consultation but yung using of phones hindi mo po talaga siya iniintroduce, as needed lang po siya.</p>
Participant 1	<p>Oo kasi I don't like the.... The.... ano 'to... the attitude or the behavior of the students being formed that anytime they can text you after 6 or after that so I reserve the phone before for urgent matters so yun lang din yun, pinipreserve ko din kasi alam kong may experience din ang co-faculty ko na wala kasing perspective... especially kasi I was teaching then undergraduate, so minsan walang perspective of time yung mga bata na madaling araw, alas dose, they expect you to answer. So at least managed ko yun, managed ko</p>

	yung expectations nila na gamitin niyo lang ito pag kailangang kailangan at in advance. If nafoforesee ninyo na magkakaproblema na kailangan ninyo yung number ko, cellphone, then I can give it to you.
Researcher	Okay
Participant 1	Yun lang yun per nung pandemic, burado yun lahat binigay ko *laughs*
Researcher	*laughs* nung dumating po yung pandemic, nagbago po talaga...
Participant 1	Oo
Researcher	But of course, Participant 1, I want to ask also, namention niyo po kanina yung academic type of openness niyo po with your students. What about when it comes to relationship building? Are you the type of professor that they can easily approach kahit hindi academic yung concern like may problem si student, magoopen up sa inyo.
Participant 1	I don't think yung personality ko kasi ganon. Although there are some students who have been close and they open up but ... honestly I project to be a strict, I project to be a strict uhhh faculty na medyo hesitant kasi nga medyo older, I'm one of the oldest not the oldest, faculty in the line so medyo may generation gap siguro for the rest but there are some who... who... just drop by and cry *laugh* in front of you and during the course of my ... ano ba 'to... service to the university kasi magkakaiba kasi nga 40 years na ako so during the time na college secretary ako ng 9 years. So during that time talaga, crying mode. Whoever will need uhh... uhh ano 'to... somebody to listen to them, that's part of my work as college secretary so I was closer then to the students. So even the student council, student organizations pag may problema takbuan lahat kasi college sec ka dapat service sa students but when I became the dean, 2016... 2013 ata yon to 2017, I was the dean for 6 years and 6 months, *laughs* tandang tanda, pero yung... nagbago yung tingin eh, merong takot. Nandun na yung takot pero at least I project that they can still approach me. Kasi may layer na na pwede silang iapproach, may college sec na, may student relations officers na, so mangilan ngilan nalang pag problemado talaga na sometimes ang problema ay non-academic, family matters na yun. May mga moments naman na takbuan kasi may mga issues, love problems at merong mental health issues na so I can refer them to... to...

	uhhh...proper services sa university but outside the services of the university there are some na it goes beyond... na... na... personal relationships na I formed through the years may mga ilan na 20 years and 30 years we have been friends. They considered uhhh... I mentored them... parang nasundan ko yung career nila tapos diredirectcho pa rin hanggang ngayon ang relationship na nagtransform na instead of faculty-student relationship, it is a colleague relationship kasi faculty na sila. Yung iba dean na din sa ibang kolehiyo tapos yung iba nasa abroad na nagtuturo at lahat but we communicate continuously. So I have maintained those relationships with them.
Researcher	Ah okay po. So it varies po no? Depende sa type ng student na kausap mo. And you've mentioned a while ago, your position din po.
Participant 1	And my age. And my age. *laugh* *overlapping* go ahead
Researcher	I was about to ask po paano niyo po nasabi that age is a huge factor when it comes to communicating with your students
Participant 1	Yeah because as I grow older I see the change in the way they see me.
Researcher	Mhmmm
Participant 1	Kasi when I was younger, parang barkabarkada.
Researcher	Yes
Participant 1	And as I grow older, parent na ang dating. Na... sa... ang ineexpect kaya naghehesitate na magapproach is pagagalitan. Especially, for me age and position, malaking factor din yun na nagbabago yung relationships sa students kasi pag merong authority na... uhhh... like administrative uhhh... work ka na they, students I think, think of the consequences when they approach you. Specially if the problem is like uhhh... concern with faculty members or may complaint sila sa mga faculty or magrereport sila ng mga ano... sa mga klase nila at lahat, when I became the dean, kumonti yun kasi merong fear na babalikan ko yung faculty. Tapos pag binalikan ko yung faculty, babalikan sila. So yun yung, I think I've seen the changes but when I was just a faculty, wala akong college sec, wala akong faculty, mas open sila eh. Pagchichismisan namin yung faculty *laughs* na ano yung ginawa nila sa ganon, ano yung ayaw nila dun sa mga klase nila. Open sila, open sila. But once I

	hold an admin position, cautious parang ganon.
Researcher	Parang nageset na po sila ng boundaries
Participant 1	Yes, and ako rin naman nageset na rin ng boundaries at some point kasi college sec naman, nung dean ako I really, I was really really conscious of how I deal with students because I didn't like to hear the favoritism... line na 'uy siya lagi siyang pumunta kay dean ako hindi' mga ganon. Even at that point in time, social media is already active. So I have also put in my boundaries in terms of how I participate in social media. Kasi merong, feel ko lang naman, meron consequences during that time when I started to be the dean and until now I refrain from posting. I refrain from even greeting students kasi may incident na kakadean ko (palang), eh close ako sa ibang estudyante, grineet ko lang na happy birthday tapos ang comment biglang 'oyyy grineet ako ng dean' eh yung mga ibang estudyante hindi ko naman nagegreet so sabi ko 'opps wag na baka maging iba ang interpretasyon ng lahat' so I've been very cautious since that time because of my position.
Researcher	Okay po. So you have mentioned already the use of social media. I want ask Participant 1, pre-pandemic, are you already utilizing online communication, social media, in terms of reaching out to your students. Like announcements...
Participant 1	Yeah we did that but I was not so active. It's all on official channel, not my personal post. I don't make announcement on my personal post. It's always through an official EIT profile or channel but we used it in communicating with our students if they are based abroad. Ang crucial... siguro ang magandang example ko dito ay during the time na meron kaming on the job trainee sa thailand na, I think 11 or 12 students tapos nagkaroon sila ng political situation, sinara ang bangkok, airport and everything, through social media kami nagcommunicate. So messenger everything to tell them 'hintayin niyo lang', 'pumunta kayo sa embassy' mga ganong klaseng communication. So that's the means kasi hindi lahat sila merong cellphone nung pumunta silang bangkok, hindi sila nakakuha ng sim card. So it's more of the facebook messenger etcetera so yun yung naging official channel before pandemic, nagagamit namin.
Researcher	Opo. Okay, Participant 1 actually yung huge difference when it comes to online communication pre-pandemic and pandemic is that, perfect example po yung sinabi ninyo kaninang story, kasi during that specific situation, correct me if I'm wrong, that's the only way for you to reach out to

	your students
Participant 1	Yeah kasi yun lang yung free eh. Uhhh... yung... uhhh... wala ng iba kasi telephone, hindi landline kasi midnight yun mga yun eh tapos crucial na masabihan sila 'wag kayong lumabas...' kasi madaming rally sa area nila at yung assurance, assurance nila... sakanila na estudyante na nandito kami na nakikinig at may ginagawa kami tapos yun din kasi sunod sunod na rin yung communication ng mga magulang, oo. Yun yung at least namanage until napauwi sila. Yun yung... nadulot or nacocontribute I think ng social media sa communication... online that was not available before
Researcher	Since during that time that is your only way to communicate with them how about for your local students, pre-pandemic, preferred niyo pa rin po si face-to-face
Participant 1	Nung pre-pandemic, honestly, ayokong magsocial media with my students. Because I feel... sometimes it's intrusive to privacy. So as much as possible, minange ko security, ako lang, ako lang... manggaling saakin dapat ang start (ng online communication). Although some tried to befriend, na iaadd, kasi pre-pandemic pa yung pagka dean ko eh kaya. For me hindi naman yung pre-pandemic and post-pandemic yung malaking bagay eh, for me it's more of my position and my role in the university during that period. Siguro yun yung nakadagdag... nagpabago nung pandemic, sige mag open na, sige magamit na nga. Yung mga ganon. Pero outright during the pandemic sinabihan ko na yung mga estudyante na 'last resort ko ha facebook group at messenger' if we could do it some other way, syempre request nila, mas madali ang communication, group chat, yung mga messenger sabi ko 'may rule lang ako' kasi sabi ko sa age ko na 'to, ayoko na aralin, kayo na ang mag create ng group kasi ayoko nang aralin pa hindi ko naman ginagawa ever. So yun lang naman yung mga requirements na naintindihan naman nila. Actually ang akin ay understanding yung mga request ko sa undergrad kasi sila yung matechy. sa graduate students kasi marami kaming ganto *laughs* (meaning older in age). So yun lang yung ano...
Researcher	Okay po, so now that we basically talked about your pre-pandemic. I want to understand naman po, what's your experience during the pandemic. Since during the pandemic po, total shift po talaga. Face-to-face is no longer an option, we are obligated to use the online platform. So can you share po yung experiences ninyo when it comes to online communication as a faculty po?

Participant 1	<p>The first semester... yun yung... big adjustment period. Especially yung time na pinagawa kami ng course pack for the whole semester. We would complete the... all the...activities, resources, dapat naka set na siya kasi isesend siya, either printed doon sa mga walang internet access 'di ba. So you have to make provision, it will be an addition compared to uhhh... the pre-pandemic. Pre-pandemic you only have to prepare for face-to-face, sometimes just the syllabus and we only have to prepare one week before or two weeks before, all the activities and requirements, that's a big change, that's a big adjustment, the preparation for the whole semester and make the course pack. And the complete course design and study guides for the students at the beginning of the semester. So yun, required so ginawa. Nagawa naman so... uhhh... choices lang na bibigyan ng leniency in terms of na... that first semester kasi is 'sige hindi niyo matapos yung buong semester course design, kalahati, kalahati' pumayag na first seven weeks activities, unahin niyo muna. Yung susunod... at least may adjustment doon. That's the first adjustment doon or hurdle na ginawa. The next is the platform... the platform that will be used. Yung UVLE at that time may mga faculty na na gumagamit. Ako yung isa sa mga hindi *laughs*</p>
Researcher	Sorry Participant 1 ano po yung UVLE?
Participant 1	<p>Ay hindi mo ba alam yun. Yung University Virtual Learning Ex... ano ba yung E.... yung provided ng UP Diliman computer center na parang Google Classroom, Moodle... moodle, UVLE ang tawag diyan which is linked to the CRS. It is linked to the registration system. So automatic yoon. So yung hindi ko pa siya ginagamit, so hindi ko siya gamay. Pero yun yung unang suggested. I tried... Madali naman siyang kapain. Then, the next is in terms of choice, dumating na yung Google Classroom, then Zoom... then siguro yung second hurdle ko is andami... andami kong aaralin di ba, adjustment in terms of the different platform. It is being given that the student and the faculty has the choice in terms of the platform but it could happen that the students would choose all. At some point, lahat yun available eh. They can shift to UVLE to Google Classroom tapos synchronous is Zoom. The others... uhhh... lahat nalang Google Classroom kasi meron naman siyang... meron naman siyang pang ano... uhhh... chat and parang discussion mode, that's the... next concern ko, the platform. So para mamanager ko siya, isa lang ginagamit ko *laughs*. Isa lang *laughs*. Zoom lang at tsaka nung una, shared Google Drive *laughs*, yun lang ang alam ko, yun lang ang alam ko. Aaralin ko pa kasi yung (Google)</p>

	<p>Classroom, aaralin ko pa kasi yung UVLE. So the first semester is really Zoom and I gave my powerpoint and my Zoom parang face-to-face discussion 'anong problema niyo? Anong hindi ninyo maintindihan? Nagawa ba ninyo assignment ninyo?' ganon ang situation, very very seldom that I do the powerpoint in Zoom because mahina din ang internet ng mga estudyante hindi rin nila nakikita yung share screen at tsaka ako rin naman nawawala dahil sa internet ko. It was like a rule at the beginning, before each of the lessons, you have to see and to read the learning resource for that module. Tapos yun na yung dinidiscuss. 'Oh hindi niyo pa nababasa, oh ito iintro ko pero basahin ninyo' then the next is discussion 'oh anong problem? Anong yung questions?' then they can ask. I require them to note down questions as they see the powerpoint as they read. But before the synchronous, hindi kami sabay sa synchronous, sayang oras *laughs* pag ganon. At yung mga panahon na unstable pa yung internet ng mga bata. So it's more of trying to put in time, this I observed more on the undergrad, that they have less capability in terms of access, internet access at gadgets. Dito ko rin naranasan yung disparity of social classes. Yung classes natin dito sa Pilipinas. Because there are some students using only a cellphone. There are some students that they have to go to the farm or field to get internet connection. So... at this point... kwan ano na ko na... nashare ko na lahat ng cellphone ko. They can call me if they want to discuss anything. They can text, they can message and the I shared also na to my students my Facebook.</p>
<p>Researcher</p>	<p>Ah okay po.</p>
<p>Participant 1</p>	<p>Open na ako. Na sige kung imessenger mo na ako. Sa graduate student. Puma... uma... kinuha pati viber, yung mga ganong klase. Pero sa undergrad walang ganon. Sanay sila sa ano... sanay sila sa FB, Facebook. So yun yung sa pandemic na hurdle. It's the... learning different technology na kailangan mong... matutunan at positive lang saamin, positive lang sakin, kasi I was able to accumulate my gadgets through the years, so I have my gadgets. The needed laptop, the needed cellphone, the needed everything, which I don't know for other faculty that is why meron support noon pati computer, pati internet, meron ata kaming allowance for internet so... and then isang kailangan iadjust, kailangang mag pa increase ng bandwidth *laughs* sa internet may backup na hindi lang isang service provider. Like meron kaming converge, meron kami sa globe, at some point meron din akong sky. Panic kasi pag biglang walang connection pag may klase. So yung mga ganon... uhhh... yung mga adjustments na</p>

	ginawa for the pandemic to be able to proceed to the online learning.
Researcher	Participant 1, I want to ask, a while ago you have mentioned, Google Drive, Zoom, tapos nag messenger din po kayo at viber, yung apat lang po ba yung talaga yung namaximize ninyo for the whole pandemic just for you to communicate to your students or nag branch out ka pa po?
Participant 1	No, I have Zoom, Google Classroom, hindi Google lang, Google Drive. On my second semester or third semester of the pandemic I was doing the Google Classroom until now, nakuha ko na yung rhythm and mas Madali kasing magsend ng email, announcements, everything automatic. Ang problema lang kasi sa Google Classroom kasi kung may mga students na walang UP email, hindi sila pwede. So meron akong mga graduate students that I have to encourage or force them to get a UP email to be able to have only one platform so that I can communicate with them, may mga ilan ilan. I am maintaining until now, since the beginning of the pandemic. I am more relying on emails. I do individual emails. Even the submission of their assignments. Even if I made provisions of uploading on the Google Drive, upload on the Google Classroom, I accept assignments that was sent to me via email and I acknowledge to them that I received your assignment. And rule ko pag wala akong acknowledgement that means hindi ko natanggap. So kailangan niyo akong sabihin or ipadala ninyo ulit. Kasi assignments ang basehan ng grado so dapat sigurado yun. In the end of the semesters, before grading, before I print out my grade, I have to make sure kung may kulang akong assignment ineemail ko pa sila ulit bago ko ilabas yung grade. 'Talaga bang wala ito? Kasi kung meron kayo at hindi ko nareceive ipadala niyo nab ago ko ilagay na incomplete kayo. So yung communication nay un mas aktibo kaysa nung pre-pandemic. Nung pre-pandemic, pakelam ko kung ano... bigay ko nalang sainyo lahat *laughs* di ba?
Researcher	I was about to ask nga Participant 1. If ganon po ba yung principle ninyo pre-pandemic, hinahabol niyo pa po ba talaga or no?
Participant 1	No... no... this one. Meron kasing condition di ba? Compassion and lahat, hindi mo alam ang pinagdadaan ng estudyante so we, the faculty, has to exhaust all means to be able to reach out para lang malaman hindi nakapagsubmit dahil hindi nagawa, hindi magawa or dahil wala akong access at system para isubmit so kailangan malaman ano yung rason kung bakit hindi mafulfill yung

	<p>requirements. It could happen that they got sick or it could happen that the family got sick so they have to take care so it has to be incorporated. Kaya first semester di ba no fail, walang fail. Kaya kung hindi nasubmit, incomplete agad yun. Then succeeding... ito yung ano... yung bawal na magbigay ng numeric grade. Mas lalo ngayon tibay ang communication dapat kasi baka complete naman pero mabigyan mo ng incomplete. Although incomplete naman is okay kasi pwede mo pa naman mabigyan ng completion grade. Ang masaklap, complete lahat ang requirements nabigyan mo ng failing grades magfapile pa ng change of grade yun. So yung... yun yung talaga change... it's more of more communication with their students with regards to their accomplishments and status which is different nung pre-pandemic. Nung pre-pandemic kasi merong understanding na responsibility mo ang progress mo. Kung hindi ka pumapasok, acceptin mo yung consequences ng hindi pag pasok. Pag hindi ka nagsusubmit ng requirements, alam mo yung consequences ng hindi pagsubmit ng requirements, tanggapin mo *laughs* kung ano yung outcome. Ngayon sa pandemic, may... may konting puso eh *laughs* na lalabas. Maraming puso ang lalabas.</p>
Researcher	<p>Okay po. Totoo yun, Participant 1. I resonate with that since teacher din po ako. Grabeng patience and understanding.</p>
Participant 1	<p>Hindi ko pa sinasabi yung patience during Zoom *laughs*</p>
Researcher	<p>Andaming adjustments po talaga. And speaking of patience, ano po yung masasabi ninyo platform, during the pandemic na nahirapan po kayong mag adjust. Yung ginamit po ninyo.</p>
Participant 1	<p>I think Google Classroom and UVLE. Hindi ko nan ga ginamit yung UVLE *laughs*. Although madali naman siyang aralin pero hindi kasi siya lahat ginagamit ng students. Ayoko yung platform na meron pang ibang hindi makakagamit. So meron pa akong hahanapin. Bale kunwari lang, ahhh... sa UVLE, may apat na hindi gumagamit ng UVLE, so Google Classroom silang apat. So sa sampu, may anim kang nasa UVLE, may apat kang nasa Google Classroom. Hati hati. SO kung alin ang lahat ay makakagamit, dun tayo. Para isa nalang ang gagawin ko. So kung sila okay na ang email, okay na yung shared Google Drive, ang Zoom, dun nalang kami wala na kaming Google Classroom.</p>
Researcher	<p>Ah okay po...</p>

Participant 1	*Hums in agreement*
Researcher	Ano naman po, para sa inyo, during the pandemic, yung most convenient way for you to reach out to your students? Google Classroom po ba?
Participant 1	Hindi, text. Cellphone. Kasi lahat sila sigurado nakakabit sila sa cellphone.
Researcher	Cellphone as in text po talaga ito hindi internet?
Participant 1	Hindi internet kasi may mga estudyante na walang internet. SO hindi uubra ang email, pag nagsend ako ng email eh sasabihin down ang internet, pano nila mababasa yun? So pinapacheck ko at the beginning of the semester, kasi sa class list namin sa CRS, nandun pati cellphone. So tinetext ko yun lahat. Na dapat working. Kasi, especially saaking graduate students, na nasa kung saan saan, meron sa batanes, may isa akong nasa Mindanao, may isa akong nasa dubai. May isang nasa Toronto *laughs*, yung mga ganon... yung mga ganong klase may internet sila, pero kung naputulan, yung sa batanes hindi nan ga pumapasok yun. Hindi ko na alam kung anong nangyari sakanya, hindi na sumagot sakin sa text at lahat, hindi ko alam kung nagkasakit ba siya or whatever, nag disappear nalang. So pinapahanap ko sa school pero walang feedback so baka hindi na rin nagtuloy. Final validation and verification sakin ang text, cellphone. Kasi pag sumagot sakin doon, 'oh ma'am wala po kaming ilaw.' 'oh ma'am wala po kaming internet.' 'ma'am wala po kaming... may sakit po ako.', 'ma'am inaalagaan ko po magulang ko.' Dun lalabas eh na... yung hindi uubra yung internet. May mangilan-ngilan, hindi ko sure... sa facebook messenger sa graduate. Sa undergrad, hindi ko sure, wala ata akong... minessage sa facebook
Researcher	Pero Participant 1 looking at it, if most convenient sainyo si cellphone. Parang extra effort po talaga sainyo pero you chose to do so that you can communicate with your students
Participant 1	Oo kesa... mas ano ako na... I know something. Basta lang alam ko kung bakit ka nagdisappear. Bakit hindi ka nakikicommmunicate. Bakit hindi ka nagsusubmit or bakit hindi ganon. Every Zoom meeting ineemphasize ko yun sa mga estudyante na okay lang magsabi kayo na hindi kayo makapagtrabaho lahat basta alam ko na hindi namin magawa, hindi namin mameet yung deadline, hindi lahat yun, I need to know, I need to know your progress every

	<p>week. If we are doing the Zoom yun yung round robin, yung lahat ng present 'oh nasan ka na?' each one. Tapos yung mga wala, pinaparelay na sabihin nila ako. Yun yung means of communication eh. Minsan nga, kasi ikaw as faculty naman na anxious eh 'may sakín na ata ito or baka nahospital na' whatever. Kasi at that point, yun mga support sa mga estudyante dapat maaccess at mailabas. Ibang iba na ngayon. Although blended kami na rin. Nakikita ko na yung mga estudyante sa building, nakakapunta na kayo. So ibang monitoring nalang pero nakasanayan na... na ganon... na minomonitor ko yung status.</p>
Researcher	<p>Okay po. Participant 1 I want to ask naman po. Ano naman po yung satingin ninyong greatest triumph ninyo in the course of online communication during the pandemic.</p>
Participant 1	<p>Maaral ang Zoom *laughs* de joke lang!</p>
Researcher	<p>Possible din po yun!</p>
Participant 1	<p>Madagdagan ang kaalaman ko sa platform. I don't know Google Classroom, I don't know Zoom. Isa pa may resistance ako na... hindi na ata kaya ng braincells ko na aralin yung Canva, yung mga pang presentation na platform, application, or softwares. So triumph for me is if I'm able to use it. It's a big uhhh... disappointment or resistance, kasi pag nabuild yung resistance ko na ayoko na aralin yan, yun ang mahirap pang aralin, andami ko pang iinstall, kung ano ano. Yun, yun ang aking mga hate...</p>
Researcher	<p>How about Participant 1 when it comes to building relationships with your students, ano po yung greatest triumph ninyo or achievement ninyo during fully online.</p>
Participant 1	<p>Nung fully online, siguro yung to go beyond the classroom. Kasi students will reach out if they... if meron silang raket for additional income. Yung mga ganon. Na dati, binibitbit nila yun sa school, yung mga pastries, cookies. But they cannot do that. So some reach out by email that 'I'm accepting pre-order ma'am' *laughs* ganon ganon. May ganon pang at least means to assist them. Alam ko naman kasing may mga estudyante na kailangan ng... ng suporta financially. So yun... yun yung makatulong kung... kung kayang tumulong, tumutulong kasi I really respect... ano nga to... yung no student left behind so kung may nag reach out na nangangailangan as much as possible... kahit nga yung, pre-pandemic, sabi nga sayom medyo strict and</p>

	<p>hindi ganon ang personalidad ko, pandemic time, kahit anong time ang request ng consultation... after 5, after 6, mamaya may thesis consultation ako alas seis, although ang requirement ko lang, pwede na ang face-to-face right now, consultation, as well as classes, hindi pa ako mag feface-to-face kasi macocompromise. Kakacovid ko lang, kaka check out ko lang sa hospital nung 20. Nung nag reach out k, kaka ano ko lang nun... okay lang. So yun hindi na ako nagbigay ng time... limit kasi yung ibang faculty alam ko, no communication after 5, no communication during weekends, yung mga ganon... hindi ko nakasanayan kasi, kahit noon pa, yun nga rin ang sinasabi ko as dean ako or as administrador, pagpasensyahan niyo ako kung ang communication ko ay madaling araw o kaya, sabado linggo, kasi yun yung mga panahon na makakasend ako, Kasi minsan napupuna ng faculty and bagong staff na, 'ma'am alas do niyo pinadala', 'ma'am alas tres?', pagpasensyahan niyo na, basta nareceive niyo, at walang oras ang working time ko.</p>
Researcher	Parang mas naging open ka Participant 1 after ano... or during the pandemic.
Participant 1	During the pandemic, yes.
Researcher	Naging open ka na po?
Participant 1	Hindi open in a sense that I open my life to you, but in terms of availability. It's more of availability that as much as possible, if I can, I will be available. Although syempre, meron din akong pangangailangan so hindi ko basta... so kaya nga always, pag nagpapaschedule, or may nagpapaconsult, give me your available time and I will match it with mine. Kasi minsan, sinabi na 'kelan kayo ma'am pwede?'. Naiilang kasi ako pag ngabibigay ako ng available time, tapos biglang 'ma'am pwede po sa iba.' Eh kung hindi naman pala ano, edi ikaw nalang magbigay una ng availability at sasabihin ko sayo if pwede ako or hindi.
Researcher	Looking back, Participant 1, pre-pandemic at pandemic, ano yung type ng transition na nangyari is communication easier, harder, ano po para sainyo?
Participant 1	Sakin the means of communication, expanded. Expanded kasi before it's personal, face-to-face, personal meeting. Yun lang ang minsang mangyayari in terms of faculty and students. Right now I think many faculty and students have... have... opened up... or disregarded their limits in terms of communication. So... so on the means of

	<p>communication, it expanded. The... the... ano 'to... how do you... the quality of communication, yun yung... hindi ko pa masabi. Kung positive or negative kasi depende sa kinakatawan sa edad, sa age. Although there are some young people, or young students that will be mature enough, but in terms of quality of communication, may mangilanngilan kasi na parang Nawala yung concept ng pakikinig. The listening portion, either, short span, or dahil... I'm not sure if it's a means of Zoom di ba, minsan kasi multi-tasking. So yung multi-tasking naform na hindi nakakafocus. Kung minsan hindi mo alam kung ikaw ba kausap or nakikinig ba sayo or hindi. Which is different nung pre-pandemic kasi nakikita mo yung face and lahat. Yun yung sinasabi ko lang na during lectures, during discussion meetings na malaking bagay kasi kung face-to-face kasi nakikita ko yung mukha, alam ko kung may sinabi ako, uy nakakunot, hindi naiintindihan. Hindi ko yun mapick up sa Zoom. Hindiko mapick up yun. So yun yung malaking bagay sa communication na Nawala.</p>
<p>Researcher</p>	<p>Parang yung pagiging expanded ng communication, na assure siya pero yung effectivity ng message that you're trying to give yun yung parang...</p>
<p>Participant 1</p>	<p>And understand that... understand the return message. You only have to rely on the sound and sometimes you can open the video, but still it is not enough to be able to see, sakin malaking bagay sa lecture yung body language, na makikita mo na uy, nababagot na sila, uy wala na dito sa classroom ang kanilang isip kasi nakatingin nalang sayo, so yung mga ganong klase, hindi mo yun mapipick up sa Zoom. Kaya sakin honestly, sa pandemic, tinanggal ko yung concept ng attendance, hindi ako naniniwala na... hindi mor in naman pwedeng irequire na umattend lahat. May naririnig ako sa faculty na nagcocount na attendance in terms of points, never akong nag ganon, tapos magrequest yung estudyante na ma'am pag everytime ba nandito ako sa Zoom may plus points, privileged kayo kasi nandito kayo. So malaking plus points niyo na yun. Hindi niyo na kailangan ng plus points sa klase. So yung mga ganong klase ng presence, iba sa face to face kasi may effort na pumunta sa classroom *laughs* at lahat. So yun din yung malaking bagay. Yung interaction din kasi ng student to student, nawawala pag sa Zoom, minimal na ang student to faculty. Tapos yung informal communication like joke or bantering, yung mga ganon, nawawala na rin yun eh. Kasi sa words, hindi naman ganon kaeffective yun mga pakikipaglokohan, lokohan na 'uy ma'am maaga kayo ngayon.' Wala ng ganon ngayon. Yun yung mga communication na nag iba</p>

Researcher	<p>Okay po. You have mentioned po kanina, that you became more considerate due to the pandemic, nagexpand nga po yung communication channels and platforms ninyo and all the other things that you have adjusted just so that you can build a relationship with your students, But I want to ask po, now that you are applying blended learning, itong mga ideas, concepts and practices po bang ito, are you still retaining it po, or yung iba tinanggal niyo na totally sa system kasi nagbabalik na sa face-to-face, ano po yung status natin when it comes to that?</p>
Participant 1	<p>Sakin, the same pa rin kasi may resistance pa ako when it comes to face-to-face. Even if it is required 50% for the undergrad, 50% face-to-face. Sa graduate courses ko naman, purely online eh allowed kami eh. And this is preferred by the graduate students, kasi our graduate students are scattered all over the Philippines. So dehado talaga. So far, right now, ay ang more inclined to go blended go all the way. Isang semester nalang siguro ako, next semester. I would foresee that I would still require purely online on a case to case basis and face-to-face. I would be open but it will not be regular like before na twice a week, thrice a week. At this point in time, hindi ko pa... wala pa akong masyadong confidence na hindi ako magkakacovid ulit. And it is the same with many of our students that, ngayon kasi di ba nag increase ulit ang cases, we received requests from our students, requesting online, because they have been exposed and they have the symptoms... yun lang yun, Kaya nga sinasabi namin sa kolehiyo na I don't think we will be entertaining going back to purely face-to-face, that's not an option anymore. It's more of an option of purely online or blended. So yun yung positive na nabigyan ng another option for delivery. Na kaya naman eh, infrastructure support lang dapat and kung bumalik ka ng face-to-face, I don't think that UP can compete with other universities anymore kasi maleft behind tayo. Kasi karamihan ng university nagbukas na ng purely online na course eh. At tsaka, college at graduate naman eh. Dun siguro sa secondary at basic ed, yun, iface-to-face mo pa yun. Kailangan pa nila yung formation doon. At itong mga to may sarili na tong personalidad at lahat lahat at tsaka karamihan pa nung nasa college level, may trabaho na rin eh. So they prefer to have an online, or the blended. Because of the hard times, they have to go to part time work, part time studies.</p>
Researcher	<p>Participant 1, The decision of... being... of being pro of fully online type of lectures and meetings, aside from the fact that you want to take care of your health, kasama po ba doon yun aspect that you are now confident when it comes</p>

	to online communication
Participant 1	<p>Yeah, kasama na rin yun, kasi at least alam ko na mag share screen, alam ko na magrecord, minsan lang nalilimutan ko magrecord pero given na yun sa estudyante ko na iremind niyo ako umpisa palang kasi nalilimutan ko, hindi yun common sakín na record, hindi ko naman sineset up yung akin Zoom na automatic magrerecord kasi kailangan mo pang ioff if hindi naman kailangan irecord yung pinaguusapan. Tapos, yes, I can say that I am confident, I am able to create my google classroom, I communicate na with the Google Classroom. My class this semester, I have three Google Classrooms, I have my Zoom, so yes, I am more confident now. So siguro nga sabi ko nga may resistance ako, so hindi ko talaga gusting aralin yung Canva, ayoko ng gumawa ng kung paano gumawa ng kung ano anong animation. Kung ano ano sa video presentatio... ang ginagawa ko ngayon na para sa mga ganyan na... natutuwa ako na... kasama siguro sa outcome of the online blended learning, it's giving the students the freedom in terms of format of presenting their assignments. Bilib ako... dun talaga ako bow sa mga bata kahit sa mga graduate students. They are able to submit not a Participant 2ument or an essay format, but they can merge now. In terms of graphics, video, submission whatever dun naeexcite ako at magandang... outcome kasi namamaster na nila. Namamaster na nila yung paggamit. Tapos... uhhh... makikita mo na na nabobore na sila pag essay yung mga Participant 2ument paper write up. Pag sinabi mo uhhh you can use any creative format everything so may nagvovlog, nagvivideo at kung ano anong sinusubmit so sabi ko, it builds their creativity. And it is also interesting for me to uhhh... see creative outputs na hindi ko nakita pre-pandemic. Kasi yung pre-pandemic sigurong creative is yung diorama, yung mga patchi patching mga libro. Butthis time really, I am amazed sometimes with what they are submitting of uhhh... of mixing the platforms together so sabi ko marami akong hindi alam pero sabi ko madami din silang alam.</p>
Researcher	Participant 1 speaking of your students, do they sometimes message you to show appreciation pag nag text ka po or nagereply ka po sa email, do they say thank you or wow si ma'am open in terms of communicating with us.
Participant 1	Yes. Yes. Yan yung... ano 'to... yan yung uhhh... yung rule... ay hindi naman parang rule. I try to start at the beginning when they offer to create group chats... group chats na kasali ako. Kaya sabi ko siguraduhin niyo na gusto ninyong kasali ako kasi makikita ko lahat ng exchanges

	<p>ninyo so isinasali nila at lahat at dun pagnagcocomment sila ng about their assignments about their... about the people that they met during doing their outputs etchetera at sumisingit ako, uy nandito si ma'am. Thank you ma'am. Yes yung mga ganon, yes they recognize it and I receive also email of noted, thank you, much appreciated, yung mga ganong klase and I put it... hindi yan norm... hindi yan normal sa panglahat ng estudyante. Tanggap ko naman na may mga personalidad na hindi ganon kaexpressive kasi ganon din naman ako may mga panahon na... hindi ako demonstrative, hindi ako nagbibigay ng kung ano man. Alam ko naman ang personalidad ko, matagal ako or mabagal ako magbigay ng recognition or appreciation, yung well done well done. Parang ang nasa ulo ko kasi, if you know what you have done and it's good, you don't need that *laughs*. But I know, some people need that. So yun yung dilemma always so sige para lang nasa safe side, okay, excellent work, good job, yung mga ganong klase, I give that during reporting as well as their submission especially lumalabas saakin yung talagang napamangha ako sa assignment good, more than excellent. At yung iba sinsabihan ko rin naman na yung mga nagawa nila sa assignment, meron akong goal kasi nga nearing retirement so I'm trying to build their assignments as learning resource. So sa graduate students... gawa sila ng learning video ng destination saamin, nagagamit ko na rin siya sa mga susunod na semester at naseshare ko rin yung ginawa nila sa ibang other stakeholders and other clients who would like to see a case study kasi nagawa na nila. So yun yung sinasabi ko na... nandun naman yung pangalan nila hindi ko inaalas, hindi ko nilalagay ang pangalan ko so it's all their credit. It's not an output of an article or a paper published but it's a creative work that they have done ang hindi ko lang mashare and sabi ko bigyan niyo lang ako ng permiso, some vlogs or personal accounts of their life or experiences kasi sabi ko nga maraming privacy matters yoon kaya hindi ko shinesshare but if it's a destination level, yun shinesshare ko. So yun yung mga good outcomes of this pandemic.</p>
<p>Researcher</p>	<p>Okay po. Last two questions nalang po Participant 1. What are the aspects of your online communication practice that you wish to improve. Ano pa po yung gusto niyo pong...</p>
<p>Participant 1</p>	<p>Siguro... it would be... yung... yung exchanges sa chat discussion, yung discussion boards at lahat ng yun. Hindi ako masyadong maganon eh. Yung maglalagay ng question yung estudyante, parang live discussion sa classroom, yun parang very minimal ang ano ko, hindi ko... masyadong... maano, yung mabigyan ng panahon sila ng</p>

	teaser questions tapos lahat kayo sagot sagot. Yun hindi ko masyadong namaximize yung discussion forum or discussion platform yoon. So yun yung gusto kong aralin. At kasi, alam ko sa ibang faculty meron silang points sa ganon na ilang questions ang masagot mo, ayun yung gusto kong idagdag in terms of succeeding delivery of my classes.
Researcher	How about in terms of building communication, or building relationship with your students through online communication.
Participant 1	Sa undergrad siguro. Sa undergrad kasi I'm more passive. Yung kung sino lang yung mageemail saakin na nangangailangan, yun lang yung nakakacomunicate ko. Kung hindi sila... wala pa akong aggressive initiative in terms of each one oh kamusta ka na *laughs* kasi nirereserve ko yun pag Zoom. And there are some... I've noticed right now, na may mga consistently hindi makaattend sa Zoom and may mga delay na in terms of submission of assignments and I think I have to give more time to communicate with them. Sa graduate students, wala akong masabi kasi masyadong aktibo yung mga yun. Sila yung nagiinitiate. Kahit nung nagkasakit nga ako, nag assume ako, sinabihan ko yung school na may sakit ako na sila yung magaanounce sa klase ko, sa awa ng Diyos walang ng announce *laughs* sa klase ko kaya lahat sila nageemail saakin na yung mga graduate students, na ma'am nandito kami bakit kayo, so yung mga ganon... so communication wise, they are adults. Graduate students are more adult so they don't feel intimidated to communicate with me kahit may ganong age, but the undergrad I know may intimidation, age gap siguro kasi ang tingin na nila saakin ay lola na nila *laughs* oo lola na talaga nila kaya nahihiya na sila magsabi.
Researcher	Last question na po, how do you think UP can help you in terms of your online communication practices.
Participant 1	Hindi ko masabi na trainings kasi may trainings naman at lahat but it is... uhhh... hindi ko talaga sure kung paano ko sasagutin yan... hindi ko naman ineexpect na magbibigay ng incentives kasi wala naman yan. So... eh may mga awards naman na binibigay kung meron kang kakaibang nagagawa at lahat na yun. So meron... nandun naman yung support at lahat siguro lang is in terms of uhhh... kasi nandoon na rin kasi yung provision of license software... ay siguro saakin if they can include the learning of platforms as part of the load *laughs* the load kasi... kasi kakain sa oras yun *laughs* kasi yung teaching load mo 12 units di ba

	<p>and some may admin load, research load at lahat. Siguro yung learning load for additional platforms. Kasi sinisingit yun lahat sa announcements although voluntary, who would like to... there is an orientation for a specific platform so kung sinong gustong umattend, aattend. But I don't think that is enough na kunwari may orientation ka sa Canva sasabihin sayo, kaya naman i self study, pwede siguro dedicated class na mahasa lahat ng features ng lahat platforms na ibibigay from beginners to mid to advance. Yung mga ganong support, continuing ha kasi may mga platforms or softwares kasi na may additional features na meron palang ganito na hindi namin alam, kaya pala ito na hindi namin alam. Kasi namin nadidiskubre. So yung mga ganon siguro. Updating... updating of knowledge for softwares.</p>
Researcher	<p>Last question na po talaga. Ano po yung final thoughts ninyo as a near retirement educator na fully adapting na po talaga sa online communication?</p>
Participant 1	<p>What do you mean?</p>
Researcher	<p>Siguro po ano po yung best memory... ano po yung...</p>
Participant 1	<p>Siguro in terms of best memory or best outcome, siguro its being able to participate in an online delivery in the period of my service. Kasi noon ko pa yan naririnig, more than a decade ago. Naririnig ko na yan mga colleagues from abroad na meron silang online delivery and may mga mangilannngilan akong imbetasyon before but it's more of sending... hindi fully immerse in an online delivery. Wala pang Zoom and wala pa itong konsepto netong lahat. But I haven't been given a chance for that... for this to happen. But right now, it happened, it opened more options and avenues for me. Honestly, it opened. Even after retirement I can do online... online courses for universities abroad.</p>
Researcher	<p>Sasabihin ko palang po sana if is this a good way, since you're nearing your retirement na po, good way po ba siya to conclude your career for now kasi of course namention niyo na rin naman po na...</p>
Participant 1	<p>One aspect. One aspect of my potential career path, kasi hindi lang kasi teaching lang naman there are still... eventual kasi after retirement kasi maraming potential... maraming potential na tutunguhin pero at least right now nalagyan ng isa pa... na online course kahit anong level, graduate, undergrad... undergraduate, graduate, to PhD lahat yun. And there are many, ang maganda ngayon, there</p>

	<p>are many universities ngayon na may online courses Before wala, so sino naman ang magoffer sayo na magtuturo eh wala namang course naganon. Eh dito sa Pilipinas madami na so you don't need to go outside Metro Manila to be able to reach some universities sa provinces. So malaking bagay yung after retirement kasi may isang potential option na pwedeng pagtunguhan na I can still continue teaching without even risking going out face to face. Yun yung isa sa malaking bagay na natutunan, natutunan at least bago ka mag retire, natutunan mo mag Zoom.</p>
<p>Researcher</p>	<p>Okay po, thank you so much for your time!</p>
<p>Participant 1</p>	<p>Good luck! Good Luck!</p>

APPENDIX D: Transcription of Interview with Participant 2

Speaker	Statement
Researcher	Participant 2 let me introduce myself. I am Krizelle R. Amoyo, I am conducting a study po regarding analyzing the obligatory online communication of near-retirement educators during the pandemic. That's why I have invited you po because I know that your insights will greatly help me with regards to analyzing how we can improve in assisting our teachers when it comes to online communication. So thank you so much Participant 2 for saying yes. I'll be asking you a few questions po but please allow me also to inject or uhm... throw follow up questions depending on your answers. So we can start na po. Participant 2 can I ask you to please introduce yourself, of your complete name, your birthday, and how long have you been teaching?
Participant 2	Uhuh. I'm Participant 2 uhm...how long I've been teaching... I've been in the academe for 40 years, 25 years for teaching in college, 4 years in Senior High School in the US. What's the other question? Senior moment...
Researcher	When's your birthday?
Participant 2	My birthday is July 3, 1962
Researcher	Next question po Participant 2 uhm... in the course of your career, what is your perception of the importance of online communication?
Participant 2	Personally, since as you've said, we belong to that age wherein uhm... it was only just recently when, I think it was uhm... 1990's online communication is basically just through email and just through messenger that we just experienced uhm... using in the academe the venue of... this... this... medium. I find it so important especially when I had an experience working in the US that... that... we uhm... used online communication, it has become easier no? Unlike before that uh... we call this slow mail, we have to wait for months or days to be able to send across your message but with online communication it is an instant that you get to send your message across and get a response outright.
Researcher	Okay po Participant 2. Now, I want to understand po what is your pre-pandemic practice when it comes to

	communicating with your students. Since part po siya ng life po natin as an educator, kung paano po natin mabubuild yung relationship natin with our students. Part of it is our communication practice with them. Now, pre-pandemic po, ano po yung usual routine ninyo or yung habits ninyo when it comes to communicating with your students.
Participant 2	First and foremost, I would like this to be formally Participant 2umented. In our ... previously in the school that I'm handling, we sent email and less formal would be the messenger or google class. But when I came to FEU Alabang, of course we make use of canvas as a medium for sending across the message for our students
Researcher	So eversince po pala talaga Participant 2, nag online communication na kayo
Participant 2	Yes... yes. Uh... I find it so essential especially with... we can consider email as one... as a
Researcher	Yes
Participant 2	I really find it ... what do you call this... I find it essential in a sense that I make sure that I send email to formally Participant 2ument communication... with... with those individuals that I need to communicate with.
Researcher	So pre-pandemic Participant 2, If we are going to put it in percentage, how much po yung for face-to-face communication with your students as compared to online communication. 70:30 po ba? 60:40?
Participant 2	Palagay ko... let's put... let's put... what do you call this... let's put it in time frame, is that okay with you, alam mo naman 40 years in the academe...
Researcher	Yes go po Participant 2
Participant 2	I think when I was... nine... ay not 90's... like in the early 20's, 20s... I ... mga 50:50, mataas na yun, kasi I really value sending email and communications, in my previous schools. And then when I came to... yung most recent... sabihin mo ng 7 years, 70:30.
Researcher	So 70:30. From 50:50 Participant 2 nagging 70:30 po. 70 po yung online tapos 30 nalang po si face-to-face.
Participant 2	Yes yes
Researcher	Leaning towards online communication po pala talaga kayo

	Participant 2. Now, jumping to pandemic situation na po Participant 2 where it is basically obligatory for us to adjust to online communication, based on what you have answered a while ago, I don't think it was difficult for you but can you share to us ano po yung notable experiences or stories when it comes to online communication with your students.
Participant 2	One for me, I find it really... puro positive yung experience ko. One is, definitely during the pandemic, it is impossible for us to communicate with them face-to-face so we have the side ways, I have personally the side ways, to students and parents, as I've said, number 1 is the email, the formality of the email, I value it so much no. And at the same time, even if I go back, looking for something, Participant 2uments, important communication, I can really use my past emails para maki... para makuha ko siya. Talagang I value it so much, it allow me to send, allow me to solve some problems that occur during the time that I know it is difficult for us to find Participant 2uments. Even printed Participant 2uments ha. Because during the time that we... we were... we were really forced to even those ... forms or attached pictures, attach it to the emails or even what I've said, messengers, and group chats, I was able to do that. So very positive yun saakin. At the same time, of course one of the negatives what if... one of the other end of the line is really not answering you back. At least through this online communication we can... we try to reach them, it's for free. For free in a sense na uhhh... we can anytime, as I've said, at a very short period of time we can send them across the message and get back the answers. And pinakamahalaga talaga saakin na anexperience ko ay yung may mga Participant 2uments na hinahanap, kaya ko siyang balikan.
Researcher	How about po Participant 2, in terms of building relationships with your students. Parang ano po yung... yung notable experience ninyo when it comes to the closeness na naestablish due to constant online communication during the pandemic? Meron po bang ganon? Na nagoopen po sila sainyo?
Participant 2	Yes... yes... I don't know whether you will believe it or not but my relationship with my students as compared to the times na I would just... as an administrator or as a teacher na I will just be confined in the faculty room or in the office, very limited lang yung time, unless estudyante kita and we meet inside the classroom. Very limited lang yung time that I will be able to talk to you. But through the gc or some... messen... or other medium like what I've said email,

	parents, students would come to you personally and really seeking your help. It became very intimate. And of course it also has something to do with how you send your message. Let's say the words that you are going to use... actually mas ano pa nga eh... mas ma... minsan mas nagiging maayos kasi di ba, you read before you click.
Researcher	Yes
Participant 2	You will have the time to go over your message bago mo siya ipadala no? So I find it... strangely, I find it more personal, more intimate, at the same time mas yung relationship with the parents and the students, I would say closer. Especially of course, if the messages that you're sending to them is 'we would like to help you/we would like to assist you', yung mga ganon.
Researcher	So kumbaga po na strengthen yung relationship instead of fully depending on face-to-face communication.
Participant 2	Exactly... exactly...
Researcher	A while ago you have mentioned that you are using email, you're using messenger, you're using canvas in FEU Alabang, are those the three platforms po talaga that you've been maximizing when it comes to online communication or nag branch out pa po kayo?
Participant 2	Yun na halos eh. Kasi yun na yung nakasanayan ko. And at the same time, at the same time, for me the advantage of using those two... is yung parang 'I don't want to find all urls'. If I can find... If I can communicate with them using those platforms okay na sakin yun.
Researcher	Okay po Participant 2. Alin po doon Participant 2 yung pinakamadalas nagamit ninyo during the pandemic? When it comes to communicating with them?
Participant 2	During the pandemic? Communicating with the students usually, email
Researcher	Ohh email
Participant 2	Email tapos second po yung messenger.
Researcher	Now, I want to ask Participant 2. Ano naman po yung triumphs, best part of using email, using messenger or online communicating with your students.
Participant	Aside from what I mentioned awhile ago, that I was able to

2	<p>solve problems, I was able to look for Participant 2uments, looking backwards, looking backwards to previous Participant 2uments, finding Participant 2uments, finding communication, of course the milestones is the intimate and personal communication with them. Kasi as I was saying, with... as an administrator confined ka sa office mo rarely you will be able to talk to your students right pero anytime they can reach you. And I make it personal. To answer them personally especially if the problem or concern is ako yung taong makatulong sakanila or makasagot.</p>
Researcher	<p>What about struggles Participant 2?</p>
Participant 2	<p>Struggles, the connectivity pa rin. The connectivity from my end or from other's end. Also those... also those people that you're trying to reach out na they will not answer you back or they don't have the capacity to answer you back. Most probably the connectivity and the know how, on how to use the platform.</p>
Researcher	<p>Okay po Participant 2. A while ago you've mentioned, basically position po. As an administrator po, and at the same time of course the 40 years that you've been teaching, I want to ask, do you think po ba that age and position plays a huge role when it comes to online communication with a younger generation. What's your take on that po.</p>
Participant 2	<p>Let me... can you repeat the question again Ms Researcher. Titingnan ko lang if tama yung pagkakacapture ko.</p>
Researcher	<p>Okay po Participant 2. A while ago you've mentioned that you've been an administrator and of course the 40 years that you've been teaching or that you are a part of the academe. I want to ask po if it's a huge role or huge part when it comes to... does it play a huge role when it comes to online communication with your students? Meron... Factor po ba siya?</p>
Participant 2	<p>I think... factor ang age. Whether we like it or not, uh... age can be a factor. And what does with age is the attitude. Most probably, there are two people who would have... two... two point of views... as far as... people from my age as far as online communication is concerned. Number 1, 'I'm too old to learn' 'I no longer wanted to learn that and I'm done with it', parang ganon, hindi ko na siya kailangan. Kasi as an administrator, as per experience, yung mga... yung mga old generation na 'di ko na po kaya yun. Di ko na</p>

	<p>po yun magagawa' so eventually they have to make a choice, especially during the time of the pandemic. Either you adjust, you embrace this new norm in education. Or else you have to go. Yun naman mga iba, of course the other side of the coin is that, they are still willing, despite of age, and at the same time, they know age is not just a number and they have a specific role to play and importance in the academe. So dalawa yun eh, saan ako. Most probably... yung latter. Because not that I'm that willing to learn, medyo nababawasan pa nga ako. Siguro nasa middle ako. May mga areas na siguro hindi ko na siya kailangan. I'm trying to make sure na yun naman sa mga satingin ko na kailangan ko pa, inaaral ko yun. If I won't be able to master it at least I will be able to maximize what I know and with what I know I will be able to maximize its use so that I will be able to send across my message. Send across my message. Yun po yun.</p>
Researcher	<p>Okay po Participant 2. How about Participant 2 position. Syempre yung mga students natin, sometimes ilang sila kausapin the more na mas mataas yung position ng mga teachers nila or the administrators. What's your take on that? Does it have a huge impact when it comes to online communication?</p>
Participant 2	<p>Uh... culture... based on culture ha, culture kasi alam mo naman. Based on my experience when it comes to my students, talagang they have this mentality na pag ikaw yun, ikaw yung nasa position, matatakot silang lumapit sayo. Definitely it has, it has an effect or bearing pag dating doon. Pero, like to me personally, uhhh... most probably it's because of my work ethics... I'm not... I am in that particular position pero I know my role uhhh... and I am redefining it in such a way na, let's say that I am the principal with the faculty, I'm the middle manager, with the students, I am still wearing that... I am still a teacher meron lang akong position and I happen to be the head or the principal. But I'm still a teacher and one of the roles of the teacher is loco parentis so yung tanong mo na meron bang bearing yung position, yes it does sa kung paano yun, it has something to do with the work ethics or the value of the one who is in the position.</p>
Researcher	<p>Okay po Participant 2. Last few questions Participant 2! What did the obligatory online communication teach you when it comes to establishing communication or connection with your students? Ano po yung natutunan ninyo?</p>
Participant 2	<p>Nangyari yan, during the pandemic right?</p>

Researcher	Right
Participant 2	Oo, ako ano... I find it... Uhhh... ano ba... positive yung effect sakin eh... yung obligatory in a sense na you have no choice. You have to embrace it. You have to find ways for the academe or the learning to continue. So kung ano yung available way for us, administrators and teachers, to continue our role, we have to learn, we have to... we have to embrace and we have to adjust. Kasi if you would not be able to adjust, as I've said, my advice is if you will not be able to embrace this change, then you might as well go. Kasi there's still the continuity of learning eh. Ibang modality nalang ngayon. And yung sinabi mong mandatory and obligatory during the pandemic, iembracing mo talaga yun if you want to remain. That's why madami ng umalis eh. Many left... many left.
Researcher	Participant 2 ano naman po yung qualities or factors na ireretain ninyo from your experience of fully online communication now that nagbeblended learning na kayo. And kung meron po ba kayong ireretire na, tatanggalin na, remove or retire in terms of practices.
Participant 2	I think I will embrace... for that... for... for online communication to remain. Kumbaga, if you notice, I'm still using that to communicate with my teachers, easier and faster, to communicate with our students, no? It remains kasi nakita ko yung value niya during the pandemic eh. It will become an additional add on. Despite of the fact that there is face-to-face, andoon yung magreremind ka sakanila using... using those platforms and it reinforces eh, it reinforces eh at tsaka nandoon yung... dinoParticipant 2ument niya no yung instructions it became formalized, yung mga posting natin sa Canvas, yung mga pinapadala natin communication sa group chat, yung mga ineemail natin sakanila, despite of the fact that... uhhh... balik tayo sa face to face, rarely do we use printed materials to inform them of ano... of... of certain activities so on and so forth. I think it has made our lives easier and at the same time... this is the norm we have to accept it. New norm, we have to accept.
Researcher	So Participant 2 if major na positive po yung experience ninyo, wala naman po kayong parang ireretire na parang tatanggalin na practice because for you online communication is technically mostly positive, sainyo po...
Participant 2	Ako talaga, I really enjoyed it so much *laughs*, I have devise ways like checking attendance, monitoring outputs, through online communication and I'm... I'm... I really

	embraced it so much and I love it so much.
Researcher	Okay po Participant 2, last few questions po Participant 2. Since you have mentioned that it is mainly positive, I want to know kung meron pa po kayong naforesee na gusto ninyong maimprove when it comes to your online communication with your students, meron pa po ba?
Participant 2	Most probably, one of the things is to... educate our students the value of online communication. Kasi para bang walang existing... meron guidelines, the proper way. Alam mo yun, it would be a part of the curriculum on how we are to teach our students online communication. Kasi meron tayong oral comm, sabi ko nga sa mga computer classes dapat siyang ituro na even the ethics of online communication and all. I think dapat na kasama na siya sa curriculum.
Researcher	Okay po, how about po on the end of the faculty, of the teachers, ano pa po ang pwede pang maimprove.
Participant 2	The same way that... we are... most of the faculty, members of the faculty right now, except from those who are newly graduate and are teaching, we came from the old school and they don't know the value of online communication. Na marami pa rin akong nakikita sa members of the faculty, would rarely go over the communication that being sent to them sa email, every now and then magremagsasabi pa ako na please check you emails, kasi ano nga siya eh... part of life. Kasi saakin it is a way of life na kung masasanay ka lang... na... na... to check... eh bakit... eh di ba cellphone nga naman lagi mo namang hawak, kung masasanay sila and at the same time they will be educated on the proper use no of this online communication, it will be... kung dapat turuan yung mga bata on the ethics, dapat ding maturuan ang school... ang teachers ng ganon.
Researcher	Okay po Participant 2, my last question po Participant 2. Like what you have mentioned po na parang equal footing na need pa ng orientation both students and also the faculty when it comes to proper use of online communication, do you think that the institution that you are currently working for can devise a program for that para po matulungan sila. Do you think that they can be of help for this type of program or embedded nalang po sa curriculum
Participant 2	Most probably for example sa faculty members, isa siguro yun sa orientation, if not institutionally, let's say for example, in our department no in our program in senior

	high school we have to orient them that this is norm... our normal way of communicating na. Gone are the days, na ipapatawag ka sa opisina and we will discuss this with you, we will send you emails and communication, very informally the group chat. And hopefully makita nila yung value kasi like what I have said, not everyone has embraced it yet. Mhhh
Researcher	Okay, I think that's it Participant 2! Thank you so much for your time.

APPENDIX E: Transcription of Interview with Participant 3

Speaker	Statement
Researcher	<p>Okay po. So good afternoon, Participant 3. Let me introduce myself po before we start. I am Researcher Amoyo po and I am currently taking my Master of Development Communication in University of the Philippines Open University and I'm currently gathering my data for thesis which is entitled No teachers left online: a hermeneutic study of online communication for near-retirement educators at universities in NCR. I am passionate about this specific topic I am working as the online class coordinator at FEU Alabang. That is why I'm looking for ways that we can improve our assistance to our seasoned faculty because we value your contribution to the academe and of course we want to make sure aside from just implementing your lectures, we want to make sure that you are able to establish relationships with your students may it be in online or offline platform. So I have sent you also the list of questions that I will be asking you this afternoon. Please also allow me Participant 3 to inject few questions in between depending on your answers.</p>
Participant 3	Okay
Researcher	Can we start po?
Participant 3	Sure go ahead.
Researcher	<p>Okay po. Thank you so much Participant 3. First and foremost po, can I ask you po to introduce yourself. What is your complete name, what's your full name, when's your birthday, and how long have you been teaching?</p>

Participant 3	Yeah. I am Participant 3. I was born on May 15, 1957. I am 66 years old now. And I work in different universities as a faculty member and administrator for almost 40 years.
Researcher	Participant 3, I want to ask, you are 66 already but what made you stay in the academe for that long?
Participant 3	Well actually it started when I was a youth coordinator in our parish. St. Joseph Parish of Las Pinas. I was... I was appointed as the youth coordinator. So every week I will conduct a seminar or a mini lecture to our youth... in Las Pinas and at one point the parish priest told me that I am gifted at teaching. And so when I left the youth ministry of the parish, I thought of teaching in the university as the continuation of my ministry to the young. So I really love teaching.
Researcher	Ah okay po. So eversince po talaga Participant 3, nandun na po talaga yung inclination po ninyo when it comes to dealing with the younger generation, the students.
Participant 3	Yes
Researcher	From the ministry to the academe.
Participant 3	Yes. Yes.
Researcher	Okay po. Now I want to understand po, what's your communication practice pre-pandemic. Because, of course, pre-pandemic, online communication is just optional. So I want to ask po, kung ano treatment ninyo when it comes to communicating with your students during or before the pandemic is it fully face-to-face, or nag mamaximize na po ba kayo ng online communication. What's your routine, habit, or practice when it comes to communicating with them to build relationship.

Participant 3	Yeah before the pandemic its used to be face-to-face because I report to work five days a week, 8 hours a day, and I always make it a point and I always remind my secretary that... students need not... uhm... uhhh... appointment with me to be able to discuss certain matters... certain concerns... uhm... students come to my office and I talk to them so... usually yeah, it is face-to-face, because I am not into social media... I don't have a Facebook, or chat group, right. I have a viber group but that's only limited to friends and fellow professionals
Researcher	Ah okay po. So pre-pandemic po talaga fully face-to-face po talaga ang communication niyo po with your students.
Participant 3	Yeah, once in a while, some students would send me an email pero that's very rare.
Researcher	Ah okay, so rarely lang po talaga. So Participant 3, with that specific practice pre-pandemic, do you think that it is effective in terms of building your relationship with them? Effective naman po ba?
Participant 3	Oh yes. Very very effective. I think some students... uhhh... from the other colleges or departments would envy the mechanical engineering students because they have direct access... to me. Sometimes I will go out of my office and meet them at the corridor if my workload is not that heavy on that particular day. Yeah
Researcher	Ah okay po. So the face-to-face communication, the interaction po talaga both verbal and non-verbal since body language is part of it is effective in terms of building connection with them. Okay po. Pero Participant 3, generally, ano po yung sa tingin ninyong importance ng communication as an educator.

Participant 3	Well, it's very important. First, if they have concerns, if they have problems, then they are addressed right away. Another thing is it creates an environment or atmosphere of openness, of trust, and even camaraderie, so I think in a way that contributed so to motivating them to study hard, right? And I would say making their stay in the school, in the college a memorable one, and a happy one and I think, through the feedback I received now email or some would even write on a piece of paper a thank you note.
Researcher	Ah okay po. Participant 3, awhile ago you've mentioned that you've been maximizing email with your students, pre-pandemic po, and you have viber but it's very kumbaga not open to everyone, strictly professional use, pero po nung pandemic, since pumasok po si pandemic. It's basically obligatory for everyone to uhm... shift to online communication. What's your reaction with that.
Participant 3	Well... being the senior director then of the college of engineering. It's not really a problem as a matter of fact. I am the one that is encouraging the faculty members to use every communication... every mode of communication possible... yeah to serve the students. But in my case, during that time, I was not really active in teaching anymore. I was just doing my administrative tasks and there was even a year that doing administrative tasks, I was freed of that responsibility already. So I was just staying at home. Yeah and the administration gave me a break for one year *coughs*
Researcher	Okay po. But Participant 3, I want to ask. Do you have any notable experiences when it comes to online communication with your students during the pandemic. Meron po bang tumatak.

Participant 3	Ah yes actually nung nagteteam teach ako... online... and it's difficult the first time I experienced that na you don't see your audience. You only see profile pictures and if you ask them to open their cameras, they have all the excuses... na sira yung camera nila etcetera and I think at one point, I reminded them that the following meeting, I want them to be ready with their cameras and I called them one by one and I asked them to recite and I would... I would say... give them kind words when they are able to answer and participate well and that particular year I think, I received very heart warming remarks in the evaluation as a dean and as a faculty. And they said those... uh... kind words, they won't forget and that it even made them even strive more, participate more in my class. Because I really... I really made it clear to them... I really... uh... convince them... that that was a difficult time and that we have to exert extra effort to be actively engaged in our class meetings and it worked.
Researcher	Ah it worked... during Zoom po yan Participant 3?
Participant 3	Yes *livier tone* Oo and if you remember we have a huge class then...
Researcher	Yes po...
Participant 3	100 students... right?
Researcher	Yan po ba yung... masterclass po yan ano? Tama po ba?
Participant 3	Yes. Yes. And... and... I... you know... I was so happy that particular term... uh... because I think the students saw the importance of the subject that I was handling and at the same time they were motivated to participate in class.

Researcher	Ah okay po so Participant 3 you've been maximizing po talaga Zoom during the pandemic, just for you to reach out to your students, communicate with them, and build relationship, and they appreciated it which is a good thing. But a while ago you have mentioned that... kumbaga, shinashower mo sila with affirmations and that is very effective for them. But I want to ask po, pre-pandemic, are you also doing the same thing? Or is it an adjustment po during the pandemic? Since it's a difficult time for your students.
Participant 3	Yeah. Even before the pandemic, I... really give this affirmation
Researcher	Hmmm... talagang tinuloy tuloy niyo lang po ba talaga?
Participant 3	Oo kaya lang ibang mode... mo... more challenging mode
Researcher	More challenging... what made it more challenging Participant 3
Participant 3	Eh kasi nga... hindi mo sila nakikita ng sabay sabay. Kasi kapag sinabi mong iopen yung camera sabay sabay sila, maglalag ka naman. Diba?
Researcher	Opo. Opo.
Participant 3	So parang dalawa lang or tatlo at a time no? Ang hirap sa isang teacher na hindi mo nakikita yung mga estudyante mo
Researcher	Why Participant 3? Why po?
Participant 3	Eh kasi di ba... my approach is always personal right?
Researcher	Opo
Participant 3	Kasi nakiki... When... when you see the students malalaman ng teacher na... talagang intently listening or the students may be looking at you but their minds are wandering. Iba talaga yung... face to face 'di ba. Sabi mo nga pati body language indicative of... whether they are in... or they are out

Researcher	Yes po. Participant 3, a while ago you mentioned that you've been maximizing zoom, but aside from zoom during the pandemic, nagopen na rin po ba kayo ng other mode of communication with them must active na po ba sa e-mail. Ano po yung adjustment natin when it comes to platforms of communication with your students.
Participant 3	Well, I think... kasi during the administrators meeting. We shift from one platform to another, no, and for a person like me who is not techy. Nahirapan ako kasi Zoom tapos MS Teams tapos iba nanaman 'di ba? Pero I think I survived. As a matter of fact they we're even teasing me during the meeting, no... na nandun ako sa meeting... na he was able... he was able to manage it 'di ba. So... so yun lang maging mode... communication mode.
Researcher	Ah okay Participant 3, so strictly Zoom, teams, e-mail pa rin po. Social media, no pa rin po.
Participant 3	Wala... wala... I... I... I really maintain as of now na... wala akong chat group except my family. And then wala rin akong Facebook. Uh... just just my preference.
Researcher	Ah yes po. But what about e-mail Participant 3 mas naging active po ba during the pandemic with your students
Participant 3	Hindi
Researcher	Hindi rin po...
Participant 3	Hindi... hindi...
Researcher	Talagang pag meeting, pag synchronous po talaga
Participant 3	Yun lang... oo... oo...
Researcher	Yun po talaga yung best way for you to communicate with them but sabi niyo nga po effective....yes po go ahead po

Participant 3	Kasi outside the classroom or outside the class period, very minimal na yung communication and I had the privilege also of as a senior faculty and as a Dean of being assisted by a young faculty member na siya ang sumasagot ng mga tanong sa Canvas
Researcher	Hmm... okay po.
Participant 3	Kasi nga ang instruction ng management ay Let Participant 3tor Participant 3 rest and just stay at home. Yeah, it's a team teaching, yeah, so.
Researcher	Technically meron po kayong quote unquote assistant
Participant 3	Yeah, it's a team teaching, yeah, so.
Researcher	Whenever your students message you po or on Canvas, siya po yung magaassist na sasagot. Ganon po yung naging routine.
Participant 3	Right. Right
Researcher	Participant 3, I want to ask, ano po yung triumphs. Yung mga best moment ninyo when it comes to fully online communicating with your students ano po yung notable aside dun sa fact na ineencouraging niyo po sila with your words and all that.
Participant 3	Yeah, I mean wanna triumphs. Well... I... I think to a certain extent... sa result nung kanilang mga exams uhhh... o kaya participation in the recitation uh... nakuha ko yung interest nila doon sa subject. Yeah, and it's really challenging on my part to say I stopped teaching anymore on computational courses in engineering... So the courses that I handled were purely qualitative ones and some students may find them boring, like engineering ethics, right, to discuss about ethical issues, ethical concerns of engineers in the workplace, alam mo ang mga engineering students pag walang number parang hindi sila nagkakainteres di ba? Lalo na when it comes to participating in the discussion or answering case studies, akala nila hindi mahalaga sa engineering yun and I think the triumph is even in those courses that are not popular to them I think I saw their enthusiasm and I showed... I... I saw also their appreciation of what I thought them.

Researcher	Okay. That's good to know. Kasi pag sinabi pong engineering subjects automatically mahirap na pero with... with your approach Participant 3 interesting talaga for your students. What about the struggles naman po Participant 3. Ano po yung mahihirap na stories na naencounter po ninyo during the pandemic online communication with your students.
Participant 3	Ah... Well, actually since I was assisted by a young faculty member, but... I'm I'm always present actually in the platform, except that I will only be asked to give... I would say supplementary lectures or main other materials. Ang nakita kong challenge ay yung integrity nung exam. Nakikita ko rin, how my assistant would call their attention if they are not looking at their, I would say screen looking somewhere else as if somebody is assisting him or her 'di ba. Yun ang mahirap no hindi mo makita ng sabay sabay lahat ng estudyante mo habang nageexam so you have to go from one student to another for a group of students and you focus your camera there and see if they are following the instruction. Right?
Researcher	Yes po. Ah okay po But Participant 3, I want to ask also, for you po kasi of course, even if you have assistant very hands on pa rin po kayo when it comes to dealing with your students, I want to ask po if you think that fully online communicating with your students is difficult. Para sayo po ba mahirap siya? Or madali?
Participant 3	Mahirap.
Researcher	Bakit po mahirap?
Participant 3	Sabi ko nga, lalo na kung hindi nakaon yung camera... hinid mo talaga... di ba sabi mo nga yung body language, yung expression nila etcetera, mahalaga yun sa communication eh. Na makuha totally... kung, let's say na... na may problema na yung estudyante right and... minsan gusto mong iextend your support mo pero you are only limited with using words, wala ng mga gestures minsan a tap on the back or you know yung mga ganon. Lalo na kapag ah... kapag may problema yung estudyante at umiiyak di ba? Yun lang, nakikinig ka lang parang helpless ka na you want to reach out pero limited ka lang. Yung ang mga difficulties kasi ang mga... ang communication kasi hindi lang naman hearing and seeing. A lot more than that. So I think yun yung problema ko sa online

Researcher	Participant 3 a while ago you've mentioned na may student ka pong nag open up sainyo, ano po yun... tapos po umiyak...
Participant 3	Yes during the pandemic. Bakit siya magdadrop yung subject. A more personal problem di ba...
Researcher	Opo opo
Participant 3	And ayun so
Researcher	Opo sige po go ahead
Participant 3	Yeah, as of now, wala na akong balita kung nakabalik siya sa face to face school or totally, hindi na niya tinapos yung pagaaral niya.
Researcher	Okay. So Participant 3, since may ganon ka pong experience, masasabi po natin na you're the type of faculty, and at the same time administrator that your students can easily open up to when they have problems may experience. recurring po ba yung ganong experience?
Participant 3	Yes oo. Sa buong buhay ko bilang isang teacher, administrator... ah *light chuckle* sabi nila meron daw akong magnet sa estudyante. Meron daw ako charisma. Any student would feel at ease when they talk to me.
Researcher	Okay po... Okay po...
Participant 3	Eh di ba dati kinakatakutan mo sa dean
Researcher	Yes po
Participant 3	Baliktad naman saakin, hinahabol ako
Researcher	Ah okay.

Researcher	For you, Participant 3, what made it different? Kasi po di ba when it comes to position, students get easily intimidated. Ah okay pag mataas posisyon naghehesitate sila to approach, but with you po it's different. What made you... a different type of administrator that your students easily approach you when it comes to like personal problems ano po yung satingin ninyong iba?
Participant 3	Yeah, kasi I always insisted na... even that I am a Dean or administrator. I always make it a point, pre pandemic even pandemic na meron akong assigned subject. Na hindi lang ako yung taong laging nasa office na dean pero nakikita nila ako sa classroom. Siguro sa classroom nakikita nila yung personality ko. Na masyadong approachable, understanding pero firm. Alam nila yun. Don't mess up with me. You will be in problem in trouble. Which means, gawin mo yung dapat mong gawin, you're OK. Pero kung meron kang maling ginawa then you have to face the consequence.
Researcher	Hmmm... Okay
Participant 3	And and also, I am involved in student organizations, even if I'm a dean. I am a faculty adviser of an organization. So nakikita nila ako doon.
Researcher	Kumbaga po kahit na nasa posisyon po kayo Participant 3, hindi nawala yun direct touch and interactions sa students ninyo.
Participant 3	Yeah, because I always believe that I am a teacher, even if I'm an administrator and I always insisted that kasi, yeah, when I was in Mapua, the president told me that I should occupy a higher position than the Dean. I should be the... one of the vice presidents, and I insisted. Sir pinagisipan ko ng mahabang panahon, kasi gusto ko lang maging teacher sa classroom. So hindi pa ako interesado maging vice president.
Researcher	Based on your answers, Participant 3, can you say na despite na hindi po kayo nag maximize ng social media naging successful yung relationship building ninyo with your students and that's because of your approach and the type of person that you are. Tama po ba, for you Participant 3.
Participant 3	Very true. Yes, I agree.
Researcher	Why

Participant 3	Kasi nga, kahit na...I would say... sabihin na nating... uh... handicap when it comes to these technologies. Pero I would say uh... nagawa ko rin naman ang aking responsibility yung aking mga duties sa estudyante, nakareach out din naman ako although very limited sa social media pero nakareach out ako sakanila.
Researcher	Okay po. Last few questions Participant 3. what did the obligatory online communication teach you when it comes to establishing relationship with your students and from fully online setup with your students?
Participant 3	Uh... Well... Una, whether online or face to face, students will really know and feel.. the kind of person you are. Kahit na online, lalabas at lalabas din yung personality mo. As a teacher, as a person. And so... yun din ang mahalaga at tsaka sa online you have to be very, very careful also. Kapag nagagalit ka...
Researcher	Why po?
Participant 3	Kasi narealize ko minsan nung nag open ng camera ang aking student, katabi niya ang mommy at daddy niya
Researcher	Hmmmm
Participant 3	Nakikinig din
Researcher	Opo opo
Participant 3	Kaya during the graduation, first time ko silang makita face to face. Ipinakilala niya yung daddy niya sakin at ang sabi niya... And sabi ng daddy niya 'Participant 3, I want you to know that you are the idol of my son.'
Researcher	Wow
Participant 3	Ang sabi naman nung son 'that's true sir but I also want you to know na mas idol ka ng daddy ko.'
Researcher	Ay wow

Participant 3	<p>*laughs* eh kasi umattend siya ng lecture ko during the entire term di ba. Yun din... di ba... you have to watch your language, your behavior, di ba, kasi you do not know kung sino yung audience mo. Hindi lang estudyante di ba. The parents. And natuwa rin naman ako dun kasi... uh... nageenjoy sa ganon yung parents... umattend di ba. Uh... yun siguro yung mga lesson na natutunan ko ang... one thing more. Bilang teacher, kahit na sabihin nating at my age... uh... you have to... try other ways of communicating with the students you know hindi lang Zoom, MS Teams, marami pa. Ang natutunan ko dun ay,... as a teacher, you should always be open to new things, changes. Hindi ka dapat masettle na sa 'ayoko na niyan, kayo nalang bahala diyan magretire nalang ako'. Kasi right now even if I'm retired already, nagtuturo ako sa maraming eskwela I teach part time in FEU. I teach part time in the De LaSalle University. I teach part time in Batangas State University and I teach uh... face to face sa alma mater ko nung high school, St. Joseph's Academy. So ibigsabihin ang advantage naman netong online namamaximize ko rin yung reaching out to different students from Senior High to college students to PhD students. Yun ang narealize ko rin na very, very powerful din yung online. And my students in the PhD program come from all over the country.</p>
Researcher	Okay po
Participant 3	<p>Yun yun ang narealize ko nun. And at the same time din, last din, I was able to invite, I would say world experts in different topics. Mga professor from US na nainvite ko na magbigay ng talk and maganda online for free, normally pagnakikita mo sila sa conference before the pandemic, you have to pay for your airfare, accommodations, you have to pay them honorarium but this online nagulat sila na I'm able to invite the... let's say, the President of the American Society for Engineering Education and then the expert in research ethics in the world to give a talk to students and faculty members di ba</p>
Researcher	Opo. connections through online platform is a good advantage po eh
Participant 3	Yes. Madami din akong nagawa through online

Researcher	Now Participant 3, since nung pre pandemic namamaximize po natin si face-to-face, then pandemic shift... total shift po to online, now naman po na nagbeblended learning na, ano po yung qualities na nakuha ninyo or natutunan ninyo during the pandemic that you want to retain now that we are in the blended learning at you want to retire or kung meron po ba kayong gustong tanggalin na. Meron po ba, na qualities or learning?
Participant 3	Well now na we're in blended na di ba, so yeah, it's good in the sense na... I'm able to see the students you are face to face at hindi rin masyadong uh... I would say difficult on my part as a... as a retired faculty na hindi ko na kailangang pumasok five days, 8 hours per day. So... one meeting face to face and one meeting online. So.. pero I make sure na pagprepare ko ng mga ituturo ko, yung mga topics na more effectively kailangan ituro face to face, yung ang nilecture ko face to face. Pag purely informative no, pwede naman yung online. At tsaka ang maganda rin ngayon, uh... kung... me... Unfortunately, last week I had a bad fall and I could not attend to my class... face to face. I shifted to online. So I think maraming advantages na natuto tayong online din.
Researcher	What about po yung practices niyo po when it comes to online communication? Meron po ba kayong ireretain now na meron ng blended learning at ireretire ngayon na blended learning na po.
Participant 3	Ah wala naman. Palagay ko kung ano yung natutunan ko, ginawa ko nung online I will just continue.
Researcher	Follow up question Participant 3, are you still open in terms of learning different let's say for example applications and softwares like for example randomly naisipan po ninyong mag branch out na matutong magmessenger, magcanva, willing pa rin po ba kayo?

Participant 3	<p>Why not, di ba lalo na kung kailangan why not lalo na engineering professional, technology di ba? Why not. Halimbawa, Yeah, I'm trying to learn also how to check my students meeting words using turnitin or the... The last challenge I had was when I read the papers of my students and I started to doubt whether they wrote the essays or not. Then I realize through turnitin that it was made by ChatGPT, right? And so I will talk to some of my colleagues and we discuss on what do we do? Wala pa namang clear policy ang mga school, eskwela tungkol don di ba. And so nakakagulat kasi nakita ko rin na pano mo ba madedetect if the essay is Chat GPT. One is walang citation, pangalawa, pag binasa mo, naghahalucinate si shat.. chatgpt. Hallucination meaning, inuulit niya sa ibang paragraph yung exact words na sinabi niya sa in the earlier paragraph. And then towards the conclusion, uulitin niya nanaman. And then one thing was I asked them to make a book review, and it's a technical book. And then the students submitted the book review without even editing it. And chatgpt said, they said this novel, how can a technical book be a novel? And then towards the last part, meron siyang acronym na ginamit... na sa una sinabi niya kung ano yung meaning nung acronym. Sa huli, hindi niya na sinabi yung meaning ng acronym and chatgpt invited the meaning of the acronym. So I think the students would not defend himself and I said you use chatgpt.</p>
Researcher	<p>So Participant 3, nageexplore na po kayo para mahuli yung mga students na gumagamit ng chatgpt... na questionable... sabi niyo nga po kanina intergrity.</p>
Participant 3	<p>Exactly Yeah, I think in this profession. Teachers should be at the forefront of change. Otherwise, kung ayaw mo na, then you simply have to retire.</p>
Researcher	<p>Hmm... Okay po... Now self-reflection naman po Participant 3, what aspects of your online communication practice with your students you wish you can improve. Meron po ba?</p>
Participant 3	<p>Uh... I would say since I was assisted by a younger faculty, uh... I would say.... Yung more interaction with them through social media. Kasi masyado akong naging limited lang eh. Yung major concern lang yung sinasabi saakin ng assistant ko, yung mga ibang bagay, siya na. So ibigsabihin very... it's a small number of students who are able to reach me for certain concerns.</p>

Researcher	OK, so more interactions with them. Last question, this is the last question paano niyo naman po sa tingin makakatulong yung institution, institutions actually, that you're working for in terms of your improvement when it comes to interacting with your students that they can help you with? Meron po ba silang portion doon that they can help you with
Participant 3	Well, actually, I think the institution should provide, I would say trainings especially to senior faculty members, kasi the younger ones should easily learn and adjust and it takes time for us to really learn these new things. Siguro either tutorial or workshop na kung ano man yung sa tingin nila uh... needs namin... as senior faculty members.
Researcher	Ok, so so continues now workshops, trainings and assistants to the senior faculty. Okay thank you so much Participant 3.

APPENDIX F: Transcription of Interview with Participant 4

Speaker	Statement
Researcher	<p>Thank you so much, Participant 4, thank you so much po. So, before we start with the interview process, please allow me to introduce myself so that you'll get a quick background of who I am as the researcher. So I am Krizelle R. Amoyo, I am currently taking my Master of Development communication in University of the Philippines Open University and I'm currently studying uhm... the experiences and journey of near retirement educators, as I want to help them in terms of not just solidifying their implementation of online classes during blended learning, but at the same time of course support them when it comes to strengthening the relationship, building and connection building with their students in the online platform. That's why I'm conducting a study entitled No teacher left offline: Hermeneutic study of online communication for near retirement educators at universities in NCR. I will be asking you a few sets of questions, but please allow me also to inject or insert questions in between depending on your answer, and I... I know for a fact that your experiences can greatly help me in understanding the phenomenon when it comes to new retirement educators communicating with their students and the obligatory set up during the pandemic. So can we start the commentarial or do you have prior questions?</p>
Participant 4	<p>Wala naman, actually when I first read the title, natuwa ako eh kasi no teacher left online. I know student left behind. No, but for us, for us who are already. It is a yeah, near retirement age, it is yeah... it is something that really we should. I mean, we should be assisted Although... although... on our part, on our end, sige you will know naman later when you ask question. We... we've been, we've been introduced to online teaching even before the pandemic.</p>

Researcher	Yes, for actually I'm also working as the online class coordinator. That's why naghahandle po talaga ako ng faculty, and I'm seeing that there are certain difficulties and triumphs. Distinct po siya eh depende sa age. So I want to make sure na hindi naman po kasi one-size-fits-all yung type of approach sa pagtulong sa mga teachers kaya kailangan po nating iaddressing certain problems depending on their needs. That's why I'm curious po sa kung ano yung experiences ninyo during the pandemic and up until now kung naaapply niyo pa rin po siya. So can we start na po, Participant 4?
Participant 4	Yes sure.
Researcher	Okay po. So once again po, good morning, Participant 4 and first part of our interview, can I ask you po to please introduce yourself? What's your complete name? When's your birthday, your age? And how long have you been teaching?
Participant 4	I am Participant 4. I'm... I have... I was born January 28, 1966. I have been in the teaching ministry for more than three decades, to be exact. Perhaps 35 years. I am on my 35th year of teaching and I... hope and I pray that I could still continue this ministry. I have considered teaching as a ministry already.
Researcher	Wow passion po talaga no Participant 4. Ang sarap pakinggan at nakakainspire po yung 35 years po. And hopefully po maachieve ko rin po yan.
Participant 4	... very very much my profession. I am married to my profession. I did not. I did not marry anymore. No. Why? Because perhaps this is where the good Lord has placed me. I always believe that it is where... you are placed, where you are needed.
Researcher	Wow... wow po... nakakainspire po talaga as a teacher din po ang sarap marinig yun especially from our seasoned and tenured teacher po. Continuing po, in the course of your career, what is your perception of the importance of communication as an educator, especially with your students. Ano po yung kahalagahan ng communication.

Participant 4	<p>It of course it is indeed very important in our profession, in the line of work we are in, It's... it's really very important that we are able to communicate that our students are able to understand us and that we are understood by them. Now there are several forms in ways of communicating with our students. That's why when we shifted online there, in some sort of a difficulty addressing to them. And we also were not able to immediately know... know how they feel because it is not only through spoken words that you are able to communicate you know because we conduct classes online and some of our students cannot... uh... cannot join. With their cameras open like what we are doing right now is we hardly... we hardly are able to see if they understand us. If they are able to grasp and get what we and absorb whatever we are talking about, you see uhm... So it's really very important that we are able to communicate, communicate, head level and heart level as well.</p>
Researcher	<p>Okay po... Head and heart level. Okay po Participant 4 I want to understand during the pre-pandemic, we're fully utilizing face to face type of communication. So, I want to know po ano po yung pre-pandemic routine ninyo when it comes to building relationship and connecting with your students.</p>
Participant 4	<p>First you have to establish the rapport. No, you have to build the trust. Uhm...yeah, I... when... when I went to, I mean this Sultanate of Oman where I taught for 21 beautiful years. No. But prior to that I have been teaching here in the Philippines. No, I have taught... I have... I mean, I have learned. No, I have learned to... Each... to communicate with students from different grade levels. So, you have to adjust to the students level. You know you have to understand where they are coming from. It's always the rule of the thumb. Start from where they are. So that they will understand what you want them to know, what message you want to convey, as well as they are given the confidence to also speak to you so that they will be able to express what they feel you no I do not like to make them feel that uh... I am always the authority in the class, although... although of course, I am their teacher and they have to respect me, but I want them to know that I do respect them too. Also, in my class I always see to it that they are able to talk and that I will be listening.</p>

Researcher	So bale Participant 4 purely face to face lang po talaga yung nangyayaring communication with your students, like in class or face to face consultation during your free time, ganon po ba yung routine natin during the day.
Participant 4	During the pre-pandemic?
Researcher	Yes po, pre-pandemic po.
Participant 4	Actually ganito no, the before... the before I left for the Sultanate of Oman, during the early younger years of my teaching career, usually no usually, it's always in the class, only that we communicate. Why? Because there was no social media yet, there was no social media. Plus, I really value my privacy. When I was a young teacher, I don't like students to see me outside, so I rarely go outside. It will only... It will always be in the school where they can talk to me. It will always be in the school where they can uhm... see me. No, I... I value my free time even during vacant periods, they can't disturb me. But as I linger in the teaching ministry, I started to realize that... I need to be in touch with my students as well, so I have... I have given them my phone number, my... my e-mail address. No, I even responded to their friend requests. Yes no? But I always tell them that I will only make them my friends if they're no longer in school. Because I would like to speak to them personally. If there are things that they would like me to know or if there are uhm... information or messages outside school, no, outside school stuff, no, But not school related and they want to communicate with me. They can always ask me, even if they're no longer my students. No, but I'd like to do it personally. For as long as they are still in school, but once they graduate from the school, then that's the only time I could accept their friend request.
Researcher	Okay po...
Participant 4	Tamo si Lysa, si Lysa Parole, She's one of my many friends in the social media, so whenever I see milestones that they have achieved, yan, I don't fail to... to greet them. I don't fail to say hello to them, no, despite my busy schedule.

Researcher	Ok po, so bale po Participant 4, ang system pre-pandemic is uhm... before hindi po talaga kayo nagsosocial media because you want to give a personal touch when it comes to communication and make it face to face. Pero eventually po mas naging open na kayo but nag rule pa rin po kayo or nagset pa rin po kayo ng boundary na magiging friend niyo lang po sila, in the online platform once they graduated.
Participant 4	And I don't like them posting things that are... not wholesome. Sabi ko nga If you want to really invite me as your friend, I should not see anything that is not wholesome, as far as you posting things are concerned, no, kasi anything you post online is forever. They know that they know that, yes. They know that.
Researcher	Okay po. So Participant 4 masasabi po natin na pre-pandemic na gumagamit na po kayo ng social media...
Participant 4	Yeah...
Researcher	But with restrictions. Paranag ganon po?
Participant 4	Yes, oo. Yes. siguro no, you know, before I was able to buy high end...hindi pa nga high end 'to eh, phone. Perhaps it took me quite a while nandun pa rin ako sa analog. I used the analog perhaps 2015. It was only... siguro from 2015 that I started using eto na, high end phones. Kasi... what the principle... my principle was for as long as I can call you, you can call me, I can send message you send messages to me. So my my analog phone is fine. But later on I can't take pictures. I can't no record. Very limited. No. Very limited. Besides that yung if you are away, you want to communicate with relatives back here in the Philippines. No, it... it... it limits me. No, it limited me from doing things that other people who have high end phones uh... can... can do. So finally I yielded in.
Researcher	Hm... nag give in na po kayo. So bale po, if we are going to lookback, gumagamit na po kayo ng... ano po yung ways of communication ninyo before, pre-pandemic with your students. Email... yun po ba?

Participant 4	E-mail, e-mail, e-mail, mostly e-mail kasi mas formal yun eh. Mas formal yun. E-mail with their parents tapos with the students so, but of course we want the... the parents also to know because we were handling at that time minors eh. No, senior, junior and senior high. I know we were handling minors and so therefore we were very careful not to just e-mail them without their parents' consent. If it's just very simple stuff. Just tell them personally. Just call them in school and then tell them personally.
Researcher	Ah okay po. So after all the pre pandemic then came the pandemic po. Yung pandemic naman po from fully face to face type of communications. Having our personal type of communication, everyone is obligated to shift to fully online communication. So malaki po siyang pagbabago talaga especially in terms of the educational sector, because of course as teachers nawalan na po tayo ng direct and personal and face to face communication with our students. Now I want to ask Participant 4 in the course of the fully online communication can you share po notable experiences or yung tumatak na storya po ninyo or karanasan during the pandemic fully online communication with your students?

Participant 4

OK During the pandemic period, no. I was in the Sultanate of Oman when it happened. We were forced to transition from the traditional setup to the fully online, though we were already... Little by little, really moving online as we wanted also to keep up with what other schools in the country were doing. No, at the time they were also doing already the transition to online learning, no. In as much as. We also would like to be at par with them little by little. We will be, we've, we've. Been introducing to our students yung Online setup, although not like when it really when and then it really happened when we were forced to close the schools when we were forced to close the schools and we need to really finish the school year. What we did was to look for an avenue whereby we can communicate with our students still and conduct our lessons. So what we did was here. You know, we had this messenger. Created group chat. You see we had group chats but with parents... with parents, you know we... we before the pandemic we had group chats via WhatsApp. That is what we use abroad. Dito yata, counterpart is the Viber ayun Viber. You know what we had there. That's What's up. That's what we use. And we communicate with parents we cause to all our messages through the parent representatives and all parents. Are members of the WhatsApp. We also have WhatsApp group or GC or group chat with our class officers, we just continued... We just continued that one. When we transition to fully online class and then we were able to have an opportunity to use other LMS like we transition to Moodle and what's the other one I forgotten talaga eh we did series of trainings in order for all of US faculty members to be able to navigate the LMS. Google Meet yeah, it was very helpful. At tsaka itong Zoom. I... I... remember kasi free siya eh limited, you know, even our faculty meetings now were conducted through this video conference. Thanks to Zoom talagang yun yung unang una na nakatulong saamin apart from Google Meet. Pero... Ah ayun, Class Dojo. Yun Class Dojo, we used Class Dojo. And yan sina Lysa, they used Class Dojo inabot sila niyan eh. I think they were in Grade 9 if I... I'm not mistaken. They were in grade 9 when that happened. So we were forced to really finish the school year because we were already in the last stretch when schools were forced to be closed. No, and we... we need to abide by. It no say. We wouldn't like. To also put our students at risk, you know. So you we communicated via the class Dojo which was the adapted learning management system at the time apart from WhatsApp group Group Chat yan and we

	<p>were able to really course through... I mean by this message messaging apps, our messages, no, they they would always be able to We have modules that we give them we provide them we... we're able to explain although syempre we also were aware of the screen time for our students. So yeah, we had synchronous as well as asynchronous set up so that we will not be making them feel that... it's it's too tiring. No especially for the young people. Lalo na yung mga nasa KG (kindergarten) talagang the parents need to assist them. They they they were able to do such kasi... because we were locked down, kasi kung nag locked down dito sa Philippines. We also experienced such... when we were away. No, we experienced such. Also, no, even among... yung mga colleagues... us know what I said a while ago, we conduct meetings we had series of meetings via video conference app ito Zoom was very helpful as well as Gmeet, Google Meet.</p>
Researcher	<p>Okay po, now I want to ask Participant 4 a while ago you've mentioned a pre pandemic personal po talaga yung communication niyo with them, so I assume na mas close po kayo.</p>
Participant 4	<p>Ay oo</p>
Researcher	<p>Sure po go ahead</p>
Participant 4	<p>Yes Ms. Amoyo, Kasi You know, there were only two sections, no the most 2 sections per level per... per grade level. And like here, you know the 10 sections, so. Dito the most na yun 3... 3 sections and usually my students ako hawak ko Senior High at junior high. From grade 7 to grade 10 hawak ko yun. Talagang close... talagang close No, you cannot really avoid na si ma'am yung teacher ko, si ma'am ulit ang teacher ko, ay si ma'am ulit yung teacher ko... depende eh no. Pero wala silang choice no. They need to... uh... kami kami lang nagiiikutan so... katulad ni Lysa Grade 7 teacher niya ako sa asian history, pagdating sa economics, sa grade 12 teacher niya ulit ako. Kaya talagang sanay na sila to communicate with us. At kami rin we... we... we all we already know them as well as their parents, no their families. May generations na... yang si Lysa na yung pinaka bunso. Yung kuya niya, yung mga kuya niya dumaan na sakin.</p>

Researcher

Ah so meron na po talaga kumbaga innate attachment and relationship with the students. Since they're bound to be taught by you po. Now nung pandemic po, sa tingin niyo po yung relationship did it got better po. Or parang naging distant na po dahil wala ng face to face communication. For you based on your experience.

Participant 4

Hindi naman siya naging distant no kasi in sultanate of oman, internet was not as bad. Sorry ha as it is here as it is here no. Walang naging connection problem. That's why when I went back home at naririnig ko sa mga students ko na naglalag. merong connection issue. Those things were unheard of. Sabi ko nga I'm finally back. Nandito na nga ako sa pilipinas kasi sorry kasi doon walang issue about connection. No, talagang kaya there's no reason for them not to be able to communicate. Mas naging, mas naging ano siguro... kumbaga... frequent... kasi apart from apart from the classes, no apart from whatever we give them during class periods. No, we always see to it. That they're OK. Kasi pandemic yun eh, those were the years, not those And the years that you really want and you really wish that everybody's OK. Kaya from time to time pag may naririnig kami na parent na merong COVID I don't get to... we really see to it na 'oh ang mga bata kamusta?' How are you? How are you coping? Sinong tumutulong sainyo? How are you able to get food? Kaya mas naging constant, mas naging close. Even among colleagues, no. na araw araw, minuminuto, kahit dito sa Pilipinas no, mga kapatid ko oh kamusta na mga pamangkin ko It thanks to the modern technology kasi kung wala nun isguro iniisip ko na... magoverthink na kamusta na kaya yung...kaya salamat sa Panginoon kasi may technology na ganon na in, in seconds we are we were able to really find ways in order to really know how. How well we are Doing and how is each other? No, kamusta kami, kamusta ang mga bata, ang mga estudyante. Yung mga umiiyak na they don't get to see us. Yung una kasi, ganto yan eh no syempre nangangapa din kami as to how to reach out to our students kasi nga hindi rin namin alam papaano yung full online. Everybody lahat naman eh, lahat naman eh, all over the world no yung talagang full online. Sige may online class pero hindi naman talaga full soo, what we did was talagang nagbibigay kami, nagpopost lang kami, nagpupublish lang kami ng mga works and they only open the work no and we were told by their parents. Ms or Ma'am, iyak ang mga anak namin kasi they don't know how to... lalo na yung mga bata, lalo na yung mga bata, sa high school hindi kasi sila na yung magsasabi sayo na ma'am pakita ka naman, ma'am online naman tayo, ma'am ano naman tayo, and I give in, I give in kasi that is also one way of keeping our sanity. Kasi nag ooverthink ka na na ano kaya kung saakin dumapo yung Covid? Sa pamilya ko kumabit yung Covid, so to get that off your head no, sige magkita kami ng mga bata kahit online. Kya kahit

	<p>kwentuhan lang na ma'am alam mo ba marunong na akong magbake, mam may bago na akong kanta sa spotify, yung mga trivial stuff na I don't. I don't usually entertain. I don't usually entertain. Kasi syempre no, nung mga panahon na walang ganyan no, why would I entertain such stuff, do it sa mga kaibigan mo but not to me, Pero during that time, mas naging mahaba pasensya ko eh, talaga sige no, sige ano yang binebake mong yan, ano yang inaano mo, just to show na parepareho kaming maging okay, maging fine. Sabi ko nga sayo hindi naging problema yung internet, nakatulong talaga siya because we were able to really see... aba'y nakita ko yung bahay nila kasi we don't get to visit their house. Kasi busy kami sa school no and there there were no reasons for us to visit them except on important occasions. Syempre dahil ito eh nakavideo conference kami, we get to see their house. Ma'am sabi ng mom ko hi daw. Kmausta po kayo ma'am, mga ganon ba. Things like that. Mas naging okay ang communication daily, really naging communication... naging okay no, hindi na siya naging formal na... kasi even sila no even in their house dresses pag walang klase, pero pag may klase they have to be in their uniform, pero pag walang klase I let them dress down, ako rin namna no. ako rin naman.</p>
<p>Researcher</p>	<p>Parang mas naging relaxed yung relationship po, parang it's a way for you to cope up din po no, both ends on the situation. Actually nga po Participant 4 I was about to ask, if your approach changed po from pre-pandemic to pandemic pero nasabi niyo naman po talaga eh parang mas nastrengthen po talaga...</p>

Participant 4	<p>I became more lenient, I became more patient, I became more... perhaps yung... kung ano na talaga ako... mabiro... mabiro kasi akong teacher eh, pero wag mo akong gagalitin kahit tanungin mo kay lya ehno, Wag mo kong gagalitin kasi pag seryoso tayo, seryoso tayo, pero mabiro akong teacher eh siguro mas naging mabiro ako at tsaka they were able to really see the uh... the other side of me na si ma'am pala kahit ganitong stuff she will entertain kasi akala nila dati... akala nila dati... akala nila dati na pag ganito wag nila bibiruin. Minsan nga pag pinatawag ko sila, kunwari, lya I want to see you, I want to talk to you, nako lagot may ginawa ako, sabi ko yun na ba yung dating ko I just want to talk to her because I want to know how she feels or what was the reason why she suddenly got this grade no not particularly her nagamit ko lang yung pangalan pero usually may ganyan ako na... anong tawag dun... may ganyan akong reputation sa klase, sa school no. But, but, as you get older natetame ka rin eh na if my previous students will see me now sasabihin nila sakin ngayon na ms hindi ka ganyan dati but talagang as you get older you become tamed, mararanasan mo rin yan, you are a teacher yourself, ngayon na nasa college ako no, actually may I share no, sorry</p>
Researcher	Go ahead po appreciated po yan

Participant 4	<p>Free ko lang... actually gumagawa ako ng grades eh. Ngayon na nasa college na ako, bumalik na ako ulit dito sa Pilipinas at salamat sa Panginoon kasi he gave me an opportunity to teach again... sa.... Eto na nasa college na... I'm... I'm able to see that there's not much difference when it comes to college students and that of the senior high and junior high students as far as responsibilities concerned and I believe na we, we teachers need to really count on them accountability and responsibility as well. Perhaps because the students I'm handling right now are products of the pandemic period. The gap there is really a gap from what they should learn from what they should have learned during the time that the pandemic happened. What they must have learned already, you know today and we need to. We really need to bridge it. No, I had a difficult time. No, I thought all the while they knew it already. But unfortunately, wala pala talaga. you know, like what I said. Saating mga guro, the rule of the thumb is start where they are No, you cannot just fill in lots of information to them. They can't understand you. They can't understand, you know, they will not really... uhhh... learn. Mafustrate lang sila, ikaw din as a teacher You will also be frustrated. So lagi kong sinasabi sa mga colleagues na mas bata, kasi ako na yung pinakamatanda ngayon sa college eh no, na wag tayong mag puno ng tubig, kung ang balde, the pail has holes. let let us first patch the pail before we can put water into it.</p>
Researcher	<p>Pag kayo po talagang mga experienced na teachers, nakakainspire. Participant 4 I want to ask, during the pandemic, during the fully online communication with your students, for you, ano po yung triumphs, pinaka rewarding, wins po ninyo or achievement during those 2-3 years of fully online communicating with them.</p>

Participant 4

That they became independent. That they became independent. Kasi they are on their own eh. That's the fact. Those people, those young people who seldom are heard during the traditionally set up the pre pandemic period kasi di ba, a class of 40, 25, 30 students yeah, you will not be able to hear them talk in one in 1/2 period. But during the pandemic online class, WOW, I was able to motivate everyone to speak. Kasi that brought out the talkative side of them. Yung... yung... talagang during the class. Online to ah, I was able to really listen, you know, and we were able to hear students who seldom talk when they during the time that it was not online, you know, and I was really surprised na talagang independent na sila, you just give them minimal instructions and they will be able to follow they will be able to follow triumphs, you know another another thing yung They were also able to. Become more creative, they were already creative but like for instance, you know, may binigay kaming project... during the pandemic, the pandemic period curriculum which no longer has yung... yung... di ba they have trimmed it They have trimmed it minimum MLMELC no. Because of that we are able to really concentrate on what were the essentials and the enduring. you you lessons that you know they will be able to really use even if they're no longer in that same grade level and we trimmed it down to lessons that will no longer be repeated, although it there will be lessons that will be repeated, it will be via increasing complexities. Kunwari sa mga Language teachers you have to repeat nouns again in the next grade level, but it will be in a higher Or in increasing complexities, no. So we always sit down. Kaming... kaming mga teachers We always sit down so that we would be able to give them things that will not really bombard our students in in taking a lot hindi proket online to hindi tayo maguusap, lalong malilito yung mga bata. So if we could align our curriculum in such a way, now let's say for example, ako social studies teacher ako eh no, you know, so if I will be giving them a performance task, I have to see to it that that performance task is aligned with what others do. What other colleagues are teaching. You know, if we can give one performance task and a student will be able to Already hit 3-4 subjects via one performance tasks, So that they Could give their best at talaga nga namang matutuwa ka sa kanilang performance. You know, like for instance. May I share? One performance Task I gave to Grade 8 ko kasi Asian history yun no I... I... told them to have... kasi Asian history sila eh you know that they

	<p>have to be tour guides. they have to pretend that they are owners of a... a travel agency and so the continent of Asia was divided into 5 geographical regions. You know, so one group. Had let's say for example East Asia, the other group North Asia. So, I gave them I'm uh... kunwari I'm a tourist who would like to avail of their services so how are they going to promote their travel agency given the fact that I only have this much money no ito lang yung budget ko. So ano yung itinerary ko And what places will I be visiting? So na hit ko na yung math dun kasi may budget ako eh. They have the budget and they have to make sure that it's within the budget that I gave them and also social studies because they they will be telling me places that I need to visit. Because they are going to present dun naman sa language or communication arts naman so kaming tatlo naman sa subjects yun na yung performance task namin.</p>
Researcher	Parang collaboration po
Participant 4	<p>Yes correct ka diyan, collab kami so that the students will not be saturated. They were able to unleash yung talaga very creative sila tapos yung sa computer teacher nila gumagawa kasi sila ng mga brochure. Nakakatuwa... nakakatuwa... so yun yung mga triumphs talaga. Yun yung mga triumphs na talagang We were very, very proud of especially sa mga estudyante. Sila rin eh talaga tuwa sila kasi they weren't able... They were not expecting that. They'll be able to do that.</p>
Researcher	<p>Now what about Participant 4, personal triumphs? Kasi napapansin ko po talaga sainyp Participant 4 parang students first before yourself kaya what about personal triumphs?</p>
Participant 4	During the pandemic?
Researcher	Yes po

Participant 4	<p>Ako rin, I was able to really... uh... maximize the time. Plus the fact that... hindi kasi ako aware that much about the apps that are available. So all the available apps that there are, natuto ako on my own with the help also of young... younger colleagues na gumamit ng interactive apps like for example quizzies, kahoot, poll everywhere, yung mga madalas na ginagamit namin, ed puzzle, ano pa yung mga apps na we were able to really explore no. At first no, noon, pre pandemic, iniisip ko waste of time lang yan eh imagine magseset up pa kami ng ganito, ganyan tapos it will take much of my time, tapos nung pandemic, wala talaga, I explored everything there are to explore. Tapos yung mga webinar, yung mga nook, yung mga massive only courses na free naman, salamat sa Diyos na merong ganyan, coursera I availed. I availed of those kasi gusto ko rin to keep up with our students. Kasi say I refuse to still hang my jersey, kung basketball player ako, I... I refuse to still hang my jersey kumbaga... ayokong...uhm... I will approach retirement na ganon nalang na sige I own I have reached this age already. I'm way over the hill. I don't need to really prove anymore myself, so I will not any more study this no because hindi kasi ako ganon because those those new stuff still excite me. Excited pa rin ako sa ganon no. Even if the teacher is going to teach me or the people who are going to teach me are way younger than I am, okay. Okay yun. Gusto ko yun. Actually sa mga bata, kasi gustong gusto kong maggitara, so whenever I see them strum the guitar 'turuan mo nga ako', 'sige ma'am kapag free time'</p>
Researcher	Lifelong learner po kayo Participant 4
Participant 4	Ano yun?
Researcher	Life long learner
Participant 4	<p>Because I also want them to become lifelong learning, but you cannot teach them what you do not practice. You have to walk the talk. You have to walk the talk. Like if... if you want them to learn, they have to see it in you no. I always... I always tell them values are caught not taught. So if they see that I put a premium on education. They have to really see that I put a premium on education hindi ko lang sasabihin.</p>

Researcher	What about po struggles? Of course kung merong advantage, good side, meron din pong bad side, ano naman po yung struggles or side difficulties during the fully online communication with your students? Sabi niyo po, internet is not a problem eh, ano po yung other... other problems po.
Participant 4	24/7 ka bukas
Researcher	Talo pa po ang 7/11

Participant 4	<p>Nawala na yung privacy mo, parang every now and then yung telepono mo. Parang opps may message no. Wala kasi that is it no. Pero I don't consider it as a disadvantage no, kumbaga yun nga lang no, minsan sinasabi namin sa mga colleagues namin na slow down, baka nagkakaroon ng information overload ang mga estudyante natin and we have to follow yung sinasabi ng international law with regards to yung privacy is concerned. Kasi sa sobrang excited si teacher na popost niya online what should not be posted. Yan very careful kami, very careful kami sa data privacy. Syempre there, there are things that we do not know yet. we need to really get the consent of the parents. Dati hindi naman eh no kasi we don't conduct classes online, but now we conduct classes online. We have to get the consent of the parents, so we have to really make sure that we... we make them know what we're doing now. Yan yung mga struggles especially among non Filipinos kasi we cater to non Filipinos as well. They are non Filipinos, no they're not Filipinos who cannot understand no, who cannot really understand, and uhm... they do not really know how to adjust, you know, ang hirap nila magadjust. So despite the fact na online na kami and it's more convenient for them, There there are some requests that we get na kung pwede turuan sila but they have to come to school pero syempre takot pa kami to come to school na baka makahawa, kasi that time talagang nakakatakot pa to be really out and to be in school. Kaya ang una namin teacher... ang unan namin estudyante, mga magulang eh. So that will be... So that they will be able to guide their students no, their kids kasi syempre .. they are our... I mean they are our helpers no, we will not be able to achieve success without their help. You know their cooperation, their uhm... assistance were badly needed. Kaya When we shifted fully online, we had series of meetings with them so that they would understand also their important roles. You know, our successes were shared with them kung hindi dahil sakanila din, kung hindi dahil sa kanila we would not have made it.</p>
Researcher	Yes po. Partnership po talaga eh...

Participant 4	Partnership talaga. Yun yung mga disadvantage talag ana nakikita ko. At tsaka yung... yun nga very... katulad niyan nagattend pa kami ng mga... So that we will be well versed in Google, you know, yeah nag enroll kami ng...Google, nag pa Google certify kami. Nag pa MS teams certification kami now. Natutuwa naman kami sa school kasi they supported it. They paid for it. Pati gadget kasi we have to upgrade our gadget kasi syempre nag oonline class ka tapos yung laptop mo, gasgas na gasgas na nasisira and we were very thankful na talagang they helped us to procure the gadgets that will last siguro half a day no, kaya may mga laptop kami na pang gamers.
Researcher	OK, well now in general I want to ask po Participant 4, after your experience of fully online communication with your students, nagbago po ba yung perspective ninyo, you know when it comes to Relationship building with them. Or is it the same?

Participant 4	<p>Yes. If there are changes, no it it became more. It it the relationship became closer. Yung we were able to build the relationship. More meaningful and deeper, more deeper and more meaningful relationships. Not only with students, but also their parents and colleagues. Like us, even friends, no friends who we were not able to communicate with for such a long time We were able to, you know, reach out to them. Sabi ko nga hindi lang to magiging because of the pandemic. Lifetiem na to kaya dumami yung... dumami na yung friends ko sa facebook kasi hindi, totoo. Kasi di ba sabi ko nga sayo, sa sobrang kabusuhan, sa sobrang kabusuhan sa school no talagang school bahay school bahay school bahay, hardly that I was able to have the chance na makausap sila. Dati hindi ko pinapansin yang kdrama eh, whenever students, totoo, whenever I hear students kapag dadaan ako whenever I walk past them sa hallway pre pandemic tapos they talk about the kdrama and kpop, talagang nagcicinge ako and they would know. 'naririnig tayo ni ma'am' 'naririnig tayo ni teacher', kasi alam nila na hindi ko papatulan yun eh. Pero nung nagpandemic, nung nag pandemic, isa na rin ako sa mga nanood na 'ano ba tong kdrama na to , masasabi mong late bloomer ako. So nakinood na rin ako so that I'll be able to understand it, their language, may mga termino sila na hindi ko maintindihan or understand eh no, so ano ba yang lingo na yan? I know no I do. I do speak the lingo. It's just so they would feel that I do understand them. Kasi hindi yun sa bumaba ka, there's nothing wrong na bumaba ka dun sa level nila as long as you are able to make them feel that you understand them. Ako importante sakin na ang estudyante ko na sabihin na 'di ko makalimutan tong teacher na to hindi dahil sa marami akong natutunan sakanya kung hindi dahil tinanggap niya ako kung sino ako. Naniwala siya saakin.' Gusto ko yun eh, yung naniniwala ako sayo kaya kailangan maniwala ka rin sa sarili mo.</p>
Researcher	Sobrang rewarding po makarinig ng ganyan.
Participant 4	<p>Totoo. Kasi yun lang yung pwede mong... sa dami mong estudyante... kasi nga when I was younger no, I was a young teacher, gusto ko kausap yung maayos na bata, gusto ko yung estudyanteng nasa cream of the crop pero syempre no, ito may I just give you an advice as a young teacher.</p>
Researcher	Ye spo go ahead po.

Participant 4	As a young teacher, You have to look out for the three letter L. Among your kids among the students. You have to look out for the Lost the least and the last. Para hindi maligaw yung mga nasa dulo and para hindi... and they don't have much in life, kailangan nila tayo.
Researcher	Thank you so much for that, Participant 4 and now na nabigyan na po tayo ng chance na bumalik, somewhat embracing new normal since we are already applying blended learning, I want to ask if there's anything quality practice during the pandemic that you are still applying now or using now at ano ano po yun at bakit?
Participant 4	Yung, number one, yung pagiging resilient. Yung resilience no. Kasi we can go back again to the pandemic period God forbids no or to anything, no. But we will no longer be afraid. Because we know already how to... adjust naging flexible na tayo. Yung sinasabi na VUCA, yung vulnerability, uncertainty... before talaga we were clueless as to how to go about it before we were really panicking as to how to get through it. Now we will no longer be clueless. We will no longer be panicking. We were able to survive and and online learning is here to stay. Hybrid learning is here to stay. We can no longer go back to the traditional full face to face. You know we we need to really adapt to the changes that are Happening and are taking place. the the best person no having any sabi nga nila If you want to endure, you have to really embrace the changes. You know you have to cope with changes are going to happen and we have to be able to really learn from it. Hindi na pwede yung full, full face to face, you know, so you just fill in the minds and the thoughts and the the thoughts of the students with so many information. Wala na yun, wag na yun, kasi talagang we have proven that it really didn't work. It really didn't work. So ayusin natin yung education system, because talagang the pandemic is what the education system was waiting for so that it could change finally. Finally.
Researcher	Last two questions po Participant 4. Self reflection po. Ano po yung sa tingin ninyo mga bagay na gusto niyo pa pong iimprove, sabi niyo nga po blended learning hybrid is here to stay. Ano pa po yung gusto ninyong maimprove sa sarili ninyo as an educator when it comes to communicating with your students.

Participant 4	<p>The pandemic really humbled me. Kasi I thought all the while because of the so many years that I've been teaching I know already a lot. I was able to realize there are a lot of things that I need to learn and so. I want to really learn more. I want to really be able to contribute more it... It's no longer about the money. You know when I returned here in the Philippines, I... I know that what I have received from the school where I came from will be not... will no longer be the same, than what I was receiving no. But this is where I belong. This is where I belong. Teaching is really... what I want to do. Yeah, if in Case No, I will no longer be... accepted because of the age, no. may retirement period na nga and they will be telling me to retire. I still would like to teach in, in small schools, or perhaps in in barangays where there are students who cannot really afford to really go to a conventional school, you know, I still will be sharing my stuff even even if, let's say, for example, colleagues will be asking me to provide a talk. To teachers know during their inset, I'll gladly do it. I'll gladly do it and I'd like to learn more. Actually ah, I just finished my MA, kasi nga 21 years ago away from the country. You know, I wasn't able to really pursue my MA kasi hindi ako makapag enroll noon kasi I was only get my vacation kunwari every... once... once a year lang tapos one month lang no. But during the pandemic, yan pa isa pang gusto kong ipag pasalamat sa Panginoon, I was able to finish my MA. Kaya walang age, walang age talagang nakakatuwa at nakakabless kasi pinagbigyan pa ako ng Panginoon na makapagtapos ng MA. Kasi na MR ako twice, Na MR ako twice, dalawang beses, sayang kasi paper nalang at tsaka isang subject pero wala eh siguro it wasn't my time yet at hindi niya ako binigo no, I was already on the verge of telling Him na siguro kung hindi ko talaga... hindi talaga para sakin matapos ko yung MA, wala, okay lang yun. Pero hindi eh, binigay Niya eh. Binigay Niya eh. Kaya salamat sa Panginoon.</p>
Researcher	In His perfect timing, timing...

Participant 4	Talaga. Napaka buti Niya. At pati yung mga lagi kong sinasabi sa mga estudyante no, ultimate dream ko was to teach in college hindi ko akalain na ibinigay din Niya. I was already... sabi ko nga eh, I want to teach in a teacher training institution kaso wala pa yun eh. Wala pa ako sa teacher-training institution, gusto ko sana na education students eh kaya lang nandito pa ako sa gen ed eh kaya sa mga colleagues nalang. Sa mga colleagues nalang. Whenever they ask me 'ma'am pano gagawin ko' yun... yun nalang siguro.
Researcher	Nako malaking tulong din yun ma'am. Malaking tulong din yun ma'am
Participant 4	Salamat sa Panginoon kasi kung wala Siya hindi ko rin to magagawa.
Researcher	Yes po. Last question Participant 4, A while ago you've mentioned that you wanted to learn more, I think Correct me if I'm wrong, it's more of skill and knowledge building pa po talaga and you want to contribute more. Now I want to ask now that you're teaching collegiate level or what are the ways that the institution that you're working for can help you in those types of improvement They're longing for it?

Participant 4	<p>I want to write research. I want to do research. You know medyo kinakalawang na ako But I want to join you research team so that I will be able to help produce materials for future teachers to use. At malaking bagay na maitutulong ng institution where I am now to hone my skill to Teach me again to help me again. To go back to Things that I need to be refreshed... I mean I I need refresher course as regards research is concerned. Kaya kailangan ko yun kaya sinasabi ko nga, whenever there are seminars about my research I joined kasi I say I want to learn again and I want to own my skill. Kasi dati, before I left for abroad, I was able to write co write a book, a textbook in history tapos hindi na yun nasundan, I wasn't able to anymore... write again. So namiss ko siya. Gusto ko sa pag retire ko, gusto kong sumulat kaya when there are opportunities for me to attend yung mga seminars, katulad ng rex they look for writers eh, and they train writers, sumasali ako dun. Sumasali ako dun. Kasi gusto ko... I want to go back sa mga dati ko ng alam pero syempre may mga bagay na hindi ko na alam ngayon eh kasi nga nagbabago na, and I'm willing to start all over again, kasi nga mas bata yung nagtuturo, ang mag kasama ko dun mas bata sakin, okay lang. Yun ngang umuwi akodito sabi ng mga colleagues 'ay uuwi na tayo so we will start all over again.' Sabi ko naman We will start from experience. We'll start from experience that should be the attitude because nothing will happen. Yung... yung... dapat... dapat positive ka na ... you need to embrace everything that will come your way. Matututo ka and makakapagbigay ka rin ng kaalaman</p>
Researcher	<p>Last na po ma'am, sorry sorry, what about po yung online communication practices. Paano... paano po kaya makakatulong yun institution na napagtatrabahuhan niyo po ngayon? Sainyo po personally, ano pong assistance or help na need po ninyo..</p>
Participant 4	<p>Siguro yung ano... What do you mean in communicating with our students?</p>
Researcher	<p>Yes po or yung skill po, technological side.</p>

Participant 4	<p>Kasi hybrid na rin naman sa school no. You know we we report on site twice and then the remaining days online. No, they they have. We are able to you know... Have yung... periodic... PDs or faculty development. Professional development sessions. We are able to Share best practices kunwari yung isang college they have this mga... katulad last time no... meron tinuro saamin When do... when we conduct online quiz online exams, how are we going to be able to detect if our students are Opening another window And now we could We could detect if our students are opening another window without us knowing yung mga ganon We, we, we... We are not aware of no, yung IT department taught us that we should not be publishing the quiz, the online quiz or the example early because There are other clever students, yeah, who are able to open it or hack it. And natuturuan na rin kami how to hack para we are able to secure or we are able to secure our our account as well. Tapos yung mga... yung mga dos and donts pa rin na what should be divulged, printed, written, yung mga reminders pa rin na You know that's why we're very also careful in in, in communicating with our students meron lang kaming isang portal where we can communicate with them And the students also have a portal where they can also communicate where they can... parang freedom wall But there is a, of course, my admin, so that unprintable things that should not be placed there, yung mga obscene, you know, they should not be putting there talagang They will be able to really screen and see what needs to be read by the students. May mga ganyan na... Online way of communicating with anyone. Kasi di ba may mga Online teachers evaluation of our part on our end now so that we would know how students see us. So that we would know what improvements we should do now these are the things that the methods, the styles that They are able to learn they're able to be able to They are able to get our Lessons so that is One form of communicating also by through the Online teachers evaluation. Binibigay saamin yan periodic kasi three terms kami eh. So everytime na matatapos yung term, we get to see how our students are able to evaluate US evaluation there even among peers, may peer evaluation din. Sila din naman They give professional development that we ask them to. Kunwari we request for this professional development, kung kaya naman nila, they give,</p>
Researcher	Wow. Very supportive, very supportive.

Participant 4	There are things na hindi kaya, pero if kaya naman ibinibigay. Meron naman open line of communication. Meroong Through our immediate superior push, the immediate superior will bring it up to the, you know, higher ups. Yeah, with proper channeling.
Researcher	Thank you so much Participant 4!